

Validation of innovative binder solution for wooden circular designed products.

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Dedication

To my son Alex Kingswood.

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Abstract

Wood-based panels have been produced since the Egyptian era. Although only bio-based adhesives were used in that period, synthetic adhesives based on formaldehyde overtook the industry during the industrial revolution due to their low cost and better performance of panels fabricated with them especially for outdoor furniture. However, it has been identified that the usage of synthetic formaldehyde-based adhesives can cause nasopharyngeal cancer in human beings due to formaldehyde emissions deriving from wood-based panels or furniture. The manufacturers, as well as the final users, are in the risk group for such exposure. The government advice for the furniture consumers is to keep the windows open for a few days when new furniture is bought, which is not practical in the winter months. On the other hand, industrial standards bodies have established limits for formaldehyde emission from wood-based panels.

The European Commission seeks a sustainable solution for the formaldehyde emission-related issues as well as for shifting the linear economy of 'take → make → use → dispose' process of wood-based panel industry into a circular economy. The waste accumulated can be eliminated by reusing, remaking and recycling. Wood waste contains formaldehyde that was used during the production of the material. When crushed, wood waste, containing formaldehyde-based wood adhesives, generates formaldehyde emissions that exceed the relevant industrial standards. Non-formaldehyde-based synthetic adhesives such as polymeric 4,4'-Methylene diphenyl isocyanate (pMDI) are relatively expensive for applications on an industrial scale though the resulting wood panel show better mechanical and physical properties.

During the process of 'take → make → use → dispose' wood waste ends up in landfill, which causes the release of greenhouse gases such as CO₂ and CH₄ damaging the ecological system. The wood adhesive industry is 65% of all the adhesives in the world. Most of these adhesives are formaldehyde-yielding adhesives such as urea-formaldehyde. Petrochemicals are one of the main raw materials in the production process of synthetic formaldehyde-yielding wood adhesives. Usage of deploying petrochemicals is another environmental hazard associated with the wood industry.

Bio-based adhesives are renewable, formaldehyde-free and recyclable. The study in this thesis reveals the combination of alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate as an innovative binder to make wood-based panels as well as to re-manufacture particleboards. The ability to enhance the mechanical and physical properties of goods made with the novel binder by incorporating synthetic non-formaldehyde-based additives is also shown in the thesis. The novel adhesives were tested with virgin wood particles as well as recycled wood particles, which were originally manufactured with formaldehyde-based adhesives. The adhesive formulation satisfied Japanese industrial standards (JIS A 5908:2015) achieving bending strength of 8.08 MPa and 18.09 MPa with virgin wood particles and recycled wood particles respectively. The samples made by using virgin wood particles can be classified as 'Type 8 particleboard', while the recycled classifies as 'Type 18 particleboard'. The resin formulation also satisfied the other properties such as modulus of elasticity, density, internal bond strength, moisture content and thickness swelling requirements for the industrial standards.

Generally, synthetic additives are incorporated with bio-based wood adhesives in order

to enhance their mechanical and physical properties to reach relevant industrial standards. In this study, tannins, as well-known bio-based wood adhesives, and six different synthetic additives were selected by considering the proteinous nature of the main component of the adhesive formulation. Out of those additives tested, incorporation of 1% (wt.) of polyethylenimine, sodium dodecyl sulfate and diacetin showed increases in the mechanical and physical properties of the bio-based wood adhesive formulation.

The re-manufacturability of particleboards made by using conventional synthetic formaldehyde-based wood adhesives is limited due to the excess content of formaldehyde. Particleboards made with synthetic adhesives as well as bio-based adhesives were re-manufactured over and over again in this study to find the optimal number of cycles that satisfies the industrial standard. The result revealed that only the first cycle of re-manufacturing with bio-based adhesives satisfies all the mechanical and physical properties of JIS A 5908:2015. The samples in the following cycles became more brittle because of the higher content of adhesives already used.

Olive seed flour taken from the waste of the olive oil industry was used as a source to extract tannins. The tannins extract was then used as the bio-based adhesive to make particleboards with virgin and recycled wood particles. The results showed that tannins and other phenolic compounds extracted from olive seed flour can be used as a bio-based wood binder with recycled wood particles to make particleboards that satisfy industrial standards. This unveils the ability to make industrial standard particleboards with the combination of two different waste materials such as olive seed and crushed particles of recycled wood and wood-based panels. The whole process would move the linear economy of the wood-based panel and the furniture industry into a circular economy by showing the ability of re-manufacturing of wood-based panels.

List of Abbreviations

DMA	Dynamic Mechanical Analysis
DP	Degree of Polymerisation
DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
EN	European Norm
E-SEM	Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy
FE	Formaldehyde Emission
FTIR	Fourier Transform-Infrared
HDF	High Density Fiberboard
IB	Internal Bond
JIS	Japanese International Standards
MDF	Medium Density Fiberboard
MF	Melamine Formaldehyde
MC	Moisture Content
MOE	Modulus of Elasticity
MOR	Modulus of Rupture
MUF	Melamine-Urea-Formaldehyde
MWCNT	Multi Walled Carbon Nano Tubes
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
OSB	Oriented Strand Boards
PF	Phenol Formaldehyde
pMDI	polymeric 4,4-diphenylmethane diisocyanate
PVAc	Poly(vinyl acetate)
SA	Sodium Alginate
T_g	Glass Transition Temperature
TMA	Thermal Mechanical Analysis
UF	Urea Formaldehyde
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
WBP	Wood Based Panels
WG	Wheat Gluten

Introduction to the Thesis

In general, the thesis is about developing bio-based adhesive formulations to make particleboards that can be used in a circular economy. This can give more benefits to the consumers of wood-based products and workers in the wood-based panel manufacturing industry by eliminating exposure to the toxic formaldehyde emissions deriving from the formaldehyde-based resins used during the manufacture of wood products. In addition to that, a circular economy in the wood-based panel industry would be beneficial for the environment as not as many trees would need cutting, therefore reducing global warming. The use of fossil fuel necessary to make synthetic wood adhesives can be minimised by moving into renewable bio-based adhesives.

The thesis explains the mechanism of wood adhesion in its first and second chapters. The analysis of adhesive strengths is explained in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 describes the different types of bio-based wood adhesives that can be used in the wood-based panel industry. The methodological approach used in the study is explained in Chapter 5 which also compares the methods used in research and the development sectors in the particleboard manufacturing industry.

The next chapter (Chapter 6) illustrates alkali-treated wheat gluten with sodium alginate as an innovative bio-based wood binder used to make particleboard samples. The binder was used with virgin wood particles as well as recycled wood particles. The mechanical and physical properties of particleboards made with wood-based binders can be tuned and enhanced by using additives, cross-linkers, hardeners and dispersing agents. In addition to this, catalysts can be used to lower the applied pressure, temperature and cure time during production by offering cost benefits for the manufacturer. A database that can be used to identify the appropriate and available additives is reported in Chapter A. Seven different additives were incorporated with the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate binder developed in this thesis to enhance the mechanical and physical properties of wood panels and this work is described in Chapter 7.

Chapter 8 explores the re-manufacturability of particleboard by using the bio-based binder. Tannins extracted from olive seed flour as a non-food input were used to make particleboards by using virgin and recycled wood particles. Chapter 9 explains the extraction process and the mechanical and physical properties of the samples made using the extracted tannins-based adhesive.

Chapter 10 expresses a general overall summary of the results obtained and the effects of the additives used with the alkali-treated wheat gluten with sodium alginate binder. A general conclusion and the potential impact of the work are discussed in Chapter 11. A list of publications is included afterwards. The appendices included at the end contain chemical equations, laboratory data and a table of properties of adhesives. The glossary and the index included helps the reader to navigate the document.

Chapter 1

Introduction

“Wood is universally beautiful to man. It is the most humanly intimate of all materials.”

Frank Lloyd Wright

1.1 Introduction to the chapter

Adhesives are the most vital factor to retain the structures of wood panels such as plywood, medium density fibreboard (MDF), particleboard, and oriented strand boards (OSB). The science of wood adhesion and the ways of minimising environmental damages that are happening due to synthetic adhesives are discussed in this first chapter. This chapter explains the importance of switching to bio-based wood adhesives from synthetic wood adhesives. It expresses the effect of toxic gas emitted by synthetic wood adhesives, as well as the poor re-manufacturability of wood-based panels fabricated with them. The ways of minimising environmental damages that are happening due to synthetic adhesives are discussed in this first chapter.

1.2 History of wood binders

Wood and wood products played a major role throughout human history. Ancient Egyptian and Roman period veneered furniture can be found in museums [1, 2]. Egyptians glued a thin veneer of wood to a thicker plank [3]. Plants and animal sources have been used to make adhesives in ancient times [4, 5, 6]. Beeswax was used to bond feathers to arrows by early hunters. Gluepot and brush to bond veneer to a plank of sycamore were shown in carvings done in 1300 BC in Thebes Greece [7]. Crude animal and casein (milk protein)-based glues were used to laminate wood for bows, wood veneers, and furniture by Egyptians in historic times [8]. Natural sources were used as the dominant adhesive for wood bonding up to World War II [9].

1.2.1 History of particleboard

Particleboard so-called ‘artificial wood’ was invented by Hubbard in Germany and dates back to 1887. Wood flour and albumin-based glues were consolidated under high pressure and temperature during that period. Production of synthetic resins was improved during World War II [10].

Table 1.1: Components depend on wood bonding [11].

Resin	Wood	Process	Service
Type	Species	Adhesive spread	Strength
Viscosity	Species	Temperature	Shear modulus
Mole ratio of reactants	Moisture content	Relative humidity	Modulus of elasticity
Tack	Plane of cut	Adhesive distribution	Biological resistance.
Filler	radial,	Open assembly	fungi, bacteria,
Total solids	tangential,	time	insects, marine
Catalyst	transverse, mix	Closed assembly	organisms
Solvent system	Heartwood	time	Percentage of
Age	versus sapwood	Pressure	wood failure
pH	Juvenile versus	Gas-through	Adhesive
Buffering	mature wood	Press time	penetration
Cure rate	Grain angle	Pretreatments	Temperature
Molecular weight	Porosity	Post-treatments	Finishing
distribution	Surface	Adherent	Heat resistance
Mixing	roughness	temperature	Hydrolysis
	Machining		resistance
	damage		Ultraviolet
	Contaminants		resistance
	Chemical		Failure type
	surface		Dry versus wet
	pH		Swell-shrink
	Buffering		resistance
	capacity		Creep
	Earlywood		
	versus		
	reaction wood		
	Drying damage		
	Dirt		
	Extractives		

Table 1.2: Composition of lignocellulosic materials [16, 17, 18].

Raw material	Lignin (%)	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)
Hardwoods	18-25	45-55	24-40
Softwoods	25-35	45-50	25-35
Grasses	10-60	25-40	25-50

1.3 Science of wood adhesion

Wood consists of extreme chemical diversity and physical intricacy due to its porous, permeable, hygroscopic, orthotropic nature [11]. Bonding wood depends on various factors as shown in Table 1.1 under four categories.

The diverse nature of wood surfaces makes wood adhesion a complex phenomenon [12]. Different types of wood species exhibit unique porosity showing a general mechanism of wood adhesion [13, 14].

1.3.1 Structure of wood

Wood is a green building material that contains about 50% of cellulose, 20% - 35% of hemicellulose, 16% - 33% of lignin on a dry weight basis [15]. However, the composition of the above lignocellulosic materials varies according to the wood material as shown in Table 1.2.

Wood can be defined as a 3D biopolymer composite naturally made by interconnecting a network of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and fewer inorganics and chemicals in the wood that can be extracted by using solvents [20]. The structure of the cell walls is shown in Fig. 1.1. Lignocellulose materials are in the secondary cell wall of wood. The cellulose microfibrils embedded in lignin function in an analogous manner to steel rods embedded in reinforced concrete, as shown in Fig. 1.2 [19].

1.3.1.1 Cellulose

Cellulose has the highest strength in wood fibre due to its high degree of polymerisation and linear orientation [21]. The building block of cellulose, the most abundant organic substance on the surface of the earth is cellobiose which has two sugar units as shown in Fig. 1.3. The average number of sugar units in a cellulose molecule (Degree of Polymerisation - DP) is 10,000 [20]. Cellulose polymers form long unbranched chains while hemicellulose polymers form short branched chains. These polymers are linear polysaccharides. They are encrusted and stiffened by lignin which is an amorphous phenolic 3D hydrophobic adhesive [22].

Figure 1.1: Structure of the wood cell wall [19].

Figure 1.2: Cell wall containing cellulose microfibrils, hemicellulose, pectin and soluble proteins [19].

Figure 1.3: Chemical structure of cellubiose [20].

1.3.1.2 Hemicellulose

Hemicelluloses are polysaccharides and include xyloglucans, xylans, mannans and glucomannans, and β -(1 \rightarrow 3, 1 \rightarrow 4)-glucans [23]. They exist in amorphous form [24]. Hemicelluloses increase the packing density of the cell walls [21]. The most abundant biopolymers in hemicellulose are xylan and glucomannan. Xylans can be found in softwoods (10% – 15%), hardwoods (10% – 35%), and annual plants such as oat spelts (35% – 40%) [25]. The chemical structure of xylan and glucomannans are reported in Fig. 1.4. When compared to cellulose, hemicellulose can be hydrolysed more easily using diluted alkali, acid or enzymes under mild conditions [26].

1.3.1.3 Lignin

Hydroxycinnamoyl alcohols, coniferyl alcohol and sinapyl alcohol, with typically minor amounts of *p*-coumaryl alcohol are the main building blocks of lignin structure [27]. Fig. 1.5 shows their combination in lignin structure. Lignin holds cellulose fibres together acting as an adhesive in the cell walls [28].

1.3.2 Mechanism of wood binding

The mechanism of binding one wood particle to the other can be illustrated with different techniques. A wood binder should satisfy at least one of the bonding techniques mentioned below to make bonds with wood particles [29].

1. Theory of chemical bonding
2. Theory of mechanical interlocking
3. Adsorption theory
4. Diffusion theory
5. Electronic theory

- 6. Theory of boundary layers and inter phases
- 7. Acid-base theory

1.3.2.1 Chemical bonding with wood

Hydroxyl groups of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin (Wood—OH, so-called, cell-wall hydroxyl groups) react with formaldehyde in two steps as shown in Fig. 1.6.

According to Fig. 1.6, formaldehyde can cross-link two hydroxyls groups of wood cells. This process has the ability to bond two wood particles chemically together. Formaldehyde based wood adhesives such as urea formaldehyde, phenol formaldehyde, melamine formaldehyde and melamine urea formaldehyde are used widely in wood adhesive industries due to their chemically bonding ability. Cell-wall hydroxyls can also react with acetic anhydrides, ketenes, acid chlorides, carboxylic acid, isocyanates, methyl iodides, alkyl chlorides, β -propiolactone, acrylonitriles, and epoxides [28].

(i) Xylan

(ii) Glucomannan

Figure 1.4: Chemical structure of hemicellulose [26].

Figure 1.5: Chemical structure of lignin [26].

Figure 1.6: Reaction of wood with formaldehyde [28].

Figure 1.7: Mechanisms of mechanical interlocking between substrate and the adhesive [34, 35].

Figure 1.8: Contact angle for Young's equation

1.3.2.2 Mechanical interlocking

Penetration of adhesives into the porous cavities and solidifying to bind two or more surfaces is explained by the theory of mechanical interlocking [30]. The mechanism of mechanical interlocking directly depends on surface roughness [31]. Rough surfaces show better adhesion properties compared with smooth surfaces [32]. Wood particles contain open cells and adhesive can penetrate into the lumen of the cell generating mechanical interlocking at the micrometre scale [33]. The mechanism of mechanical interlocking between the substrate and the adhesive is shown in Fig. 1.7.

1.3.3 Properties of wood binders

Wood is a porous and anisotropic material due to the lumens of its cells which give a better pathway for the flow of the liquid resin into it. When the molecular weight of the resins is higher, pits or lumens can inhibit the flow. This is called the conglomeration of resins. The geometry of the interphase region between wood substrate and the resin depends on factors such as wood anatomy, permeability, porosity, resin viscosity, surface energy, consolidation pressure [36, 37].

The wettability and the roughness are the two main physical factors that affect the quality of the bond. The interfacial tension between the liquid and the solid directly links to the

wettability. The angle that liquid contacts the surface is the contact angle θ as in Fig. 1.8 that can be expressed by Young's equation as shown in Eq. 1.1.

$$\gamma_{lg} \cos \theta = \gamma_{sg} - \gamma_{sl} \quad (1.1)$$

Where,

γ_{lg} - interfacial tension of liquid and gas interface,

γ_{sg} - interfacial tension of solid and gas interface, and

γ_{sl} - interfacial tension of the solid and liquid interface,

For better wettability, the surface must be clean and the $\theta = 0$.

The roughness of the adherend surface enhances the mechanical adhesion making better anchoring. The root mean square roughness (R_{rms}) can be expressed as shown in Eq. 1.2.

$$R_{rms} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i (h_i - h)^2}{n}} \quad (1.2)$$

Where h_i is the i^{th} sampling point feature height value, h is the mean height value, and n is the number of data points [38].

The degree of penetration of the wood adhesive into the porous network of interconnected wood cells represents the performance of adhesive bonding between wood particles [36].

1.3.3.1 Penetration of wood adhesives

The penetration of wood adhesives into wood can be categorised into two groups. The flow of liquid adhesive into the porous structure of wood is called the gross penetration. Diffusing the resins into the cell wall or flowing into the micro-fissures is cell wall penetration [36].

When the consistency (viscosity) of the adhesive increases, the penetration depth decreases at constant pressure. So, the pressure should be increased with the consistency of the adhesive to have better penetration into the wood cell walls. However, too much pressure can make insufficient adhesive to fill the bondline between two wood substrates as shown in Fig. 1.9. The optimum bonding condition of applied pressure vs. adhesive consistency is shown in the shaded area of Fig. 1.10 [13].

The secondary cell walls provide the strength to the wood cell [40]. The S2 layer of the secondary wall is the thickest layer and it is considered as the major component of the cell wall (Fig. 1.1). The structure of it determines the mechanical properties of wood cells [41]. The S2 layer shows the most profound effect when the physical properties of wood are

Figure 1.9: Scheme of determination of area of filled lumens, rays and interphase region. (The urea-formaldehyde penetration is shown in yellow) [39].

Figure 1.10: The relationship between adhesive consistency and bonding pressure for affect on bond formation using thermosetting adhesive [13].

Figure 1.11: Average penetration depth (d_{ap}) (μm) for poplar and UF resin I as a function of the specific pressure during the press process [43].

concerned [22]. So, it is important that the resin penetrates into the S2 of the secondary layer. Urea-formaldehyde resin penetration into wood cells was evaluated by using scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive analysis of X-rays (SEM/EDXA) [42]. Wood is a series of tubular fibres or cemented cells [21]. Therefore, the adhesive penetration into wood can be illustrated in two different radial and tangential directions. The schematic diagram for urea-formaldehyde (UF) adhesive penetration is shown in Fig. 1.9 [39].

UF adhesive resin penetration depths into the poplar wood were evaluated with different pressures. The penetration depths remain the same after the pressure of 1 MPa as in Fig. 1.11 [43].

The resin penetration in the longitudinal direction has the least resistance compared to the tangential direction. The longitudinal penetration goes through a slender tracheid of softwood or vessels of hardwoods [36].

Increase in degree of polycondensation such as molecular size and viscosity reduces the flow-ability of adhesive resin into the wood tissue. This lowers the possibility for penetration (degree of penetration) [44]. Three different viscosities of UF resins were used to find the penetration depths as shown in Fig. 1.12 [45].

Adhesive flow and infiltration into the wood can be measured using X-ray computed tomography and X-ray fluorescence microscopy [46]. Analysing a chain-link of an adhesive bond inferred the weakest link which determines its strength. Chain-link analogy of an adhesive bond is illustrated in Fig. 1.13 [47, 36, 37, 48].

Figure 1.12: Average penetration depth into beech as a function of viscosity (different degrees of condensation) of the three UF adhesive mixes used [45].

Figure 1.13: Chain link analogy for an adhesive bond in wood. (The resin in between two pieces of wood is shown in light blue) [36].

Link 1 - 'The Adhesive Film'

Pure adhesive phase unaffected by the substrate.

Links 2 and 3 - 'Intra-adhesive Boundary Layer'

Adhesive boundary layer which may have cured due to the substrate. (No longer homogeneous).

Links 4 and 5 - 'Adhesive-Adherend Interface'

Interphase between the substrate and the boundary layer. It may contribute to the mechanical interlocking, covalent bonding, or secondary chemical bonds due to electrostatic forces [36].

Links 6 and 7 - 'Adherend Subsurface'

The wood interphase regions are weaker than wood itself [47]. Wood cells in this region have been modified during the process of preparing the wood surface.

Links 8 and 9 - 'Adherend Proper'

This region represents the unadulterated wood [36, 48].

When the properly designed adhesive bond is considered, the structural integrity is lower at 'Links 8 and 9'. It implies that the weakest link is 'wood' [37]. Wetting the adhesive into the substrate assists in spreading and penetration. The best wettability can be obtained when the contact angle of the adhesive liquid to the substrate is zero [36].

Figure 1.14: An illustration of the various defects which might be present in an adhesive bond-line [49].

Table 1.3: Causes of defects in bondline [49].

Defects	Caused by
Porosity	Volatiles, and entrained air in the adhesive.
Voids	Products of the chemical reaction[s] involved in curing the adhesive.
Adhesive cracks	Problems with curing (cure and/or thermal shrinkage) or to large applied stresses, either one-off or repeated (fatigue)
Poor cure	Incorrect mixing of the adhesive system.
Unbonds	When adhesive is applied to one adherend only and unevenly.

1.3.4 Defects of adhesive bondline

Possible defects that can occur in adhesive bondline are illustrated in Fig. 1.14. Each type of defect can occur and the reason for them are shown in Table 1.3

1.4 Synthetic wood adhesives

In the early 1970s, bio-based wood adhesives were widely used to manufacture plywood. The bio-based adhesives were replaced by synthetic phenol-formaldehyde adhesives in the mid-1970s due to their superior bond durability provided by phenolics [50]. Phenolic, isocyanate, epoxy, elastomeric, and amino resin types behave as synthetic thermosetting wood adhesives while vinyl and hot-melts resin types behave as synthetic thermoplastic wood adhesives [2]. Thermosetting adhesives are based on the condensation type of polymerisation reaction where water is eliminated. Thermoplastic resin adhesives are polymerised and then set by losing the dispersing solvent [51]. Formaldehyde-based thermosetting resins are being used more than half by volume of all the adhesives in the world today. That is mainly due to their properties of low cost, highly reactivity, quick gelling and hardening behaviour, a steep increase in bonding strength, ability to mix with additives, hardeners, cross-linkers, and others [52]. The wood, particularly its surface condition, the adhesive resin, working condition, and the process are the main parameters that decide the quality of a bond line of wood-based panels [53]. The uses of formaldehyde-based adhesives in household applications are shown in Fig. 1.15.

Synthetic adhesive resins used for wood can be divided into three major types according to their pH as shown in Table 1.4.

Figure 1.15: Formaldehyde uses [54]
http://www.formaldehyde-europe.org/common_uses.uses.0.html.

Table 1.4: Synthetic resin types [55].

Condition	Type to the resin
Acidic	Aminoplastic resins such as those based on urea and melamine.
Highly alkaline	Phenolic resins.
Neutral to light alkaline	Resorcinol resins, tannins.

Table 1.5: Source of raw materials for the production of the major synthetic wood adhesives [2].

Resin	Ingredient	Source
PF	Phenol	Petroleum
	Formaldehyde	Methanol derived from natural gas
UF	Urea	Natural gas
	Formaldehyde	Methanol derived from natural gas
Isocyanate	Aniline	Petroleum
	Formaldehyde	Methanol derived from natural gas
	Phosgene	Carbon dioxide and chlorine
PVAc	Vinyl acetate	Acetylene and acetic acid (from petroleum)

Formaldehyde-based resins are;

- Urea formaldehyde resin - UF,
- Melamine formaldehyde resin - MF,
- Melamine urea formaldehyde cocondensation resin - MUF,
- Melamine fortified UF resin - mUF,
- Mixture of MF and UF resin - MF+UF,
- Melamine urea phenol formaldehyde resin - MUPF, PMUF,
- Phenol formaldehyde resin - PF,
- Phenol urea formaldehyde resin - PUF [53],
- Phenol resorcinol formaldehyde PRF, and
- Resorcinol formaldehyde RF [2].

The main raw materials of these synthetic adhesives are urea, melamine, phenol and formaldehyde [53]. Synthetic resins and their sources are shown in Table 1.5. Requirements for wood adhesives can be categorised into two groups as general requirements and actual requirements. The general requirements are;

- Composition, solids content, viscosity, purity,
- Colour and smell,
- Sufficient storage stability for given transport and storage conditions,

- Easy application,
- Low transport and application risks,
- Proper glueing quality,
- Climate resistance hardening characteristic: reactivity, hardening, cross-linking,
- Compatibility for additives,
- Cold tack behaviour,
- Ecological behaviour: life cycle analysis, wastewater, disposal, etc.
- Emission of monomers, volatile organic compounds, formaldehyde during the production of the wood-based panels and during their use [56].

The actual requirements in the production and in the development sector of wood adhesives are;

- Short press times,
- Short cycle times,
- Enhanced hygroscopic behaviour of boards (such as better outdoor performance, higher resistance against the effect of humidity and water, lower thickness swelling),
- Cheap raw materials and alternative products,
- Modification of the wood surface,
- Life cycle assessment, energy and raw material balances, recycling and reuse, and
- Reduction of emissions during the production and the use of wood-based panels [56].

1.4.1 Urea formaldehyde - UF

UF resins (so-called aminoplastic resins [57]) constitute about 55% of all wood adhesives to use as a binder or adhesive in particleboard and MDF for composite panels. The chemical structure of UF resin is shown in Fig. B.1. Among all the types of formaldehyde-based resins, UF resins are produced in the highest proportion (55%) as illustrated in Fig. 1.16 [54].

Other than the lack of resistance to moist conditions, the UF resin has many advantages such as lower cost and cure temperature, water-solubility, ease of use, resistance to microorganisms and abrasion [58]. The water-resistance can be improved by adding succinaldehyde into UF adhesive for a ratio of urea:formaldehyde:succinaldehyde to 1:1.3:0.2 [59]. Adding melamine to the UF resin molecules can also be used to increase moisture and water-resistance [57].

Figure 1.16: Product tree for formaldehyde [54] <http://www.formacare.org/>.

1.4.2 Phenol formaldehyde - PF

PF was discovered by Dr Leo Bakeland in 1909 [51] and introduced in the 1930s as the first truly synthetic plywood adhesive [60]. The chemical structure of PF resin is shown in Fig. B.2. It has been shown that the PF resin / phenol-resorcinol-formaldehyde can penetrate the wood cell wall [61, 62, 63]. Plywood manufactured using phenolic resins exhibits superior water-resistance compared to UF [64].

1.4.3 Melamine formaldehyde - MF

MF adhesives are mostly used for exterior and semi-exterior grade plywood and particleboards due to the excellent water and weather resistance of MF [65]. MF resins are more expensive than PF resins [50]. The chemical structure of MF resin is shown in Fig. B.3. The cost of MF can be minimised without changing its properties by adding urea to MF (from melamine:urea, 30:70 up to 50:50, and in some less demanding applications it is 20:80) [66]. Melamine urea-formaldehyde (MUF) prepared by adding urea to MF shows medium thermal resistance compared to the UF and MF resins [67]. The chemical structure of MUF resin is shown in Fig. B.4.

Figure 1.17: Formation of resorcinol-formaldehyde resin [70].

1.4.4 Phenol resorcinol formaldehyde (PRF) and resorcinol formaldehyde (RF) adhesives

Resorcinol adhesives are cold-setting adhesives that show good water-resistance. Resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF) and phenol-resorcinol-formaldehyde (PRF) adhesives are expensive and are used to manufacture structural exterior grade joints at ambient temperature [68]. RF and PRF are mostly being used for the manufacture of laminated lumber beams and finger-jointed products [69]. These adhesives are used when fast or room temperature curing is needed and also when wooden assembly bonded is too thick for sufficient heat to be allowed to cure. The higher price is the disadvantage of the usage of PRF and RF adhesives. The chemistry of the formation of PRF and RF is similar to the formation of PF [2]. The formation of resorcinol formaldehyde resin is shown in Fig. 1.17.

1.4.5 Isocyanate

Isocyanate is a synthetic wood adhesive that shows high bonding strength, short press time, resistance to water, and 0% emission of formaldehyde compared to the traditional water-based UF and PF resins. The disadvantage in the industry is its high price [71]. Polymeric 4,4'-methylene diphenyl isocyanate (pMDI), toluene diisocyanate (TDI), and diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI) are widely used in the wood adhesive industry [72].

Isocyanate is used as a cross-linker to enhance the water-resistance of starch wood adhesive [73]. Pine needles and eucalyptus wood particles in 50:50 were treated with 4, 40 di-phenyl methane di-isocyanate to make particleboard. They exhibited superior mechanical properties [74]. However, the particleboard bonded with eMDI (emulsifiable methylene

diphenyldiisocyanate), a non-formaldehyde resin of an isocyanate type [75] exhibits superior mechanical properties than those bonded with pMDI [76].

Isocyanate adhesives are used in the wood-based panel production industry in the form of water emulsion. Direct emulsion-type isocyanate, polyurethane pre-polymer water emulsion and water-based polymer isocyanate are the three types in use in the industry and they all meet the national standards [77]. Polyurethane polyester elastomer adhesives prepared from natural resource and plastic waste gave superior bonding strength and showed excellent shear strength as a wood adhesive [78]. High-density polyethylene is a non-formaldehyde emitting adhesive that can be used as a wood adhesive to make plywood having comparable mechanical and physical properties to formaldehyde-based adhesives [79]. Palm oil-based polyester polyol in a solventless condition was synthesised from epoxidised palm olein before reacting with pMDI and toluene 2,4-diisocyanate (TDI) to produce wood adhesive with improved mechanical performance compared to commercial wood bonding adhesives [80]. Water-based polymer isocyanate adhesive can be used in the bamboo craft sector [81]. Polyurethane wood adhesives with maximum lap shear strength of 36.8 *MPa* were achieved from bio-polyols (crude glycerol, a by-product of the biodiesel process) through the reaction with isocyanate at an NCO/OH ratio of 1:3. Properties of resulting polyurethane wood adhesives showed good thermal stability, comparable lap shear strength and chemical resistance to petroleum-based analogues [82, 83]. The addition of 20% isocyanate into a colourless, non-volatile and non-toxic aldehyde, dimethoxymethane contributed to cross-linking of urea dimethoxymethane by its reaction with isocyanate to also form urethane bridges. The panels satisfied the JIS A 5908 standard and emitted low formaldehyde [84].

Isocyanate is a synthetic, relatively expensive wood adhesive that does not emit formaldehyde. It gives higher bonding strength, shorter pressing time and better resistance to water as an adhesive. Isocyanate has the ability to blend with some other adhesives to enhance their adhesive performance.

1.4.6 Hot-melt adhesives

The primary uses of hot-melt adhesives are for packaging and in wood for edge veneering and veneer splicing. The advantages of using them are mentioned below.

- Ease of Application via high-speed equipment,
- Formation of strong, permanent, and durable bonds within a few seconds of application,
- No environmental hazard and minimal wastage because of 100% solid systems,
- Ease of handling,
- Absence of highly volatile or flammable ingredients,
- Excellent adhesion,
- Wide formulation possibilities to suit individual requirements, and
- Cost-effectiveness [85].

Table 1.6: Advantages and disadvantages of synthetic adhesives used in manufacturing of wood-based products [88].

Properties	Synthetic adhesives			
	UF	MUF	PF	pMDI
Price	Low	Medium to high	Medium	High
Cure temperature	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Pressing time	Short	Medium	Medium to long	Short
Susceptibility against wood species	High	Medium	Low	High
Efficiency	Low	Medium to high	Medium to high	High
Compatibility with bio-based raw-materials	Medium	Medium	Medium to high	High
Manipulations	Easy	Easy	Easy	Difficult
Resistant against hydrolysis	No	Medium to high	High	High
Use in wet conditions	No	Partially yes	Yes	Yes
Formaldehyde emission	Possible	Possible	Very low emission	No

The wood adhesive industry is about two thirds (by volume) of all the adhesives used in the world. Each year, 11 million tons of UF resins are being sold [86]. The formaldehyde content in UF resin is the highest value followed by PF. The formaldehyde content in virgin wood chips can be taken as negligible in comparison with the formaldehyde content in synthetic adhesives [87]. There are some advantages and disadvantages of using synthetic adhesives as shown in Table 1.6.

1.4.7 Polyester adhesives

Polyester adhesives are relatively cheaper and can be cured at room temperature. Various types of activators can be used to initiate the cross-linking process of polyester adhesives at ambient or raised temperatures. As for disadvantages, they emit styrene and have a low impact strength on the surface [68]. Polyester polyols were synthesised from renewable sources by condensation polymerisation of different dicarboxylic acids and castor oil using green chemistry principles. It was then reacted with MDI and polypropylene glycol and butanediol to prepare a wood adhesive which showed excellent lap shear strength values and good resistance to cold and hot water [89].

1.5 Issues with synthetic wood adhesives

1.5.1 Formaldehyde emission - FE

The annual global production of formaldehyde is approximately 29 million tons [90]. As Table 1.6 shows, widely used synthetic adhesives such as UF, MUF, and PF emit formaldehyde. International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has determined with sufficient evidence that formaldehyde causes nasopharyngeal cancer in human beings [91]. FE comes from the adhesives as well as wood itself [92]. The formaldehyde emission is influenced by exogenous factors and endogenous factors as shown in Table 1.7.

The formaldehyde emission is mainly coming from three sources.

1. Formaldehyde compound in the wood material,
2. Residual free formaldehyde of the formaldehyde-based resin that is not involved in the reaction (The main source of indoor air pollution), and
3. Formaldehyde released by the structural degradation of the wood-based panel used [93].

The FE can be measured by desiccator method [94], gas analysis method (UNI EN717-2:1996) and chamber method (UNI EN717-1:2004) [95, 96, 97].

1.5.1.1 Reducing FE

Synthetic wood adhesive resins can be modified to reduce or minimise FE without degrading the mechanical and physical properties of wood-based panels. FE can be reduced by adding formaldehyde scavengers or by decreasing free formaldehyde in the adhesive [71]. Urea can be taken as the most typical formaldehyde scavengers used in the wood adhesive industry in addition to ammonia and ammonium salts [98]. Charcoal (the best scavenger of all), wheat flour and tannin powder are organic scavengers. The formaldehyde emission can be reduced by 40% by using 5% (wt.) of charcoal [99, 100]. Activated multi-walled carbon nanotubes, carbon nanotubes, and exfoliated graphite nanoparticles behave as formaldehyde absorbent in formaldehyde-based adhesives [101, 102]. Formaldehyde emission can be reduced by adding diphenylmethane-4, 4'-diisocyanate (MDI) into the UF resin mixture [103]. The hardener type associated with particleboards significantly affects the formaldehyde emission [104]. Citric and oxalic acid, in solid form, were used as catalysts in UF resin in the production of particleboard which enhances the internal bond strength and reduces the formaldehyde emission [105]. Although the adhesive with magnesium chloride as a hardener emits more formaldehyde as shown in Fig. 1.18, the adhesive shows the best mechanical properties [104].

Non-volatile and non-toxic aldehyde glyoxal was reacted with melamine to prepare novel melamine-glyoxal resins to eliminate the formaldehyde emission from melamine resin [106]. Formaldehyde emission can also be reduced by adding furfural into UF resin [107]. Aluminium sulphate and ammonium persulphate reduce free formaldehyde in adhesives by 20% (wt.) and

Table 1.7: Factors affecting formaldehyde emission [112, 113].

Exogenous factors	Endogenous factors
Air humidity	Wood species
Temperature	Type of resins used
Air change	Condition of manufacture

Figure 1.18: Formaldehyde emission with hardener type used in engineered wood panels [104].

60% (wt.) respectively [108]. Diatomaceous earth as an inorganic additive can be used to reduce the FE by 45% following addition to the UF resin [109].

Inorganic ammonium salts such as ammonium chloride, ammonium phosphate, ammonium hydrogen phosphate, ammonium sulphate and persulphate can be used to reduce free formaldehyde by acting as accelerators in the resin cross-linking process. Organic additives such as polyvinyl alcohol, polyacrylamide, starch, urea, and melamine can reduce FE from UF-based adhesives, by acting as formaldehyde scavengers [110]. However, the FE can be minimised by changing the manufacturing conditions that lead to change the physical and mechanical properties of engineered wood panels [111].

To reduce FE in an indoor environment, some techniques such as avoiding the formaldehyde sources including formaldehyde yielding building materials, removing the formaldehyde sources, surface coating on formaldehyde yielding building materials, increasing ventilation, fumigation with ammonia, catalytic reactions and adsorption can be done [114].

Figure 1.19: Possible VOC emissions related to formaldehyde for the case of a wood-based material [114].

1.5.2 Volatile organic compound (VOC) emission

VOCs are emitted from natural sources and manufactured products. They are in the gaseous phase at room temperature due to their vapour pressures [115]. Solid wood, engineered wood-based panels, flooring products, paints, finishes, sealants, waxes, adhesives, mastics, cement, roofing materials, furniture, insulations and cleaning products emit VOCs [116]. The VOCs emitted by wood and wood-based panels are α -pinene, β -pinene, camphene Δ 3-carene, limonene, benzaldehyde, decanal, furfural, hexanal, nonanal, octanal, pentanal, acetic acid and formaldehyde [117]. Most of those are emitting from indoor applications. Humans spend 90% of their lives indoors [118]. VOC emission in newly renovated homes is much higher than the average homes [119]. As a result of that, humans are vulnerable to inhalation health risk associated with VOC emission. Therefore, the construction materials have to be selected considering indoor air quality as the main criteria [120].

Wood and wood-based panels release non-formaldehyde VOCs and formaldehyde related VOCs [113]. Possible formaldehyde related VOC emissions from wood-based materials can be categorised as shown in Fig. 1.19. Synthetic adhesives such as PF, PVA, epoxy and polyurethane consist of toxic chemicals namely epichlorohydrin, MDI, TDI, formaldehyde that are harmful to the health of living organisms and the environment [121].

1.5.3 End life of wood-based panels

The life span of pieces of furniture is 30 to 40 years in Europe. Wood-based panels and their final products become waste wood at the end of their service life [122]. The traditional method of disposing of engineered wood panels consists of landfilling and burning [123]. This

increases CO₂ and CH₄ (the greenhouse gas potential is 21 times higher than that of CO₂) emissions which leads to the disturbance of the ecological balance [124]. However, recycling of wood waste is difficult due to the content of harmful chemicals contained both in the glue used during the manufacturing process and the additives originally served to protect it from moisture content, wood-decaying fungi and to increase fire resistance [125, 126].

Even though virgin wood waste can be used as high-grade solid biofuel for energy recovery, wastes of wood-based panels can't be used due to their high content of formaldehyde substances [127]. On the other hand, it is needed to introduce chemo-thermo-mechanical processing, hydrothermal treatment, chemical treatment and mechanical treatment to reconstitute particleboard and MDF wastes into new products. Then UF and PF can be used to manufacture particleboard and MDF from recycled wood materials by using the similar process used in particleboard manufacturing with virgin wood particles [128]. However, the formaldehyde emission limit exceeds industrial standards due to the formaldehyde content of recycled wood materials. Fig. 1.20 shows how used wood-based panels can be re-used as new raw materials to manufacture wood-based panels.

The process in Fig. 1.20 illustrates the way of moving the wood-based panel manufacturing industry from a linear economy to a circular economy by reusing wood wastes as the raw material of wood-based panels. However, it does not give many advantages from the economical and ecological aspect due to the process costs and emissions. A ratio of round wood (virgin wood) to wood-based waste as 49:51 percent was used to manufacture particleboard [129].

1.5.4 Usage of recycled wood-waste

The manufacturing of low-formaldehyde-emission particleboard from recycled wood-waste chips can be done by using polymeric 4,4'-methylenediphenyl isocyanate with PF (ratio up to 70:30) resin for use in indoor environments. The formaldehyde emission released was 0.3 mg/L [130]. The resin formulation is industrially not viable due to the high cost of polymeric 4,4'-methylenediphenyl isocyanate.

1.5.5 Usage of non-renewable inputs

Even though some non-fossil raw materials such as natural gas, ammonia, carbon dioxide and urea are being used to produce UF, the major parts of raw materials of almost all the other synthetic adhesives are coming from petrochemicals [131]. Therefore, the prices of those synthetic adhesives fluctuate with petroleum prices [132]. As a result of decreases in the stock of fossil resources, there can be restrictions on using petrochemicals as the raw material of wood adhesive in the future [133]. Due to the decrease in availability and increasing cost of non-renewable fossil resources, it is vital to focus on renewable bio-based materials to make adhesive resins [134].

Figure 1.20: Wood-based panels in a circular economy [137].

1.6 Non-synthetic wood adhesives

Non-synthetic adhesives or bio-based adhesives are natural polymers (green binders) that act as adhesives. Biopolymers also act as stabilisers, thickeners, binders, dispersants, lubricants and drug delivery agents [135]. They consist of proteins, carbohydrates, lipids or some complex mixtures in varying proportions [136]. Bio-based adhesives do not generate environmental and health issues. They are being extracted and fractionated from natural substances and used as wood adhesives by applying heat and pressure as shown in Fig. 1.21.

The increase in the global bioadhesive market in USD billion by region is shown in Fig. 1.22. However, in general, bio-adhesives show poor performance in terms of water-resistance. In addition to water-resistance, in order to become competitive against synthetic adhesives, bio-adhesives require improved mechanical and chemical properties and reduction in their production costs [121].

1.7 Effect of additives

Additives used with adhesives act as binding agents and lubricants. They increase the production rate of the wood-based panel industry and decrease the energy consumption during the production process of wood-based panels [140]. Lignosulphonate as an additive has increased the production rate by bringing energy and the cost down [141]. Mechanical strength and the density of sawdust pallets were increased by adding proline as an additive [142]. The addition of 6% of sodium metabisulphite into MUF can increase the internal bond strength of wood panels [143]. Additives are being used in the wood adhesive industry for different purposes such as preservatives to protect against biological degradation

Figure 1.21: Green binders for wood adhesives [138].

Note: e-estimated p-projected.

Source: Expert Interviews, Secondary Sources, and MarketsandMarkets Analysis

Figure 1.22: Global bioadhesive market by region [139].

or against fire, to overcome weaknesses of the wood material, and to get a more favourable aesthetic appearance [68]. Denaturant additives, such as guanidine hydrochloride, sodium dodecyl sulfonate (SDS), and urea enhanced the performance of cottonseed wood adhesive [144].

1.8 Effect of hardeners

Hardeners in thermosetting adhesives promote the curing reactions by cross-linking with the adhesive or taking part through catalysis [145]. Some hardeners such as ammonium chloride reduce the formaldehyde emission, while some other hardeners such as ammonium sulfate reduce water absorption [104]. A lower viscosity value was obtained when furfural was used as the hardener with tannin adhesive. Better bending strength was achieved when pMDI was used as the hardener [146]. A pure bio hardener derived from the African trees *Vachellia nilotica* and *Senegalia senegal* slowed the gel times increasing curing rate and satisfied industrial standards [147]. Hexamine-hardened wood exhibits greater improvement in the fire properties and better resistance against artificial weathering [148].

1.9 Blending of bio-based adhesives

Most of the bio-based wood adhesives themselves have low mechanical and physical properties compared to most traditional synthetic polymers, which greatly limit their applications. The addition of additives, cross-linkers, dispersing agents, and hardeners into the bio-based adhesive increases the mechanical properties of the adhesive formulations. Wood gap-filling and adhesive properties of pMDI can be increased drastically by adding lignin-containing cellulose nanofibril as an excellent reinforcing material [149]. Table A.1 in Chapter A shows mechanical property enhancers that can be added to bio-based wood adhesives.

1.10 Wood preservation

Wood is sensitive to biological attacks due to its organic nature [150]. The service life of wood and wood-based composites can be lengthened by treating them with biocides [151]. Traditional wood preservatives were used to protect the wood in ground contacts.

It has been found that the long-term usage of synthetic wood preservatives can damage the environment, including killing widely non targeted wood-destroying organism [152]. So today, the trend is to replace the traditional preservatives with lower environmental impact and non-toxic preservatives [153]. Particleboard can be protected from biological agents in unleached (waters were not leached) environments by incorporating NaF without making any effects on mechanical and physical properties [154].

The addition of 0.5% - 6% commercial tannin Coltan, extracted from Quebracho (*Schinopsis Lorenzii*) as a greenwood preservative can inhibit the wood decay better than all

other natural wood preservatives [155].

1.11 Wood bonding

Surface properties and the physical properties of the wood are the main factors affecting bondability. Better wettability of the wood surface gives better bondability. Absorbing a drop of water within 20 *min* indicates good wettability of wood substrate [156]. Due to thicker cell walls and lower lumen volume of high-density woods, the adhesive penetration into cell walls is limited to one or two cells. This leads to poor mechanical interlocks and difficulty in making a strong bond [2]. The wood adhesives can be categorised according to their expected structural performance at varying levels of environmental exposure as shown in Table 1.8. Adhesives and their properties are shown in Fig. C.12. Working and strength properties of wood adhesives are mentioned in Table C.12.

1.11.1 Plasma treatment adhesion

Adhesion properties such as internal bond strength can be improved by applying plasma treatments to the adhesive surfaces [157, 158, 159]. Plasma treatment increases the hydrophilicity of adhesive surfaces of wood and wood-based materials, which increases the adhesion of common adhesives and paints [160, 161, 162, 163, 164, 165, 166, 167, 168]. Black spruce (*Picea mariana*) and sugar maple (*Acer saccharum*) wood surfaces treated in a dielectric barrier discharge at atmospheric pressure in Ar, O₂, N₂ and CO₂ containing plasmas, and then coated using a waterborne urethane/acrylate coating improved the adhesion up to 35% after exposure to N₂/O₂ (1:2) plasma for 6 *s* [169].

1.12 Manufacturing wood-based panels and composites

Low-grade logs such as thinnings, bowed, and twisted logs are the main raw materials of manufacturing wood-based panels (WBPs) such as particleboards, fibreboards (low-density - LDF, medium-density - MDF, and high-density - HDF), oriented strand boards - OSB, flakeboards, chipboards, waferboards, and wood moulded products. The bark is taken off during the very first step of the production process in commercial industries. Drum debarker is used for thin logs, thinnings, and branches [10]. Debarked logs are then chopped, milled, and ground for bonding by adhesives usually at high temperature and pressure to manufacture wood-based panels and composites [171]. According to the size of the wood particle, smaller particles (smaller than 1 *mm*) are used for surface layers and larger particles (bigger than 1 *mm*) are used for the core layer of particleboard [172]. The wood-based panel board production in Europe is shown in Fig. 1.23.

Table 1.8: Wood adhesives categorised according to their expected structural performance at varying levels of environmental exposure [2, 156].

Structural integrity	Service environment	Adhesive type^{a,b}
Structural	Fully exterior (withstands long-term water soaking and drying)	Phenol formaldehyde Resorcinol formaldehyde Phenol resorcinol formaldehyde Emulsion polymer/isocyanate Melamine formaldehyde
	Limited exterior (withstands short-term water soaking)	Melamine urea formaldehyde Isocyanate Epoxy
	Interior (withstands short-term high humidity)	Urea-formaldehyde Casein
Semistructural	Limited exterior	Cross-linked polyvinyl acetate Polyurethane
Nonstructural	Interior	Polyvinyl acetate Animal Soybean Elastomeric construction Elastomeric contact Hot-melt Starch

^a Priming wood surfaces with hydroxymethylated resorcinol coupling agent improves resistance to delamination of epoxy, isocyanate, emulsion polymer/isocyanate, melamine and urea, phenolic, and resorcinol adhesives in exterior service environment, particularly bonds to chromated copper arsenate treated lumber.

^b Assignment of an adhesive type to only one structural/service environment category does not exclude certain adhesive formulations from falling into the next higher or lower category.

Figure 1.23: Panel board production in Europe in the year 2005 [170]. (OSB - oriented strand boards, MDF - medium density fibreboards)

Wood generally has a strong moisture-induced swelling and shrinking anisotropy. The ratio of swelling of wood in tangential:radial:axial directions is about 20:10:1 [173]. As a result of the anisotropic swelling behaviour of wood, wood particles are dried before they are mixed with the adhesive formulation to maintain dimensional stability. The mixture is then pre-pressed pre-heated using steel belts of batch or continuous presses. The typical ranges of hot-press temperature and pressure are 200-220 °C and 2-4 MPa respectively. Industries are maintaining the ‘Press Factor’ of around 10 s/mm as shown in Eq. 1.3.

Figure 1.24: Star cooler used in particleboard industry <https://www.trenoxlaminates.com/MDF>.

$$\text{Press Factor} = \frac{\text{Time (s)}}{\text{Thickness (mm)}} \quad (1.3)$$

Where, *Time* is the total hot-press time, and *Thickness* is the thickness of the three-layer (surface-core-surface) particleboard. The cooling process is done in a ‘star cooler’ as shown in Fig. 1.24 and stacking is done for additional curing and re-humidification in intermediary storage [10].

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Overall aim and individual objectives of the study

Aim

The aim of this study is to develop environmentally friendly, non-toxic, bio-based and innovative adhesive formulations to manufacture wood particleboard.

Objectives

- [1] Identify non-toxic, bio-based substances with good adhesive properties to use for the base adhesive formulation;
- [2] Identify environmentally friendly additives to improve the adhesive properties in the formulation;
- [3] Develop a manufacturing route with different quantities of adhesives and additives with thermosetting properties to manufacture particleboards;
- [4] Test manufactured particleboard samples against the industrial standards;
- [5] Make recommendations for manufacturers on the use of bio-based wood adhesives considering economic and ecological factors.

Chapter 2

Wood welding and binderless bonding of wood - A Review.

“The woods are never solitary-they are full of whispering, beckoning, friendly life. But the sea is a mighty soul, forever moaning of some great, unshareable sorrow, which shuts it up into itself for all eternity.”

L.M. Montgomery

Abstract

The process of friction welding of metals can be used to weld two pieces of wood together without using any kind of wood adhesive formulations. The heat generation occurred due to the mechanically applied linear or rotational friction on wood surfaces melts lignin of wood surfaces and condenses during the cooling phase bonding the two pieces of wood together satisfying relevant industrial standards for mechanical and physical properties by greatly enhancing water-resistance. This binderless wood bonding process is called linear or rotational wood welding. The optimal results for mechanical and physical properties of welded wood joints can be obtained by varying some parameters such as the pressure applied, vibrational frequency and amplitude, holding pressure, holding time, the welding time in linear wood welding, and the relative diameter difference between the substrate and the dowel in rotational wood welding. Wood-to-wood frictional welding is a greener and environmentally friendly process of bonding two pieces of wood together without using formaldehyde yielding volatile synthetic adhesives. The fast curing time of the wood welding process shows a greater advantage compared to the usage of wood adhesive formulations to bind two pieces of wood. It is also an alternative way of using wood fasteners, nails, screws and glue retaining the homogeneous nature of the product.

Keywords: Wood welding, dowel welding, linear friction welding, vibrational welding, rotational welding.

2.1 Wood welding

2.1.1 Introduction

The wood welding process is done by applying mechanical linear or rotational friction on the wood interfacial region without the use of any adhesives [1]. Fig. 2.1a illustrates linear friction (vibratory) welding of wood. With this technique, the top piece of the two wood samples that need welding, vibrates horizontally with a certain frequency, an amplitude of 'a' and a pressure of PZ for a period of VZ time. During this process, the lignin of the wood surfaces melts due to the heat generated. Once the vibration stops, the melted lignin solidifies bonding the two pieces of wood together [2, 3]. The same mechanism happens when a rotating wood dowel is inserted into a pre-drilled hole on a wood piece as shown in Fig. 2.1b. The diameter of the hole should be around 1 mm smaller than the diameter of the wood dowel in order to have good friction which is necessary to melt lignin when the dowel is inserted. The same concept of rotational wood welding (so-called wood nail concept) is used to fasten wood nails without pre-drilled holes [4].

The solder layer of the interface joint produces a dark amorphous compound that acts as an adhesive that basically consists of a network of interlaced cells immersed in an array of molten lignin polymers [5]. The time required for the wood welding process is less than a few minutes. The mechanical performance of welded wood joints is as good as wood joints glued with conventional wood adhesives [6]. The experimental cooling speed of the wood welding process was higher than a numerical model prepared. It reveals that chemical reactions such as hydrolysis, pyrolysis, and gas generations are responsible for temperature discrepancies between the predicted and experimentally measured values [7]. The joint strength occurring via cross-linking chemical reactions can be improved by applying longer holding times [8]. Lignin is the most important wood constituent for successful wood welding [9] in addition to hemicelluloses [10]. De-polymerisation and re-polymerisation reactions of lignin are possible

Figure 2.1: Methods of wood welding. Where, PZ - welding pressure, VZ – welding time, F_R - friction force, a - amplitude of vibratory movement and p – displacement [2].

Figure 2.2: Tensile-shear strength as a function of welding time, standard deviation is expressed as a percentage [18].

during the wood welding [11]. Characterisation of lignin after thermal treatments can be performed using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy [12]. This shows the varying proportion of functional groups, particularly a decrease of acetyl groups and aryl-ether groups, an increase of newly formed carbonyl groups, which undergo dehydration reactions while making bonds within wood particles [13].

Microfibrils of cellulose, in both amorphous and crystalline states, tear off from the wood surface during the welding and this can be seen by SEM coupled with NMR analysis [14]. The grain orientation on linear wood welding does not influence significantly the average shear strengths [15], with differences not exceeding 10% [16]. However, the tensile strength of tangential grain orientated maple was 6.5 ± 1.6 MPa while that of radial grain orientation was 9.0 ± 0.9 MPa [17]. Schematic representation of the two methods of wood welding is shown in Fig. 2.1.

The optimal tensile shear strength was achieved for birch (*Betula pendula* L.) wood welding carried out by linear vibratory welding at a welding time of 3.5 seconds as shown in Fig. 2.2. Shorter welding time could be achieved using higher linear vibration frequencies. The formation of dark colour quinones in weldlines as shown in Fig. 2.3 is a common issue in the process of wood welding carried out both by vibratory and rotational welding. Nevertheless, wood welding performed by linear vibratory welding with a frequency of 150 Hz yielded colourless weldlines with no dark coloured quinones in the weldlines [19]. Wood dowel welding is an ecological alternative to glued or nailed wood connections [20]. Rotational welding of wood dowels resulted in joints with considerable strength. Wood dowels immersed in CuCl_2 and welded for 3 seconds showed the highest pullout resistance and data reliability [21, 22].

A rotational speed of 1230 rpm gave the optimal results for the tested species of *Eucalyptus saligna*, *Eucalyptus pilularis*, *Corymbia maculata*, *Ochroma pyramidale*, and *Tectona grandis* [23]. Nonetheless, for sugar maple and yellow birch, the optimal rotational

Figure 2.3: Cuboid composed of alternating layers of beech and spruce wood [26].

speed was 1000 *rpm* [24]. Linear friction (or vibratory) welded specimens ($20\text{ mm} \times 10\text{ mm} \times 150\text{ mm}$) were welded at the amplitude of 2 *mm*, frequency of 100 *Hz*, welding pressure of 1.9 *MPa*, holding pressure of 1.9 *MPa* and holding time of 7 *s* by varying welding time 2.5 *s*, 3.0 *s*, 3.5 *s* and 4.0 *s*. The result showed that the optimal welding time was 3.5 *s* as shown in Fig. 2.2 [18]. Canadian sugar maple and yellow birch wood could be successfully welded. Whereas the joints of birch were comparable to those obtained by gluing using PVAc adhesive, the maple joints were even superior to those obtained with PVAc adhesive [25].

Beechwood dowels with a diameter of 10 *mm* and with the radius of the ends chamfered by 0.6 *mm* were inserted into holes of 9 *mm* diameter in order to achieve good wood bonding [27]. The critical parameter to obtain optimised joint strength is the relative diameter difference between the substrate hole and the dowel. A smaller difference between the two improves the joint strength [28]. Beechwood is the best material for welding dowels regardless of fibre orientation [29]. The shear strength of welded spruce wood samples reached 70% of its ultimate value after 20 *s* from the termination of the welding process. This helps to weld many layers of wood without generating damage in the already formed joints [30]. Wood-bamboo-wood laminated composite lumber bonded by linear vibration friction welding showed mechanical properties suitable for the application in the furniture industry and even in the wood construction industry [31]. Alternating layers of beech and spruce wood were welded having an interval of about one minute to make a cuboid as shown in Fig. 2.3. During the process of frictional vibration, smoke was generated at 320°C and the maximum temperature reached was about 440°C [26]. Linear vibration wood welding of grooved surfaces increased the welded surface area and showed better results [32].

It is important to have a good knowledge of wood chemistry to understand the chemical

composition related to thermochemical reactions occurring during the welding process leading to adhesion and ultimately the weldline strength [33]. The chemical mechanisms related to wood welding are shown in Fig. 2.4. Ether bond splitting mechanisms shown in Fig 2.4a can be observed by the increasing of the peak at 1335 cm^{-1} in the FT-IR spectrum. Fig. 2.4d. shows the formation of formaldehyde and water during and after the curing of wood welding.

The temperature of the wood welding interface (T_0) can be expressed as in Equation 2.1.

$$T_0 = T_i + \frac{2\beta u\tau\sqrt{\alpha}}{h\sqrt{\pi}}\sqrt{t} \quad (2.1)$$

where

T_i – initial temperature of the wood,

t – time,

τ – the friction stress,

u – the rate of rotation or vibration,

β – the fraction of mechanical energy convertible into thermal energy, (it is 0.080 ± 0.01 for both the rotation welding and linear welding systems) and h and α are, respectively the thermal conductivity and diffusivity of the wood [39].

An interface of butt joints between two wood planks joined using rotationally welded dowels in a zig-zag pattern as shown in Fig. 2.5. has resulted in strong joints without the need to use any adhesive. The joint could even resist immersion in boiling water for 2 hours as well as subsequent oven drying [40]. When wood dowels were welded at an angle of 45° , the joints showed lower maximum failure stress compared to surfaces glued by PVAc bonded and UF bonded glulam. However, they seemed to have lower slippage than the PVAc bonded joints [41]. When the dowel insertion angle of rotationally welded dowels of blockboard panels was 20° , the best result for both tensile and bending strengths was achieved compared to the angles of 10° and 0° [42]. High-speed dowel rotation welding is capable of holding together structures such as wood suspended floors [43]. The decrease of the maximum rotational rate value is making the dowel-welded wood suspended floor more competitive with traditional floors [44]. This allows to maximise the rigidity of the suspended floor by minimising the number of timber planks used to build it [45]. Combining dowel welding with shrink-fitting using mortise and tenon wood joints has shown better joint strength than individual techniques alone [46].

The water-resistance of welded wood joints depends on the wood species. It has been visualised that the water-resistance of welded beech is lower than welded pine by using magnetic resonance imaging [47]. It has been shown that the addition of citric acid can improve the water-resistance of welded wood joints [48]. Pre-oiling the dowels by using sunflower oil eases insertion into the pre-drilled substrate, pre-lubricating the dowels for a better depth, which allows more layers of wood to be joined together, can provide improved water-resistance to the welded joint [49]. The research revealed that using a vibration frequency of 150 Hz , displacement of 2 mm , and welding time of 1.5 s showed that no fibres expelled out from the interface edge during the wood welding. At the same time, there was no

(a) Changes in lignin after side chain oxidation [34].

(b) Free radical thermal degradation pathways of β -O-4-bonded lignin structures [35].

(c) Depolymerisation (route 1) and condensation (route 2) reactions of lignin [36].

(d) Formation of formaldehyde from lignin units [37].

Figure 2.4: Chemical mechanisms related to wood welding [38].

Figure 2.5: Photographs of a joint of two wood pieces tightly joined by a zig-zag pattern of welded dowels before the dowels are cut [40].

darkening and an improved water-resistance in the welded joints was observed [50]. Computed Tomography (CT)-scanning has revealed that crack formation of Scots pine wood welded can be delayed by applying a pressure of 1.3 MPa in contrast to 0.75 MPa , a welding time of 1.5 s instead of 2.5 s , and by using heartwood [51]. Also, water-resistance of welded Scots pine can be enhanced at 1.3 MPa and welding time of 1.5 s [52]. It has been revealed that the degree of densification of weldlines (weldline density divide by the respective untreated wood density) for heartwood specimens was lower than that for sapwood samples of Scots pine. The results also showed that the water-resistance of weldlines is independent of the density of weldlines [53]. The use of heartwood, a welding pressure of 1.3 MPa , 1.5 s of welding time can decrease water absorption in the weldline, can increase water-resistance, and can prove a better performance of welded wood upon exposure to highly varying air humidity [54]. The addition of a small proportion of a native mixture of terpenic acid (as known as rosin) gives an enhanced water-resistance to the welded wood joints [55, 56]. It has been revealed that joining wood by either linear vibration welding or rotational dowel welding can greatly enhance the water-resistance of welded wood joints [57]. Improvements in cold water-resistance of vibration-welded wood bondline were obtained by using naturally derived additives such as tannins and furfural by autocondensation and polymerisation [58]. Reduced moisture content leads to a decrease in scale effects and produces much higher mechanical joint strength [59]. However, the weld strength of hydrothermolysed wood is poor [60]. This is due to the increase in the rigidity and brittleness of the wood cells during the solidification of melted lignin, occurring during the elevation of temperature up to 240°C during hydrothermolysis process of wood [61].

Poplar wood hydrolyses at 200°C into hydrolysable polysaccharides and then at 260°C into polysaccharides which are more difficult to hydrolyse [62]. Wood veneers can be welded at a temperature of 225°C to 250°C and pressure of 4 MPa for one hour without vibration or rotation. However, shorter times yield poor welding [63]. A developed three-dimensional heat transfer model can predict the thermal behaviour of welded wood [64].

An analysis of anatomical deformations has confirmed that the specific structure of entangled wood fibres disappears after a certain time for long welding times [65]. Thin wood pieces can be welded with better strength using an ultrasonic wood welding process.

Figure 2.6: Modified Arcan fixture device[68]

Nevertheless, microfriction stir welding can be done for any length of wood pieces. The limited depth of the weldline is the disadvantage of microfriction stir welding [66]. Generally, the multi-axial mechanical behaviour of welded wood assemblies can be taken from a modified Arcan device by varying tensile shear loading angle [67]. The method optimises the strengths through the multi-axial geometry of the welded wood samples. Modified Arcan device is shown in Fig. 2.6.

The welded interface of end-grain-to-end-grain of spruce has shown equivalent or better strength than glued fingerjoint [69]. End-grain-to-end-grain butt joint wood welding using Sidney blue gum (*Eucalyptus saligna*), spotted gum (*Eucalyptus maculata*, *Corymbia maculata* spp.) and Blackbutt (*Eucalyptus pilularis*) woods showed average welded joint strength of 6.6 MPa, 8.6 MPa and 5.3 MPa respectively, yielding good joint strengths [70].

End-grain-to-end-grain welded beech and oak wood yielded much better strength compared to the Type A and Type B grain at 45° joints as shown in Fig. 2.7 [71]. Three high density (800–900 kg/m³) Australian eucalyptus woods welded to end-grain-to-end-grain yield good joint strengths [70]. Also, there was no significant energy release rate difference obtained for the three different wood species used [72]. A minimalist Z chair was built by rotational dowel welding without metallic or wooden angular supports. The dowels were welded at two different angles in order to minimise the leverage action on the joints [73].

The most significant factors of wood dowel welding are rotation rate/dowel moisture content, followed by rotation rate and 20 min soaking into ethylene glycol. The least significant factors are the ratios between rotation rate/dowel temperature, wood grain direction/wood species, and dowel temperature/wood species [4]. Accelerating dowel insertion rates yields better results than constant dowel rates [74]. Partial unplugging of long wood fibres forms an entanglement network drowned in a matrix of melted material during the first phase of wood fusion welding. During the solidification of melted material, a wood cell entanglement network composite lignin matrix is formed [75]. Welded wood dowels give comparable results with PVAc adhesive which needs 24 hours to achieve the same result. Pre-heating the dowels and substrate at 100° C yields better results than obtained with PVAc gluing [76]. A study showed that through-welded dowel assemblies gave better stiffness than steel-nailed assemblies of the same design [77]. The morphological differences of different

Figure 2.7: Photographs of test pieces of end-grain-to-end-grain wood welding with end grain at 0° (0° butt joint), with both wood pieces at 45° to the wood longitudinal direction (Type A) and with both wood pieces at 45° to the wood longitudinal direction but at 90° to each other to form a fishbone-like pattern (Type B) [71].

types of welded wood joint depend on the density and the evenness of the bondline [78]. In the comparison of the outcome of numerical modelling and strength prediction of welded wood double lap joints, the experimental mean values were accurately predicted by the probabilistic joint strength method [79]. The energy release rate of the wood welded joints can be measured using a double cantilever beam test. The test revealed that the crack propagates only in the joints which enable to have a good representation of the mechanical properties of the welded segment [80]. Some experiments revealed that circular vibrational movement during the wood welding was more advantageous over linear vibration welding and the strength of wood welded specimens showed 40% of the corresponding adhesive glued connections [81]. And also, experimental evidence showed that the large variabilities of the strength of wood welded bonds can be described using Weibull statistics [82, 83].

The compounds in the smoke emitted from the welding interface during linear vibration welding of beech and oak wood were found to be water vapour, CO_2 , and degradation compounds from wood polymeric carbohydrates and amorphous lignin and volatile terpenes. But there was no emission of gases or degradation volatiles after welding was done [84]. The main carbohydrates of volatile compounds are xylan hemicelluloses (for hardwood such as beech wood), and glucomannans (for softwood such as Norway spruce) [85]. Wood carbonisation starts increasing during cross-linking of the lignin network after welding the wood surfaces [86].

The surface hardness of the wood surface can be measured using the Brinell hardness number (BHN) as shown in Eq. 2.2 by applying a load of 500 N on a 10 mm diameter hardened steel sphere on the tested wood surface.

$$BHN = \frac{F}{(\pi/2D(\sqrt{D^2 - d^2}))} \quad (2.2)$$

Where, D is the diameter of the striking steel ball (10 mm), d is the diameter of the indentation left on the surface to be tested, and F is the force exercised (500 N). The surface hardness of wood pieces prepared using mechanically induced vibration wood fusion welding

technique has shown that applying unsaturated oil gives harder surfaces due to the heat generated by vibrational welding treatment [87].

Mechanically induced vibrational wood welding has been used for different types of wood panels namely particleboard, OSB, MDF, and plywood by welding them in edge-to-edge and face-to-face orientations. In general, the strength of edge-to-edge panel welding is better than the face-to-face one [88].

Linear friction welding of wood can minimise and even eliminate the use of PVAc in the furniture and the interior wood joinery industry due to its economic and ecological benefits. In addition to that, the time needed to bond in the wood welding process is a few seconds while PVAc glue takes 24 hours after application. Wood welding would allow shortening the time required to manufacture the final product. Apart from that, welding of wood reduces the usage of synthetic and oil-derived adhesives. Cutting boards can be manufactured using a linear friction wood welding process without using any adhesives even in a small backyard workshop. Goods made by wood welding can be added to the existing market as greener, non-toxic and reliable final products.

2.2 Binderless bonding

Binderless particleboard panels are manufactured using sugar-containing lignocellulosic materials, such as sugar-cane bagasse and stalks of sorghum, corn, sunflower, flax, utilising the residual sugars as bonding and bulking agent without using any kind of adhesive resins. The process involves self-bonding via chemical components activated during the hot press [89]. This cuts the production cost and avoids the use of harmful chemicals utilised as adhesive [90]. High density and high-performance binderless boards were made using whole coconut husk following a detailed characterisation of the carbohydrate content in the fibres. The characterisation revealed that the fibres coir seemed to contain 16% of glucose, which worked as a self-adhesive in the process of the hot press [91].

Binderless boards prepared using finely ground powders of Kenaf at 180°C and 5.3 MPa for 10 min showed values for modulus of rupture (MOR) in the dry condition, modulus of elasticities (MOE), and internal bond (IB) strengths high enough to exceed the minimum requirement for grade type 15 medium density fibreboard (MDF) by the Japanese industrial standards JIS A 5905-1994 [92, 93, 94]. Higher values for IB but lower values for water absorption and tensile strength were achieved from the binderless boards prepared from the powdered Moso bamboo [95]. In another study, binderless particleboard manufactured at 260°C using bagasse showed better mechanical properties and dimensional stabilities than that of pMDI particleboard made using recycled chip [96].

The oil palm industry proportionately generates a large amount of biomass residues such as oil palm fronds, trunk, empty fruit bunches, ash and shell [97]. Oil palm trunk waste can be used as the raw material to make binderless particleboard by pressing at 120°C for 46 min or 215°C for 29 min. The resulting boards showed IB of 0.49 MPa; MOR, 8.18 MPa; thickness swelling (TS) of 22%; and water absorption of 51.43% [98]. In another study mechanical properties (MOR, MOE, IB strength) of binderless boards prepared from steam-exploded oil palm frond linearly increased with board density. They satisfied the requirements of S-20 grade according to JIS A 5905 - 1994 at a density of 1.2 g/cm³ for 6 mm

Table 2.1: Optimal processing conditions from numerical optimisation [100].

	Thickness (mm)	Temperature (°C)	Time (s)	IB (MPa)	MOR (MPa)	Thickness swelling (%)	Water absorption (%)
Sample 1	5	191	23	7.957	5.3	13.363	59.241
Sample 2	10	196	24	2.564	7.1	15.938	56.970
Sample 3	15	195	30	1.245	9.8	18.702	63.742

boards [99].

The optimal press temperature and press time for manufacturing binderless particleboard from oil palm trunk biomass are given in Table 2.1. The properties of all the panel produced satisfied the Japanese Industrial standards [100].

The chemical composition of the oil palm biomass waste consists of high holocellulose, lignin, starch, and sugar contents, which are required for self-bonding adhesion [101]. Experimental binderless composite panels manufactured using fine particles of oil palm trunks showed MOR and IB values of 4.04 MPa and 0.49 MPa while strands of oil palm trunks show MOR and IB values of 24.95 MPa and 0.95 MPa. MOR of the panels fabricated using palm strands satisfied JIS [102].

It has been shown in the literature that although the MOR of the binderless particleboard manufactured from oil palm trunk increases with the pressing temperature, it remains insufficient to meet JIS standard [103]. In another study, in order to achieve fibreboard property requirements, hydrogen peroxide was added to produce non-resin fibreboards from wheat straw. Calcium chloride as a water-repelling agent was used to reduce the thickness swelling by approximately 25% [104]. Laccase enzyme was also induced to create phenoxy radicals in the fibre lignin that could generate covalent bonds and cross-linking by radical-radical coupling on self-bonding boards manufactured with treated wood fibres [105].

2.3 Outlook and future work

Wood-to-wood friction vibratory welding has a high potential for future applications due to its fast curing time, no requirement for expensive adhesives and the eco-friendliness of the process. The ecological and renewable nature of the process and the absence of volatile

organic compounds emission, as well as formaldehyde and residual vinyl monomers emission, makes wood welding a green and environmentally friendly procedure for bonding wood within a circular economy framework. In addition to this, wood dowel welding can be taken as one of the best alternatives to wood fasteners, nails, screws and glue. Although wood is not a homogeneous material, it is possible to adjust several influential parameters during the welding process to achieve the optimal mechanical and physical properties even when different types of woods are used. Nevertheless, future studies are needed to minimise the unpleasant odours and the dark colour formation in the welded interface in order to achieve a more pleasing appearance of the final product.

Other advantages of wood welding include a good water-resistance of welded wood joints and the possibilities of welding wood veneer sheets by altering the grain orientation without using glues in the plywood manufacturing process. Because of the excellent moisture resistance of welded wood joints, these can compete with the conventional joint glueing process. However, for a real impact in the wood market, the mechanical and physical properties of welded wood-based panels need to be fully characterised and compared with those of welded virgin wood. In addition, the strength of welded wood joints should be tested and analysed over time. Finally, a scale-up of laboratory experiments into an industrial scale is required.

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Chapter 3

Testing and analysis of wood adhesives - A review

“Wood feeds the fire which burns it.”

Leonardo da Vinci

Abstract

Wood adhesives are polymeric materials that undergo heat treatment during the process of curing. Thermoanalytical methods can be incorporated to identify the change in phase behaviour, material characterisation, and degradation of the adhesive formulation during the change of temperature or heat flow. The optimal curing temperature of an adhesive formulation can be revealed in order to give the best adhesive strength to the substrate by using thermoanalytical methods. The flowability and viscoelastic properties of adhesive formulations can be determined by using an appropriate rheometer.

Keywords: Rheology, thermal analysis, adhesive polymers, thermal characterisation.

3.1 Introduction

Adjusting the preparation and application parameters of bio-based adhesives is a crucial factor to gain desirable mechanical properties. Various rheological parameters such as viscosity, storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E''), are very important to study viscoelastic properties of material [1]. The (E') measures the deformation energy stored in the sample during the shear process while (E'') measures the deformation energy used in the sample during the shear process. They are important values to analyse the internal structure of the adhesive that is affected by chemical and physical phenomena [2]. Addition of tannin and hexamine to corn-starch was able to reduce its viscosity to improve adhesive properties and these findings were found as a result of the evaluation of rheological properties of corn-starch-tannin wood adhesive

with hexamine as a hardener [3]. Adhesives generally behave as non-Newtonian fluids. As a result of this, it is important to get their rheological measurements to study the properties of viscous fluids [4].

Wood adhesives are subjected to temperature-dependent structural changes during the curing process. Thermoanalytical tests such as thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and thermomechanical analysis (TMA) are carried out to find properties of adhesive formulations such as thermal transitions, degree of crystallinity, glass transition temperature, thermal stability, melting, crystallisation, and reaction enthalpies.

3.2 Mechanical tests

3.2.1 Flexural Strength

Flexural strength so-called Modulus of Rupture (MOR) or bend strength, or transverse rupture strength is one of the most important value needed to be calculated. The 3-point bending test machine as shown in Fig. 3.1 is used to get the reading for the failure load to work out the flexural strength σ using the Eq. 3.1 for a rectangular cross section [5].

$$\sigma = \frac{3FL}{2bd^2} \quad (3.1)$$

Where,

F : the force (failure load),

L : the distance between bottom two rollers of the 3-point bending test machine,

b : width of the sample,

d : thickness of the sample.

In order to test the properties of particleboards, the samples must be prepared according to the Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS A 5908: 2015) particleboard specifications. According to the standards, the distance between the two rollers of the machine (L) should be greater than or equal to the value of 15 times its thickness and the L value should also be greater than 150 *mm*. The length of the sample should be $L + 50$ *mm*. The radius of all three rollers of the bending test machine should be 10 *mm*. '5/100 *kN* Instron 5500R Electro-mechanical' machine has been used for testing in this study [6].

The vertical test speed should be set for 1 *mm/sec*. The tests have to be carried out for both longitudinal and transverse directions.

Figure 3.1: 3-point bending test machine.

3.2.2 Bending Young's modulus test

Bending Young's modulus or modulus of elasticity (MOE) is calculated from the deflection that appears when the load is applied. It is calculated using the Eq. 3.2.

$$MOE = \frac{(P_2 - P_1)L^3}{4bt^3(d_2 - d_1)} \quad (3.2)$$

Where,

- MOE : Bending Young's modulus (N/mm^2),
- $P_2 - P_1$: increase of the load at the linear part (N), P_2 is about 40% of the maximum load, and P_1 , about 10%,
- L : span (mm),
- b : width of test piece (mm),
- t : thickness of the test piece(mm),
- $d_2 - d_1$: increase of deflection at the linear part, corresponding to $P_2 - P_1$ (mm) [6].

The MOE of the wood adhesive industry varies in a wide range from 0.1 GPa up to 15 GPa [7].

3.2.3 Internal bond (IB) test

In order to test the internal bond, the wood sample is attached to the aluminium blocks as shown in Fig. 3.2. After it is attached, an increasing tensile load is applied until it reaches the maximum failure load. The IB is calculated using the Eq. 3.3.

Figure 3.2: Testing IB of a sample by applying tensile load.

$$IB = \frac{P'}{b \times L} \quad (3.3)$$

Where,

- IB : Internal bond (N/mm^2),
- P' : maximum load at separation (N),
- b : width of the test piece (mm),
- L : length of the test piece (mm) [6].

3.2.4 Wood screw withdrawal and holding strength

The maximum resistance to withdraw or separate a fastener of a plane normal to the testing face can be taken by wood screw withdrawal strength. The wood screw holding strength is half of the withdrawal one [8]. Wood screw withdrawal strength and holding strength are carried out to determine the values of f_w and f_h using the Eq. 3.4 and 3.5 respectively.

$$f_w = 39(IB)^{0.85} D^{0.5} (L - D/3)^{1.25} \quad (3.4)$$

$$f_h = 18.4(IB)^{0.85}D^{0.5}(L - D/3)^{1.25} \quad (3.5)$$

Where,

- f_w : withdrawal strength (*lb.*),
- IB : internal bond strength (*psi*),
- D : diameter of the screw (*in.*),
- L : depth of embedment of the screw (*in.*),
- f_h : holding strength (*lb.*) [9].

3.3 Physical tests

3.3.1 Moisture content test

The moisture content of a test piece of the wood-based panel was calculated using the Eq. 3.6 by taking the mass of it before drying and after drying at $103^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until it attains a constant mass [6].

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{m_1 - m_0}{m_0} \times 100 \quad (3.6)$$

Where,

- m_0 : mass after drying,
- m_1 : mass before drying.

3.3.2 Thickness swelling

For the assessment of thickness swelling, a test piece of the sample was immersed in water of $20^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ horizontally about 3 *cm* below the water level for 24 hours as shown in Fig 3.3. The thickness swelling was calculated using the Eq. 3.7 [6].

$$\text{Thickness swelling (\%)} = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{t_1} \times 100 \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.3: Steps for thickness swelling test.

Where,

t_1 : thickness before immersion (mm),

t_2 : thickness after immersion (mm).

3.3.3 Water absorption

A piece of particleboard sample was fully immersed in water of $20^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ horizontally about 3 cm below the water level for 24 hours. By using the initial and final weight of the sample, the water absorption is calculated as in Eq. 3.8 [10].

$$\text{Water absorption (\%)} = \frac{w_2 - w_1}{w_1} \times 100 \quad (3.8)$$

Where,

w_1 : weight before immersion (N),

w_2 : weight after immersion (N).

3.4 Analysis methods

3.4.1 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

The rheological properties of curing and cured adhesives can be characterised by DMA analysis [11]. The viscoelastic nature of polymers can be identified using a DMA analysis by applying sinusoidal stress to the sample. The phase angle lag δ of the resultant strain ϵ and the applied stress σ can vary according to the material property following Eq. 3.9 and 3.10.

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \sin(t\omega + \delta) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_0 \sin(t\omega) \quad (3.10)$$

Where,

σ_0 is the initial stress,

ϵ_0 is the initial strain,

ω is the frequency of strain oscillation, and

t is time [12].

The storage modulus (so-called elastic modulus, in-phase modulus, real modulus [13]) E' can be defined as follows.

$$E' = \frac{\sigma_0}{\epsilon_0} \cos \delta \quad (3.11)$$

$$\Delta E' = E'_{max} - E'_{min} \quad (3.12)$$

$\Delta E'$ can be used as a parameter for the evaluation of the rigidity of the resin. The loss factor ($\tan \delta$) curve plotted on E' vs *Temperature* can be used to get the gel point and the vitrification point [14].

$$\tan \delta = \frac{E''}{E'} \quad (3.13)$$

Where,

E'' is the Loss modulus (so-called viscous modulus, imaginary modulus [13]).

$$E'' = \frac{\sigma_0}{\epsilon_0} \sin \delta \quad (3.14)$$

DMA analysis can also be used to get the thermal expansion coefficient, Young's modulus, the glass transition temperature of the adhesive. DMA technique was used to identify fibril/polymer interactions and to evaluate the reinforcement effect of the viscoelastic response of cellulose nanocomposites. The significant increase in storage modulus in the whole temperature range and the significant decrease of $\tan \delta$ in the glass state showed a strong interaction between cellulose nanofibrils network and highly hydrophilic matrix [15]. DMA analysis can be used to obtain the degree of mechanical cure that gives the shortest hot-press time for a given temperature [16]. The degree of mechanical cure can be calculated using the following equation.

$$\text{Mechanical conversion}(\%) = \left[\frac{E'_{max} - E'(t)}{E'_{max} - E'_{min}} \right] \times 100 \quad (3.15)$$

Where,

- $E'(t)$: the storage modulus value at given time t ,
- E'_{min} : the storage modulus value when it starts to increase sharply (0% of mechanical conversion),
- E'_{max} : the maximum modulus of the E' curve (100% of mechanical conversion).

If an adhesive with the highest degree of mechanical cure such as mechanical interlockings shows the lowest degree of chemical cure with chemical reactions converting liquid to solid mostly consisting of dehydration reactions, the mechanical cures can be achieved at a lower temperature than the chemical cure [17].

3.4.2 Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA)

Dimensional changes of solids, liquids or pasty materials as a function of time or temperature under a defined static load at atmospheric pressure can be determined by using TMA. This method is also called thermodilatometry or dilatometry [18].

Thermal expansion, coefficient of thermal expansion, volumetric expansion, density change, shrinkage steps, glass transition temperatures, softening points, penetration behaviour, phase transitions, creep behaviour, anisotropic behaviour, and Young's modulus can be determined by using TMA. It has been revealed that the readings for mechanical properties taken by using the Automated Bond Evaluation System (ABES) are similar to those observed from TMA analysis [19]. Performing TMA measurements is more effective, quicker and more precise than making various particleboards in the laboratory and test them. The

Figure 3.4: Raman Spectroscopy Imaging [23].

internal bond value of particleboards can accurately be forecasted by using TMA [20]. The modulus of elasticity can also be investigated by TMA [21].

3.4.3 Dielectric Analysis (DEA)

The change in the dielectric properties of an adhesive resin during curing can be measured using DEA. Cure monitoring, degree of cure, glass transition temperature, and diffusion properties can be revealed using DEA. The curing of liquefied wood during the bonding of wood lamellae was evaluated by DEA. A continuous curing process can be monitored using DEA which provides data for the evaluation of the degree of cure (α) of the adhesive formulation as reported in Eq. 3.16 [2, 22].

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{\epsilon''_{max} - \epsilon''_t}{\epsilon''_{max} - \epsilon''_{min}} \quad (3.16)$$

Where,

ϵ''_{max} is the maximum dielectric loss factor,

ϵ''_t is the dielectric loss factor during the cure,

ϵ''_{min} is the minimum dielectric loss factor.

3.4.4 Raman Spectroscopy Analysis

Raman Spectroscopy can be used to find substantial and deep penetration of wood adhesive into the wood cell walls [23]. Fourier-transform Raman (FT-Raman) spectroscopy techniques can be used to determine changes in the chemical structure of heat-treated woods [24]. The reaction homogeneity in vinyl acetate grafted starch granules was detected by using confocal Raman microscopy. The quality of high solid content of starch-based wood adhesives was also assessed by using FT-Raman [25]. A single spectrum is recorded in every pixel across a predefined region with diffraction-limited resolution in confocal Raman spectroscopy imaging as in Fig 3.4.

Figure 3.5: Atomic Force Microscopy Imaging [23].

3.4.5 Atomic Force Microscope (AFM)

AFM is a useful method in adhesion force measurements, owing to its ability to identify surface forces at precise locations and its stability for various materials and environmental conditions as shown in Fig. 3.5 [26]. It can characterise physio-chemical properties such as stiffness, elasticity, or adhesion to a given surface or interface [27]. AFM and confocal Raman spectroscopy imaging can be used to get chemical and mechanical characterisations with sub-micron lateral resolutions at high sensitivities [23].

The roughness of the surface has a major influence on adhesion distribution. AFM is a sensitive and reliable method that gives quantitative and qualitative data concerning surface topography [28]. The size and size distribution of polyurethane wood adhesive in the dispersed phase were significantly affected by wood interaction. This was determined by AFM [29]. Larger aggregates were found in modified soy protein isolate based wood adhesive when AFM tapping phase images were observed [30].

3.4.6 Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) Analysis

FTIR spectroscopy is an entrenched technique used for the chemical analysis of wood [31, 32]. It can be used to obtain an infrared spectrum of absorption or emission. The intensity over a narrow range of wavelengths at a time indicates the chemistry of the molecules. The FTIR spectra of control fir wood and its holocellulose, cellulose, and lignin contents (4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1}) is shown in Fig. 3.6.

This can be used to identify the availability of the desired chemical compound in the sample. Table 3.1 reports some of the most typical chemical bonds observed in FTIR with their wavenumber.

Formation of new compounds, crosslinking and effect of hardeners can be identified using the peaks newly obtained or shifted in the FTIR spectra. Grape pomace tannins as bio-based wood adhesives extracted in different extraction conditions were characterised by FTIR analysis [35, 36].

Figure 3.6: Fourier-transform infra-red spectroscopy of wood components [33].

3.4.7 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The rates of chemical reactions or the chemical cure of the formulated adhesive can be identified using DSC analysis [11, 17]. Any energetic effect occurring in a solid or liquid during the adhesive thermal treatment can be analysed by using DSC. DSC is carried out to determine the thermal energy released (exothermic) or absorbed (endothermic) via chemical reactions between the wood and the adhesive. Exothermic reactions provide information on crystallisation, oxidation, combustion, and decomposition. Endothermic provides sample melting, phase, transitions, evaporation, dehydration, and pyrolysis [37]. Curing kinetics and viscoelastic properties of adhesive resins can be investigated by DSC [38].

Specific heat capacity, thermal transitions, glass transition temperature, degree of crystallinity, melting, crystallisation, and reaction enthalpies of adhesives can be determined using DSC analysis. It also gives onset temperature, reaction heat, and peak temperature and activation energy of the adhesive resin [39].

Mainly there are two types of instruments available commercially. The differential thermal analyser (DTA) and the DSC. DTA measures the temperature difference between the reference pan and the sample. But DSC measures the energy differences between the sample and the

Table 3.1: Assignment of major absorption IR spectra peaks in wood forming tissue [34].

Wave Number cm^{-1}	Band assignment
1739	C=O stretching in un-conjugated ketone
1640	C=O stretching vibration in conjugated carbonyl of lignin
1510	Aromatic skeletal vibrations
1457	CH ₂ deformation stretching in lignin and xylan
1425	Aromatic skeletal combined with C-H in-plane deforming and stretching
1371	Aliphatic C-H stretching in methyl and phenol OH
1320	Cl-O vibrations in S derivatives, CH in-plane bending in cellulose I and cellulose II
1267	Syringyl ring breathing and C-O stretching in lignin and xylan
1160	C-O-C asymmetric stretching in cellulose I and cellulose II
1059	C-O stretching vibration (cellulose and hemicellulose) C-O
1034	C-O stretching vibration (cellulose , hemicellulose and lignin)
897	Cl vibration

reference pan by keeping the temperatures constant. Two types of DSC instruments are listed below.

3.4.7.1 Heat Flux Differential Scanning calorimetry

The reference and the sample are heated at the same rate from one single heating source in a heat flux DSC system. The difference in heat flow is taken from the temperature difference between the pans and then converted to a power difference which gives the difference in the heat flow. Disk-type DSC and cylinder-type DSC are the main two types of DSC instruments.

3.4.7.2 Power-Compensated Differential Scanning Calorimetry (PCDSC)

The reference and the sample are heated separately in PCDSC. The temperature values of pans are monitored using attached thermocouples to the disk platforms. The differential heat flow is measured by using thermocouples connected in series. The heat flow according to

Ohm's law can be expressed as follows.

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = \frac{\Delta T}{RD} \quad (3.17)$$

Where,

ΔT is the temperature difference between the sample and the reference,

RD is the thermal resistance of the disk platform [18].

3.4.8 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The changes in the mass of a sample over time as the temperature changes can be taken in TGA analysis. Physical and chemical phenomena such as absorption, desorption, chemisorption, thermal decompositions can be measured using a thermogravimetric analyser. Thermal degradation [40] and thermal stability of a wood adhesive can be found using a TGA [37]. The mass change as a function of temperature or time can be evaluated using TGA analysis. Thermal stability, the kinetics of reactions, composition analysis, and filler content can be identified by using the TGA technique. TGA provides complementary and supplementary characterisation information to DSC. The simultaneous thermal analyser (STA) is a single instrument that can do TGA and DSC at once.

Thermal degradation which is the molecular deterioration that happens due to overheating can be determined from the TGA plot by measuring the weight over time [18].

3.4.9 Differential Thermogravimetric (DTG) analysis

The first derivative or its negative value of TGA plotted in the same plot of TGA is taken as the DTG curve. $-\frac{dm}{dt}$ where m is the mass lost and t is the time of TGA is plotted in Fig. 3.7.

DTG shows the mass loss per time in the specific temperature. For a specific example, the DTG curve in Fig. 3.7. shows that there are four steps of mass losses at around;

- 110⁰ C, Moisture release;
- 245⁰ C, decomposition of the polenta cornstarch;
- 270⁰ C, decomposition of the mimosa tannin;
- 300⁰ C, decomposition of the tannin-UF-adhesive mix [40].

3.4.10 ¹³CNMR Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra

The molecule structure of adhesive polymers can be chemically characterised by nuclear magnetic resonance microscopy in liquid or solid state [11]. Using the positioning of

Figure 3.7: TGA and DTG curves of the adhesive mix of polenta cornstarch, mimosa tannin, and UF resin (10:4:86 mass proportions); temperature increment = $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. [40].

resonance peaks of ^{13}C NMR Spectra it was possible to identify the changes that have happened to the chemical structure of cellulose and that of melamine formaldehyde. Also, the reaction mechanism with different temperature changes can be approximated [41, 42].

3.4.11 X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD)

The crystallinity and its changes with time and temperature of wood adhesives can be studied by using X-ray diffraction analysis. A broad diffraction peak indicates a high degree of crystallinity of the sample. The effect of the addition of additives into wood adhesives can be identified by using the crystallisation peak of X-ray diffraction patterns [43]. The crystallinity index of an adhesive sample can be calculated by using its XRD patterns using Eq. 3.18.

$$\text{Crystallinity index} = \left[\frac{I_{200} - I_{am}}{I_{200}} \right] \times 100\% \quad (3.18)$$

Where,

I_{200} is the peak intensity of the crystalline fraction,

I_{am} is the peak intensity of the amorphous fraction.

Lowering the value of the crystallinity index increases the strength of manufactured wood composites [44].

3.4.12 Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (E-SEM)

Cracks on fracture surface and moisture uptake of the different cured adhesive samples can be observed using E-SEM images [43]. The mechanical interlocking into the wood substrate can also be studied with scanning electron microscopy [45]. Sputter coating with gold is used in order to improve the imaging of samples [46, 47]. The penetration of phenol-formaldehyde wood adhesive into wood cell walls can be observed by using SEM and UV-microscope. SEM also shows the PF resin penetration into tracheids and rays, rays through parenchyma cells, filling bordered pit cavities, and porous resin due to gas bubbles [48]. Well-known urea-formaldehyde resin distribution across wood cells can be illustrated by using SEM analysis [49].

3.4.13 Matrix assisted laser desorption ionisation Time-of-flight mass spectroscopy

Matrix-assisted laser desorption ionisation time-of-flight mass spectroscopy (MALDI-TOF) is used to identify the formation of new compounds during the curing process of wood adhesives. It can be used as a powerful method to characterise both synthetic and natural polymers [50, 51]. In addition to that, the amounts of newly formed compounds can be compared by using the height of the peaks plotted on the mass/charge axis [52].

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Chapter 4

Literature Review

“A tree without roots is just a piece of wood”

Marco Pierre White

Introduction to the chapter

As the previous chapter explained, formaldehyde emission is the main health issue in the wood-based panel industry. In order to overcome this issue, several research studies are being conducted worldwide today. This chapter explains the formulations of wood adhesives developed to reduce or eliminate formaldehyde by maintaining physical and mechanical characteristics of the resultant wood-based panels. Some of the adhesive formulations included in this chapter are purely bio-based while others are a mixture of bio-based and synthetic components. Fig. 4.1 reports the types of wood adhesives in the market. It has been shown that blended adhesives have enhanced mechanical and physical properties able to satisfy industrial standards.

Figure 4.1: Types of wood adhesives.

Non-toxic wood binders for manufacturing engineered wood panels: Challenges and Future opportunities - A Perspective.

Abstract

Most of the wood adhesives used in industries are synthetic and carcinogenic because of the formaldehyde emission that occurs during the manufacturing process and their usage by the general public. Furthermore, the re-manufacturability of synthetic wood adhesive used products such as particleboard is limited. This causes waste accumulation which ends up in landfill. Synthetic wood adhesives are mostly derived from depleting petrochemical resources. Therefore, introducing bio-based wood adhesives would be the best alternative way to overcome these issues. Agricultural and industrial by-products can be used as raw material for most of the bio-based wood adhesives and additives. In addition, the ability to blend bio-based adhesive with the synthetic ones makes the adaptation to the current manufacturing lines of wood panel production easier. It has also been shown that the addition of nanoparticles into the bio-based adhesive resins gives added advantages on their performance. Many of the bio-based wood adhesive formulations have demonstrated to satisfy international industrial standards in most of their physical and mechanical properties. However, in general, the moisture adsorption and the generally poor water-resistance of wood-based panels manufactured using bio-based adhesives have to be improved.

Keywords: Bio-based adhesive, Formaldehyde emission, Engineered wood panels.

4.1 Introduction

Currently, the most widely used industrial wood adhesives are aldehyde yielding compounds such as melamine-formaldehyde (MF), melamine urea-formaldehyde (MUF), phenol-formaldehyde (PF) and urea-formaldehyde (UF) resins (so-called amino-plastic resins) [1]. However, it is now recognised that these adhesives emit formaldehyde. The effect of formaldehyde emission was re-classified from “probable human carcinogen” to “known human carcinogen” by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) in 2004 [2, 3].

Apart from that, petroleum-based wood adhesives may not be biodegradable. This can lead to waste accumulation [4]. On the other hand, bio-sourced wood adhesives are renewable, recyclable, re-manufacturable, natural and non-oil-derived materials. UF as a non-bio-based adhesive, can actually be sourced from a non-oil derived raw material and it is used to manufacture more than 90% engineered wood panels used in households [5]. Tannins, lignin, carbohydrates, unsaturated oils, proteins, blood and collagen are bio-based wood adhesives that were utilised in the past, before the introduction of toxic synthetic wood adhesives [6].

The wood adhesive industry is about two thirds (by volume) of all the adhesives used in the world. Each year, 11 million tons of UF resins are being sold [7]. There are some advantages and disadvantages of using synthetic adhesives as shown in Table 1.6.

Polymeric 4,4'-Methylene diphenyl isocyanate (pMDI) and 4,4'-Methylene diphenyl isocyanate (MDI) are widely used in the wood adhesive industry. They show high bonding strength, short press time, resistance to water and 0% emission of formaldehyde compared to the traditional water-based urea-formaldehyde resins and phenol-formaldehyde. The significant issue of pMDI is its high price [8]. pMDI also has characteristics of being efficient (small amount needed to achieve a product with optimal performance), good weather resistance and fast curing [9, 10].

4.2 Wheat gluten adhesives

Gluten proteins can be considered as the most complex protein network in nature [11]. Wheat gluten (WG) is a relatively inexpensive abundant protein source [12] and a by-product of starch production for bio-ethanol. WG is a complex mixture containing 80% wheat protein, and the rest is lipids, polysaccharides, and minerals [13, 2]. Wheat protein consists of glutenin that has elastic properties (being dispersible in acids) and gliadin that has viscous properties (soluble in alcohol) [2]. Gliadins are monomeric and have low molecular weight, while glutenins are polymeric and have high molecular weight [14]. WG has an isoelectric point of 7.3 with a high amount of hydrophobic amino acids [15]. As a result of that, WG is not dispersible in water alone, but it becomes so following the addition of alkali and acids [2]. WG-based adhesives can be prepared by dispersing WG powder in an alkaline solution. A mixture of 25 wt.% WG with 0.2M NaOH applied on wood panels, heated at 130°C for 15 minutes under a pressure of 0.7 MPa has provided the highest bond strength of 7.07 MPa and the optimum bond line thickness compared to the other percentages of WG and NaOH that were tested [16]. Dispersion concentration, viscosity, and the application method are the factors strongly affecting WG dispersion into the wood particles. Nevertheless, other factors such as drying temperature, presence of cross-linkers, dispersing agent and type of wood species have less effect on the penetration and film formation [17]. Performing the WG dispersion in two steps, by drying of the glued chips in-between the first and the second addition is beneficial compared to other proposed one-step process [15].

WG (80%) was mixed with UF resin (20%) and then 1% and 2% boric acid as a fungicide was added to the resin mixture and used to produce high-density particleboard using reed instead of wood particles. The addition of boric acid resulted in no significant change in the mechanical properties such as modulus of rupture (MOR), modulus of elasticity (MOE), internal bond (IB) strength, but resulted in a slight improvement in the physical properties such as water absorption and thickness swelling [18]. The particle size of alkali-denatured WG in WG-

protein adhesives is independent of tensile strength achieved [19]. The adhesive performance of wheat protein thermoset adhesives can be increased by adding triacetin [20]. Wheat gluten hydrolysed (0.3%–0.6%), heat-treated at 90 °C and finally dispersed in 0.1 M NaOH(aq) was used as wood adhesives. The result shows improved bond strength and an enhanced water-resistance [21].

Wheat gluten itself shows better wood adhesive properties when mixed with alkaline such as NaOH. It also can be blended with synthetic adhesive such as UF in an acidic environment to minimise formaldehyde emission.

4.3 Sodium alginate

The basic raw material for the production of sodium alginate (SA) is brown algae [22]. Alginates are unbranched polysaccharides and complex carbohydrate polymers derived from brown seaweeds [23]. Tens of million tons (frozen weight) of seaweeds are harvested from offshore and onshore [24]. Alginates are used in industrial applications considering their properties of gelling, viscosifying and stabilising [25]. SA has been used as a biodegradable additive in the papermaking industry with polyamideamine-epichlorohydrin to increase the mechanical properties of the cycles fibres [26]. SA should be blended or modified or copolymerised with some other biopolymers in order to be used as a structural scaffold [27]. The chemical structure of SA depicted in Fig. 4.2. shows the phenolic polymer nature and the ability to react with wood cell wall hydroxyls when SA is dissolved in water.

Figure 4.2: Chemical structure of sodium alginate molecule [28, 27].

Aldehyde sodium alginate and amino gelatin can be utilised in surgeries as a bioadhesive for soft tissue [29]. Sodium alginate showed the best bioadhesive force among some other bioadhesive polymers tested in the production of omeprazole buccal adhesive tablet [30, 31]. By mixing chitosan and sodium alginate, oral mucosal bioadhesive tablets of diltiazem were produced [32].

4.4 Lipid-based adhesives

Canola, soybean, palm, maize, sunflower, castor and jojoba seeds are mainly used in industrial applications by extracting the lipid/oil from them. The oils can be functionalised by

transesterification, epoxidation, hydro formation and ozonisation to achieve enhanced functional properties [33]. Soy oil [34] and castor oil [35] were previously used to make bio polyols to use in polyurethane wood adhesive.

4.5 Oil palm trunk-based wood adhesives

Carboxymethyl starch extracted from the oil palm trunk by using the method of Noor et al. [36] was tested as wood adhesives by comparing with native starch, UF and by mixing it with 2% of UF. The extracted carboxymethyl starch itself when used as an adhesive led to products with a modulus of elasticity and internal bond strength satisfying the requirements of the Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS). The addition of 2% of UF allowed obtaining a modulus of rupture as 'Type 8 particleboard' in JIS [37].

Polyurethane wood adhesive without adding volatile organic solvents prepared from palm oil-based polyester polyol exhibited comparable mechanical strength to a PVAc wood adhesive available in the market [38]. The properties of synthesized polyol that have a higher molecular weight, lower hydroxyl functionality, good spreadability on wood surfaces, strong lap shear strength and long gel time (90 *min*) implies that it can be used for adhering to the large wood surface for a longer work life [39].

Particle sizes of 0.5 *mm*, 1.0 *mm* and 2.0 *mm* of dried oil palm strands were used to make sample boards. The samples made from 2.0 *mm* particles of oil palm were able to meet the minimum requirement for the mechanical properties, while other sizes show better properties [40].

Liquefied oil palm extracted from empty fruit bunches with phenol can be used as a novolak¹ resin in wood adhesives [41].

Lignocelluloses biomass bio-oil from oil palm trunk can be applied for wood preservation on an industrial scale [42]. The use of the trunk of the palm tree to make particleboards without using any type of resins has been described in section 2.2 [43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48].

4.6 Protein Adhesives

Proteins are polymer chains made out of amino acids linked together by peptide bonds. Agricultural, industrial and forestry residuals and municipal wastes (disposed off either by incineration or by landfilling [49]) even consist of proteins which are the principal organic building blocks in all living organisms. Proteins represent over 50% of the dry weight of a cell [50].

Single-cell protein extracted from yeast showed a joint strength from 2.40 *MPa* to 2.99 *MPa* proofing as similar to the urea-formaldehyde wood adhesive but with superior performance [51]. Whey-protein based aqueous polymer-isocyanate adhesive reacts with polyvinyl alcohol and cross-linking agent polymeric methylene diphenyl di-isocyanate to

¹Novolaks (or novolacs) are PF resins with a formaldehyde to phenol molar ratio of less than one.

produce a resin, which when used has led to wood products that have satisfied the demands for structural uses in JIS K6806-2003 standard [52]. Whey protein post-treated by phenol formaldehyde oligomers as wood adhesive showed good water-resistance and when combined with ammonia and sodium sulphite showed a positive effect on formaldehyde emission, as these behave as formaldehyde scavengers [53].

Wood adhesive made from the protein extracted from *Rhodotorula rubra* with some reinforcing agents (liquid glyoxal in 40% concentration, resorcinol in flakes and liquid diphenylmethane diisocyanate) has given a good performance and stiffness, comparable to that using UF [54]. On the contrary, it has been shown that Zein (protein of maize) is not suitable as a wood adhesive at least in the tested glueing conditions such as glue quantity in grams per square meter, spreading on each side of the assemblies, pressing time and the bonding pressure [55].

4.7 Canola protein isolated adhesives

Canola (vegetable oil derived from rapeseed) is the second-largest oilseed crop product after soy [56, 57]. Most of the canola protein is used as animal feed [13]. Canola meal is a by-product of canola oil extraction and contains 30% to 50% of proteins [58]. Canola proteins were modified by using 3 g/l of sodium bisulphite (NaHSO_3). This seemed to improve dramatically the flowability and handling ability of the adhesive without compromising its wet shear strength [59, 60]. However, NaHSO_3 did not improve the adhesive properties of canola protein [59] but it improved the water-resistance [60].

Another study has reported that polyurethane (PU) adhesives were produced using canola oil derived polyol and have shown better adhesive properties in terms of lap shear strength than synthetic PU adhesives [61].

4.8 Soy-based adhesives

Soy-bean flour, soy-bean concentrate and soybean protein isolate (SPI) are cheaper [62] than some synthetic resins and have shown good mechanical properties when they are used as non-toxic wood adhesives [63]. Soybean protein concentrate with gelatin resin showed increasing bond strengths in both shear and tensile modes [64]. Soy flour was used to make interior plywood from the 1930s to the 1960s. It was gradually replaced by UF adhesives due to lower cost and rapid curing of UF under hot pressing conditions [65].

Soy protein isolate was modified with maleic anhydride and mixed with polyethylenimine in order to achieve dry shear strength of 7 MPa at hot-pressing time of 2 min [66]. Also, soy protein/ CaCO_3 hybrid wood glue was greatly improving the water-resistance and bonding strength of soy protein adhesives compacting rivets or interlocking links, and ion crosslinking of calcium, carbonate, hydroxyl ions in the adhesive [67].

Water-resistance can also be improved by adding lignin-based resin into the soy-bean meal-based adhesive [68]. SPI showed a very strong affinity to cellulose from wood almost

twice as wheat gluten adhesives under acidic and alkaline conditions [69].

Some other adhesive proteins such as heat-cured or heat-set animal blood and casein have been used to blend with soy protein for bonding interior-grade plywood, doors, and mill-work [70]. The moduli of rupture of soy-based adhesive (57.319 *MPa*) and petroleum-based urea-formaldehyde adhesive (38.12 *MPa*) were evaluated and compared and the results indicated a better flexural strength of the soy-based adhesive for making plywood [71].

Glyoxalated soy flour adhesives for wood particleboard with a very small amount of glyoxalated lignin or tannin and without any addition of UF, PF, MUF were able to satisfy the relevant standard specifications for interior grade wood boards [72]. However, the major disadvantage of the soy-protein-based adhesives is their poor water-resistance [73]. That is mainly due to the weak intermolecular interactions that are easily destroyed by water, including hydrogen bonds, electrostatic bonds, Van der Waals forces, disulphide bonds (so-called an S-S bond, or disulphide bridge). The three major chemical modification approaches performed to enhance water-resistance of bio-adhesives can be classified into three categories: protein denaturing agent modification; soy protein molecular modification (graft modification, acetylated modification, protein enzyme modification, and bio-mimetic modification); and mixing with reactive cross-linkers [74, 75, 76]. The soy-based adhesive cross-linked with hydroxymethyl phenol cured at low temperature (80°C) showed better mechanical performance and heat resistance than the adhesive without hydroxymethyl phenol [77].

A wood adhesive prepared by cross-linking soy-bean soluble poly-saccharide in soy-bean meal and then conjugating soy protein showed enhanced thermal and mechanical properties and reduced moisture absorption meeting the water-resistance requirements for interior use plywood [78].

A long-chain cross-linker diethylene glycol diglycidyl ether and denaturation agent sodium dodecyl sulphate have shown to increase the performance and water-resistance of soybean meal-based wood adhesive [79]. Soybean meal and triglycidylamine and modified sepiolite have shown enhanced performance as wood adhesive [80].

Soybean meal with ethylene glycol diglycidyl ether and diethylenetriamine can be used as adhesive in the plywood industrial application [81].

Water-resistance of soy protein isolate adhesive was increased by introducing triglycidylamine and γ -(2,3-epoxypropoxy) propyltrimethoxysilane as a cross-linker [82].

Superior water-resistance and shear strength of plywood panels were achieved when polyethyleneimine and NaOH were added to the Soy-bean flour/acetic anhydride adhesive formulations [83].

A soy-based adhesive cross-linked with a hybrid cross-linker made of 6.4% of epoxy resin and 6.4% of melamine-formaldehyde showed the best water-resistance at a pressing temperature of 160°C and press time of 8 *min* among the several percentages of hybrid cross-linker tested [84].

Thermochemical treatment of soybean protein in the presence of sodium sulphite and sodium dodecyl sulphate, followed by cross-linking by epichlorohydrin-modified polyamide shows wet bond strength of up to 1.22 *MPa*, exceeding the required value for structural use of

plywood (0.98 MPa) [85]. The processing pressure of soy-bean wood adhesive was found to be the most important factor in determining adhesion strength. The optimal value of that pressure was 4.55 MPa [86]. Soy-bean protein-acrylate composite mini-emulsions were used for wood adhesive showing an internal bond strength higher than 0.7 MPa, meeting the standard of GB/T9846-2004 II [87].

Chemical phosphorylation of soy flour, using phosphoryl chloride (POCl_3) as a phosphorylating agent, dramatically increased its wet bond strength from 1.06 MPa to 2.6 MPa [88]. The water-resistance of soy flour-based wood adhesives was greatly improved by adding POCl_3 , inorganic oxidising agents, such as NaClO_2 and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_2)_2$ in addition to POCl_3 . These oxidising agents are non-toxic and environmentally safe [89].

Soy flour with a curing agent derived from the reaction of epichlorohydrin and ammonium hydroxide in water was used as a wood adhesive with NaOH, showing an improved water-resistance as well as an improved dry shear strength [90].

Soy flour with polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin as a wood adhesive showed greater adhesive bond with protein-protein and protein-wood [91].

Modification of defatted soy flour with acid salt and alkali showed water-resistance and high performance as a wood adhesive [92].

Soy flour crosslinked by 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid was used as high-performance environmentally friendly defatted soy flour-based bio-adhesives [93].

Enhanced water-resistance and bonding strength were achieved by using defatted soy flour enzymolysed by Viscozyme L as a bio-based wood adhesive [94].

Rice husk (RH) as wood chips and soy protein as the adhesive was chemically modified to increase the performance of formed medium-density particleboard. NaOH or NaOH and H_2O_2 were used to eliminate lignin, hemicellulose, and silica from RH by chemically treating. Then alkali-treated soy-protein adhesive was reacted with treated RH. A better mechanical interlocking and more hydrogen bonding between OH groups of cellulose and the polar groups of the unfolded soy protein was responsible for greater adhesion strength [95].

Generally, soy-protein-based adhesives show poor water-resistance due to disruption of hydrogen bonds, electrostatic bonds, Van der Waals forces, and disulphide bonds. Among all the tested solutions to improve water-resistance of soy-protein based adhesives the following showed the most promising results:

- Addition of polyethyleneimine and NaOH,
- Blending with epoxy resin and melamine-formaldehyde,
- Addition of sodium sulphite and sodium dodecyl sulphate, followed by cross-linking by epichlorohydrin-modified polyamide,
- Reaction of epichlorohydrin and ammonium hydroxide in water and then with NaOH.

4.9 Natural Rubber-based wood Adhesives

The two types of natural rubber-based adhesives are:

1. latex adhesives, made by adding stabilisers, wetting agents, and other components to natural rubber-based adhesives; and
2. solution adhesives made by adding a solvent such as toluene, naphtha, or trichloroethane into natural rubber-based adhesives [96].

Modified natural rubber latex used as natural rubber-based wood adhesive had shown lower formaldehyde emission compared to commercial UF adhesive [97].

Epoxidised natural rubber-based wood adhesives (ENR) showed superior properties compared with unmodified natural rubber-based adhesives [98]. Higher tensile strength was obtained by using ENR-toluene-based wood adhesive [99]. SEM images indicate better adhesion properties of modified natural rubber compared to the unmodified natural rubber [100]. Natural rubber is also used to produce cellulose acetate and cellulose acetate butyrate adhesives [101]. MOR and MOE values of composite boards made using natural rubber-wood adhesives were much higher than those of oil palm fronds and stem as shown in Table 4.1.

4.10 Chicken Feather Protein-Based Wood Adhesives

Chicken feathers are composed of 91% keratin protein [103]. The insoluble feather keratin can be used to produce feedstuffs, fertilisers, glues and films [103]. Today, most of the proteinaceous material of waste feathers is landfilled [104, 105, 106]. On the other hand, proteinaceous adhesives such as chicken feather based adhesive are being used in the wood-based panel industry by using hydrolysed chicken feather (in NaOH) and hydrolysed chicken blood (in H₂SO₄) as the hardener [107].

Using feather protein as adhesives show added advantages compared to soy protein due to the hydrophobic nature of keratin, which is the protein contained in chicken feathers. The anti-mildew nature of feather protein, less likeliness to flocculate and easier nature to hydrolyse than globulin such as soy show possibilities of manufacturing a better adhesive using feather protein [108]. Chicken feather fibre can have the ability to withstand both thermal and

Table 4.1: Bending Strength between compressed oil palm fronds composite boards, Composite Oil Palm Stem and Rubber-wood [102].

Composite boards	MOR (N/mm^2)	MOE (N/mm^2)
Oil Palm Fronds	16.66	999.61
Oil Palm Stem	15.13	480.06
Rubber-wood	56.57	2543.34

mechanical stress due to its high thermal energy [105]. Waste keratin material such as feather, hair or hoofs with known adhesives such as blood, casein, bone glue or hide glue alone or with some other glue materials is suitable to produce plywood, corrugated paper, cardboard and other similar materials [109]. The protein molecules of the chicken feathers can be unfolded by heating in an alkaline solution and would be exposed to polar functional groups of wood veneers showing appreciable adhesion properties under dry condition. However, the water-resistance of the resulting plywood panels was poor [110]. Improved water-resistance and thickness swelling of medium density fibreboard (MDF) made using chicken feathers fibre and 5% of PF resin were achieved over the control panels due to the hydrophobic keratin in the feather fibres [111, 112].

Improved stiffness of elastomeric matrix and increased storage modulus were found in a composite made using copolymer styrene-butadiene and chicken feathers [113].

Three proteins (soy-proteins, wheat gluten, and chicken feathers) were able to provide nearly the same cohesion to fibres and abrasion resistance as starch in the cotton warp sizing industry. This result indicates that soy-proteins and wheat gluten can be replaced by the chicken feather to prepare different sizes of cotton threads. This can save food by sparing wheat and soy, is environmentally friendly because of the use of a waste product and can also benefit the poultry and textile industries [114].

The hollow honeycomb structures and very low density of chicken feather give excellent compressibility and resiliency, warmth retention and fluid absorption properties for lightweight composites and sound protection applications [115]. Acoustic panels can be made using chicken feathers, cardboard bins glue and water [116].

Chicken feather with wood pulp can be used in paper manufacturing industries by varying the proportion of the chicken feather fibres up to 100% wood pulp [117].

Hollow keratin fibres of the chicken feather can be used to make environmentally friendly composite by using soybean resin [118].

4.11 Citric acid as a wood additive

The citric acid (CA) is used as the major component of adhesive formulation to make wood-based moulding, fibreboards and particleboards [119]. A mixture of *Acacia mangium* bark powder and 20 wt.% of CA as the adhesive were hot-pressed at 180°C and 4 MPa for 10 minutes to make binderless boards. The results have shown good bending properties, improved MOR and MOE [120]. Increasing CA content has shown increasing water-resistance [121]. Bamboo particleboard bonded with CA has shown high performance on mechanical properties and better dimensional stability [122] and excellent water-resistance. The internal bond value was increased by 10 times when 10 wt.% of CA was used for bonded boards. When the percentage was increased to 30% (wt.), the optimum MOR and MOE were obtained [123].

Water absorption and thickness swelling of three different bamboos (petung, wulung and apus) particleboard were reduced significantly when CA adhesive content was increased from 0% to 30% [124].

Particleboards adhesive made using CA and sucrose (15/85 and 10/90 wt.%) has shown higher mechanical properties, lower brittleness, and comparable dimensional stability compared to the adhesive made using CA and PF [125]. Pre-dried wood particle bonded showed the best mechanical properties and water-resistance with 20% - 30% (wt.) CA [126]. The optimal pressing temperature and time were 200 °C and 10 *min* respectively [127].

CA can also be used as a wood adhesive additive, a cross-linking catalyst, a cross-linking agent or a dispersing agent in order to enhance the adhesive strength [119].

According to the chemical structure of CA shown in Fig. 4.3, hydroxyl groups of the wood cell wall can react with the hydroxyl groups of CA at high temperature releasing H₂O vapours. CA molecule can bond more than one wood cell as it has more than one hydroxyl groups. This can bond one wood cell to the other chemically.

Figure 4.3: Chemical structure of Citric acid.

CA adhesive provides improved dimensional stability, enriched water-resistance and high performance on mechanical properties for particleboards [128].

4.12 Cottonseed protein wood adhesives

Cotton is mainly grown for the fibre industry. Cottonseed consists of gossypol which is toxic for human consumption [13]. Cottonseed protein as a wood adhesive has shown higher shear strength compared to the modified or unmodified soy protein-based adhesives [129]. The adhesive properties of cottonseed are independent of the type of meal used (derived from glanded or glandless) and the method of fraction retentate (by water/NaCl and phosphate buffer/NaCl) [130].

Water washing of cottonseed meal is more cost-efficient and environmentally friendly compared to the alkaline extraction and acidic precipitation [131]. Alkali extraction and acid precipitation were done on defatted cottonseed to get cottonseed protein isolate. Cottonseed meal isolates, as well as the defatted cottonseed meal, can be used as wood adhesives. Water washed cottonseed meal shows better water-resistance properties compared to the defatted cottonseed meal [132].

Several protein modifiers such as amino acids, fatty acids, and other organic molecules with cationic or anionic charges were used in cottonseed and soy protein isolate-based wood adhesives. When anionic charges such as aspartic acid, glutamic acid, acetic acid, butyric

acid, and adipic acid were used in the cottonseed protein-based adhesives, these exhibited the best performance. However, there was no significant enhancement in properties on soy protein isolate [133].

Cottonseed protein isolate was used as a wood adhesive in the presence of protein denaturants, such as guanidine hydrochloride (GuHCl), sodium dodecyl sulfonate, urea, and alkali. The dry adhesive strength and hot water-resistance of cottonseed protein isolate were superior to that of soy protein isolate, with or without the denaturants used [134].

Cottonseed and soy protein isolates were separately blended with a polysaccharide such as starch, xylan, cellulose. Blended cottonseed protein has shown superior adhesive strength compared to the soy protein in the protein/polysaccharide blends [135].

The phosphorus-containing additives have improved the hot water-resistance of the cottonseed protein formulations but showed no effect on the soy protein formulations [136]. Dry and water-soaked bonding strengths of pure UF resins were improved by introducing 30% of cottonseed meal. It also improved rheological properties, glue line features, and it lowered the cost [137]. Water-resistance of water-washed cottonseed meal was improved by mixing with synthetic adhesive vinavil 2259 L from the classification of 'D1 - Inside application field condition' to 'D3 - Protected outside application field condition' in European standard EN204/205 [138].

In conclusion, the ability to use defatted cottonseed meal as a wood adhesive gives economic benefits to the wood adhesive industry for indoor applications. The process of water washing the cottonseed meal can enhance the water-resistance of the adhesive.

4.13 Geopolymer (Inorganic polymer) binders

Geopolymers (inorganic polymers) are synthetic alkali aluminosilicate compositions produced with the reaction of an aluminosilicate powder with a highly concentrated alkali solution [139]. Geopolymer binder for wood-based composites was developed based on pozzolanic by-products such as fly ash. Silica fume can be used as a replacement agent to extract geopolymer from aluminosilicate components such as fly ash and metakaolin to make the binder. The bonding shear strength was evaluated using 'Automated Bonding Evaluation System' (ABES) technique [140, 141]. The best shear strength of fly ash binders was found at the lowest press temperature and longest pressing time. Silica fume showed higher pozzolanic activity² than metakaolin, whereas fly ash showed lower strength compared to metakaolin. When investigating the use of increasing percentages of silica fume from 20% to 100%, a superior shear strength compared to conventional urea-formaldehyde resin and other geopolymer binders was achieved with the highest percentage studied (100%). Nevertheless, even at 20% of silica fume, the same bonding shear strength as for UF resin was achieved [140]. Geopolymer binding materials are inorganic and they can be used as an alternative approach to the current formaldehyde emitting synthetic binders [142].

Alkaline activator (a mixture of a highly alkaline solution such as sodium silicate or potassium silicate) with NaOH or KOH is used to activate industrial by-products (silica fume

²A measure for the degree of reaction overtime or the reaction rate between a pozzolan and Ca_2^+ or calcium hydroxide $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the presence of H_2O .

or/and fly ash). Activated industrial by-products and high amount of silica and alumina from natural raw materials are used to manufacture geopolymer materials [143]. Alkali activation of fly ash shows cementing characteristics such as smoothness, glassy state and shiny appearance [144].

Fly ash that can be taken from power plants is cheaper than pozzolanic materials. Fly ash can be divided into two groups according to the availability of calcium.

- ASTM class F - Low calcium fly ash. The preferred material.
- ASTM class C - high calcium fly ash. This interferes with the polymerisation and alters the geopolymer micro-structure [145].

Silica fume is a by-product of the ferrosilicon production industry and a highly effective pozzolanic material due to its extreme fineness and high silica content. So, its use in binders improves properties like compressive strength, bond strength and abrasion resistance [146]. It has been shown that the interaction between geomaterial foam binder and wood achieves a desirable mechanical performance of resulted assemblies [147]. Geopolymer binders show good adhesion properties between wood and earth bricks [148].

In conclusions, the addition of geopolymers into synthetic wood binders showed superior bond strengths as well as a reduction in the formaldehyde emission of the binder. Cementing characteristics of geopolymer can give smoothness, glassy state and shiny appearance for the final product of wood-based panels. Geopolymers are a by-product that can be sourced at a very low cost and have shown the ability to even bond wood with earth bricks.

4.14 Hemicellulose wood adhesives

Wood is a complex mixture of large organic polymers, mainly cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. These three make up at least 95% by weight of dry wood. The remainder consists of fats, waxes, resins and simple phenols [149]. Xylan is a group of hemicellulose that can be taken as a by-product in the pulp industry and recovered in large quantities from side-streams of the agriculture and forestry industry [150]. Although xylan cannot be used directly as a wood adhesive, it has shown promising results as a high-performance wood adhesive following the addition of dispersing agents such as poly(vinyl alcohol) or poly(vinylamine), and cross-linkers, such as glyoxal or hexa(methoxymethyl) melamine [151].

Olive kernel a lignocellulosic material that mainly contains cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin can have the ability to replace up to 15% of PF in a PF resin adhesive [152].

A four-stage squeeze extraction process was used to extract a wood adhesive from the bark of radiata pine (*Pinus radiata*). This four-stage extraction comprised: first two stages of hot water extraction, a third-stage of extraction at pH 8.3 (NaOH) followed by a fourth-stage extraction consisting in hot water washing. The resulting adhesive showed 'Type A' bond (fully weather and boil proof) in plywood [153, 154].

In conclusions, dispersing agents and cross-linkers are needed to prepare an improved

hemicellulose wood adhesive. Nevertheless, a number of synthetic adhesives can be replaced by hemicellulose wood adhesives.

4.15 Laccase-Mediator

Laccases are multi-copper proteins (EC 1.10.3.2, *p*-diphenol: dioxygen oxidoreductases). They use molecular oxygen to oxidise various aromatic and non-aromatic compounds by a radical-catalysed reaction mechanism [155]. They are widely found in fungi [156]. Lignin, hemicellulose and some carbohydrates are the planet's own natural cross-linking agents [157]. Lignin contains many active functional groups such as phenolic hydroxyls, alcoholic hydroxyls and esters [158]. So, lignin behaves similarly to cement in reinforced concrete [159]. This causes wood to have tangential and radial direction mechanical strength [160].

The hemicellulose cross-linking effect can be achieved by the production of aldehydes, ketones, phenolic and other substances during hot pressing of lignocellulosic materials [161]. This causes to increase in the MDF cross-link density [159].

Laccase catalyses the oxidation of phenols, polyamines, lignin as it has an oxidoreductase activity [162, 163]. During the catalytic oxidation, phenolic lignin forms phenoxy radicals which change into quinone compounds under different conditions. In a study, natural mediators (vanillin) and artificial mediator ABTS³ were used by considering the steric hindrance in the reactions [159]. In this radical displacement reaction, the smaller molecular compounds get to oxidise the non-phenolic groups in lignin, but they do not occupy the active site of the laccase due to steric hindrance [164, 165]. As a result of that, the catalytic efficiency of laccase increased and the chemical and mechanical properties of MDF were improved due to the availability of phenolic compounds in the active site of laccase to react with the hydroxyls of wood cell walls [159]. After both types of the mediator (vanillin and ABTS) were prepared, acetic acid/sodium acetate buffer solution was added to the laccase solution. Then they all were mixed, and weighted wood fibre was added. Oxygen was fed into the mixture for 55 *min* at 50°C. Chitosan (1.2%) was then added to the mixture as a waterproof agent. The mixture was hot-pressed at 10 *MPa* and 160°C for 512 seconds. Controlled samples were tested using deionised water as the solvent without adding laccase or mediator. Chitosan was not added into it before the hot-pressing [159]. The adhesives properties on the wood of alkyl-chitosan exhibit better water-resistance compared to native chitosan [166]. Mechanical properties were examined after leaving the samples for 48 hours. Mechanical properties of MDF samples met the performance requirements of the 'People's Republic of China National Standard GB/T 11718 - 2009 (2009)'. The self-adhesive properties were achieved through esterification, hydrogen bonding, poly-condensation, coupling and Schiff base reaction. Coupling and poly-condensation were the main reactions of all above [159]. The newly generated crystalline region in the cellulose increased the mechanical strength of MDF during the reaction process. Degraded lignin moved to the MDF surface increased the content of carboxyl during the hot-press process. As a result of this, high content of aldehyde groups was observed in the MDF interior [159]. Agricultural wastes and by-products of some industries are the main sources of bio-based wood adhesives as well as some of the additives such as tannin. The pressing time can be reduced when tannin as an additive is used with laccase [167].

³(2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid))

In conclusions, laccase has the ability to increase catalytic oxidation of phenols, polyamines and lignin which are the natural cross-linkers of plants. As a result of that, laccase can increase the mechanical and physical properties of wood-based panels.

4.16 Lignin Adhesives

Lignin is a large, amorphous, 3D polymer that can be produced by vascular terrestrial plants [168]. Lignin acts as an adhesive in the cell walls by holding cellulose fibres together [169, 170]. Hydroxy-cinnamyl alcohols, coniferyl alcohol and sinapyl alcohol, and minor amounts of *p*-coumaryl alcohol are the main building blocks of lignin [171]. They are phenolic, abundant, and low-cost materials that have lower reactivity towards formaldehyde or other aldehydes. Lignin and lignosulphonates can be mixed in small proportions with synthetic formaldehyde resins to reduce their cost while achieving similar mechanical and physical properties [7, 172, 173]. Lignin structures undergo fairly rapid cross-linking reactions by forming esters and anhydrides [174]. Similar thermal properties of lignin were found in PF resins [175].

Exterior-grade structural finger joints and glulam based on soda bagasse lignin wood adhesive showed to satisfy the requirements of the relevant international specifications [176].

Lignin with glyoxal as a wood adhesive has achieved international standard specifications showing better values for internal bond (IB) strengths and sufficient press times compared to formaldehyde-based commercial wood adhesives [172].

Lignin modified with zinc and choline chloride-based deep-eutectic solvent (ChCl–ZnCl₂ DES) enhanced its reactivity towards the formation of resin adhesive. So, the sustainable integration of lignin in the wood adhesive industry can be further advanced [177]. The main disadvantages of lignin as an adhesive in the wood composite industry are:

1. Low reactivity → slow hardening → longer press curing times.
2. The concern of chemical variation in the feedstock due to the complex structure of lignin [168].

However, there is a successful system used today worldwide for high-density hard boards, which is called the 'Shen' system based on self-coagulation and cross-linking of lignin. This is done by a strong mineral acid in the presence of certain aluminium salt catalysts. However, this system has failed to produce medium density fibreboards (MDF) [6]. Nevertheless, the pressing time was acceptably shorter when 1% of isocyanate (pMDI) was added to the board [178]. The cross-linking of desulfurised Kraft lignin with triethyl phosphate adhesion tested on wood has shown good hydrophobicity properties of the surface treated with lignin triethyl phosphate-based resin [179].

The combination with lignin into PF resin increases adhesive strength and decreases gel time [180]. Also, lignin-phenol-formaldehyde with coffee bean shells has resulted in a better adhesive [181] which require lower curing temperature [182].

Figure 4.4: Schematic path of the simultaneous corrections of glyoxalated lignin with the tannin/hexamine adhesive system [7].

Amounts of 65 wt.% of pre-methylated lignin, 10% - 15% of synthetic phenolic formaldehyde resin and 20% - 25% of pMDI were used as a wood adhesive. This gave the fastest pressing time in the industry due to the high cross-link density of formation of methylene and urethane bridge [6, 7].

Lignin isolated from Kenaf *Hibiscus cannabinus* via soda and Kraft pulping and modified with soda lignin-phenol-glyoxal showed higher tensile strength and internal bonding stress at 72.08 MPa and 53.83 MPa respectively compared to that of PF [183].

Tannin/hexamine with glyoxylated lignin as a wood adhesive satisfied the values required by the European standards [184]. It was found that up to 50% of phenol can be replaced by bagasse lignin to give lignin phenol formaldehyde wood adhesive having better bonding strength in comparison to a control phenol formaldehyde wood adhesive [185].

In addition to 50% glyoxalated-alfa, lignin and 50% of Aleppo Pine tannins yielded a good internal bond strength of 0.45 MPa for one-layer wood panels satisfying relevant international standard specifications for interior-grade wood panels [186]. Lignin can be pre-glyoxalated in a reactor to get glyoxalated lignin⁴. That can then be mixed with tannin and pMDI eliminating the need for any formaldehyde or formaldehyde-based resins. Wheat straw organosolv lignin is used to apply the above technology. It satisfies requirements for industrially significant pressing time. The mechanism of copolymerisation and hardening is shown in Fig. 4.4 [7].

Lignin can react with hexamethylene diamine to form hard, condensed solids showing wood adhesive properties between the temperature of 100°C and 180°C [187]. Enzymatic hydrolysis lignin derived from bio-ethanol with PF gives comparable properties to those of commercial wood adhesive [188].

Alkali-treated Moroccan sugar cane bagasse lignin could be used to replace 30% of the PF resins used to bond plywood panels satisfying relevant international standard specifications for interior-grade panels [189].

⁴glyoxal is a non-toxic and non-volatile aldehyde.

Lignocellulosic ethanol residue is a by-product of lignocellulosic ethanol production and rich in activated lignin and usually treated as waste. The thermal stability of lignocellulosic ethanol residue modified PF adhesives was better than that of PF adhesive in the initial thermal degradation [190].

Fibreboards containing 15% acid-washed Kraft lignin have indicated good mechanical and water-resistance properties that fully satisfied the relevant standards specifications [191]. The addition of hyperbranched poly (amine-ester) to tannin adhesive could improve the water-resistance of glyoxalated Kraft lignin resin [192]. Higher bonding strength and water-resistance were obtained by using a chitosan-lignin wood adhesive which is inexpensive and environmentally friendly [193].

In conclusions, lignin in virgin wood behaves as a natural binder of wood cell walls binding cellulose fibres together. So, lignin as a complex organic polymer has the ability to bond one wood cell to another. The ability of copolymerisation of lignin with some other polymers can give added advantages for the adhesive properties of lignin. Lignin is the second most abundant biopolymer; it is inexpensive and the ability to be developed into a wood adhesive to an industrial scale is viable.

4.17 Nanoparticle Modification of Polymers and Soy-based Adhesives

Nanoparticle reinforcement in polymers and adhesives is very effective in improving their performance [194]. Multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) was used to reinforce soy-based polyurethane (PU) foam and then its compressive, flexural, and tensile properties were compared with neat polyurethane foam. The properties of MWCNTs-PU foam were improved by 24%, 30% and 34% respectively [195]. Aligned MWCNTs (compared to the unaligned MWCNTs) can successfully prevent crack development. As a result that, the tensile strength increases. Soy-based polyol and polymeric diphenylmethane diisocyanate (pMDI) were used to make polyurethane foam. Mechanical properties and thermal stability were improved by incorporating Nanoclay Cloisite® 30B [196]. By adding a nanoclay of 0.5% (wt.) to the soy-based polyurethane, the mechanical properties were increased by 22% - 98%. The smaller cell size of foam composites causes an impressive increase in strength and modulus of Nanoclay soy-based polyurethane foams [197].

Although bio-nano-adhesives obtained by dispersing montmorillonite clay into a soy protein concentrate matrix showed the better adhesive performance to the wood material, the wet adhesion of the nano-composites has similar values of the adhesive without nanoparticles [198]. The addition of nanoclay sodium-montmorillonite into urea-lignin-formaldehyde resin showed to increase the viscosity by 1.5% and free formaldehyde and gel time of the resin were reduced [199]. Nanoclay can efficiently be mixed with polyvinyl acetate by using ultrasonication technique [200].

Biological resistance of wood-composites against wood-deteriorating fungi (fungi, insects and termites, and marine borers) was improved by adding nano-metals and nano-minerals. In addition to that, the thermal conductivity coefficient of the wood composite mats was increased by adding highly thermal conductive nano-metals and nano-wollastonite.

As a result of that, the hot pressing time, physical and mechanical properties were improved [201]. Nano TiO₂ with natural castor oil-based polyurethane adhesives exhibit improved water-resistance compared with castor polyurethane itself [202]. Nano-silver impregnated wood panels showed a lower amount of water absorption and an insignificant increase in thickness swelling. The impregnated panels showed a better impact of mechanical properties compared to physical properties [203]. However, both physical and mechanical properties were increased by adding 100 ml/kg and 150 ml/kg nanocopper, which also reduced the hot press time by 5.7% and 3.4% respectively [204].

Water impermeability of MDF can be improved by adding zycosil nanoparticles [205].

Wollastonite nanofibers demonstrated the ability to increase the thermal conductivity by 11.5% making better curing of the resin in the core section of MDF mat [206].

Penetration of water and vapour into a wood-composite matrix was prevented by adding silane nanoparticle [207]. Higher effectiveness of preservatives and fire-retardants, ultimately increasing the service life was obtained by impregnating the wood with aqueous nanomaterials, which increased the permeability of solid wood [208].

Nano-silver shows fire-retarding properties in solid woods [209]. In general, nanomaterials can have the ability to improve the properties of wood-based panels and to help in overcoming some of their shortcomings [210].

Nanomaterial reinforced canola protein adhesive showed improved water-resistance and adhesion strength. In fact, hydrophilic bentonite, surface modified nanoclay (SM-MMT), graphite oxide, and nanocrystalline cellulose were exfoliated using the solution intercalation method. While the addition of SM-MMT increased the dry, wet and soaked strengths, bentonite significantly increased only the dry strength [211]. Nanomaterial reinforcement gave added value for canola protein isolated adhesive by improving water-resistance. However, new research studies are needed to shorten the curing time of canola protein isolated adhesives.

In conclusions, the addition of nanomaterials into a wood adhesive resin can prevent crack development, penetration of water and vapour into wood composite, reduce hot press time, improve mechanical and physical properties, and biological resistance against wood-deteriorating fungi of wood composites.

4.18 Polyvinyl acetate (PVA) wood adhesive

Polyvinyl acetate (PVA) is ready-to-use thermoplastic resins that set rapidly at room temperature. Due to the high dry strength, low clamping pressure, and competitive cost, PVA is widely used in the furniture industry [212]. PVA resists microorganisms attacks [213]. In addition to PVA, polyvinyl formal, and polyvinyl butyral are used to bond metals or plastics to wood [214].

PVA is a non-toxic, colourless thermoplastic adhesive made by polymerised vinyl acetate [215]. PVA with 15% of melamine-formaldehyde has shown better thermal stability than when it was used purely as a wood adhesive. The wood joint strength in wet conditions and elevated temperature were improved by adding a small amount of melamine urea

formaldehyde or melamine formaldehyde into PVA [216].

PVA has been used as a wood adhesive to bond oriental beech in order to investigate the effects of the amount of adhesive, pressing pressure, and pressing time on bonding strength [217]. Vitamin C was introduced as the reduction agent as an alternative to sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate to enhance the adhesive properties of PVA D3⁵ and also to minimise formaldehyde emission [218].

The tensile strength was doubled and the stiffness was increased by 50% by adding 0.1 vol% of graphene into PVA wood adhesive [219]. The bonding performance of environmentally friendly PVA emulsion adhesive can further be improved by copolymerising with vinyl acetate and butyl acrylate monomers [220]. PVA is also capable of attacking microorganisms in wood [213]. Drying oil-modified poly(vinyl acetate) shows improved water and solvent resistance [221]. Improved water and moisture resistance can also be achieved when aluminium salt is added to PVA [222].

PVA can also be used as a non-formaldehyde emitting wood adhesive directly or when blended with some other adhesives. It can minimise the formaldehyde emission when blended with formaldehyde-based wood adhesives.

4.19 Starch-based wood adhesives

Starch is a polysaccharide that can be obtained from roots, stalks, and seeds of staple crops⁶. It is a biodegradable, inexpensive, easily accessible, renewable, and readily available biopolymer that can be used as a wood adhesive [223, 224, 225]. The building blocks of starch are polymers of the six-carbon sugar D-glucose units consisting of two major bio-macromolecules-amylose and amylopectin [226]. Amylose has the ability to form a gel when the starch granule is cooked. Gel formation is the result of the retrogradation (re-association) of solubilised starch polymers after cooking [227, 228, 229, 230].

High amylose starch-based wood adhesive with the addition of sucrose fatty acid esters 6% (w/w, dry starch basis) was shown to be able to improve its dry and wet bonding strengths, storage stability and mobility adhesive [231]. Amylopectin is a branched polymer that has a much higher molecular weight than amylose [232].

The starch-based biopolymer system has advantages of low brittleness, low formaldehyde emission (when mixed with UF), and the ability to reduce water reduction adsorption [233]. The bonding strength and water-resistance of particleboard were improved significantly by adding isocyanates to the starch adhesive and UF as additives showing very low formaldehyde emission [234].

Epichlorohydrin-modified oil palm starch adhesive was used to make particleboard using rubberwood particles. Apart from water-resistance, the mechanical and physical properties of the resulting particleboards were able to meet the minimum required strength as stated in Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS A 5908: Particleboards) [235]. Particleboards made of non-modified oil palm starch adhesive met all mechanical properties but none of the

⁵Protected outside application field condition PVA

⁶rice, corn, wheat, tapioca and potato

physical properties such as water-resistance according to JIS [236]. However, carboxy-methyl starch-based adhesive which has hydrophilicity and stability during freezing and thawing was manufactured in order to enhance water-resistance [237]. Carboxymethyl starch (prepared by chemically modifying oil palm trunk starch with phosphoryl chloride) as a wood binder with rubberwood has shown better mechanical and physical properties compared to the panels bonded with native starch [37].

The addition of 1.5% – 2% (w/w of the total amount of dry starch) of sodium dodecyl sulphate into starch-based wood adhesive resulted to enhance significantly the resin mobility and storage stability although with a slight deterioration in the shear strength [238].

Corn-starch and tannin mixed wood adhesive has shown excellent structural stability according to European norms EN 312 (2004) [239]. Plywood panels bonded with a ratio corn starch:quebracho tannin:PF resins (15:5:80, w/w/w) exhibited better mechanical properties than plywood panels bonded with commercial PF [240]. Wood adhesive made by cross-linking corn-starch and polyvinyl alcohol with hexamethoxy-methylmelamine has shown excellent mechanical properties comparable to many of the commercially available UF plywood adhesives used for interior applications [241]. Starch-based wood adhesive cross-linked with γ -methacryloxypropyl trimethoxy silane has exhibited enhanced shear strength and storage stability showing improved apparent viscosity and less pseudo-plastic behaviour [242].

The cost of starch and polyvinyl alcohol-based cross-linked wood adhesives is lower or equivalent to conventional phenolic resins used as wood adhesives [243].

Acid hydrolysis of starch-based wood adhesive exhibited the optimal shear strengths of 6.65 MPa in the dry state and 3.6 MPa in the wet state with the improvement due to the grafting reaction and reduced steric hindrance [244].

Particleboard panels were manufactured using 15% corn starch-modified with glutaraldehyde and tested. The modulus of rupture and the internal bond strength of the panels met JIS [245].

In another study, starch-based polyvinyl acetate wood adhesive was made using graft copolymerisation of mixed grafting monomers vinyl acetate and butyl acrylate onto the grafting skeleton of corn starch. The resulting wood products showed to satisfy the national standard HG/T2727 - 95 especially with their compressive shear strength [246]. Corn-starch adhesives behave as pseudo-plastic fluids [247].

A graft-copolymerised high-performance starch-based wood adhesive prepared using H_2O_2 , a silane coupling agent and an olefin monomer as an oxidant, cross-linking agent and comonomer respectively has shown enhanced thermal stability and increased bonding strength and enhanced water-resistance [248].

Graft copolymerisation of vinyl acetate monomer onto corn-starch in aqueous solution was developed with a system based on potassium persulfate/acetone sodium bisulphite and higher shear strength was achieved [249]. Improved bonding performances were seen with the addition of sodium dodecyl sulphate to the starch wood-based adhesive [250]. High amylose starch-based wood adhesive with sodium dodecyl sulphate as an effective emulsifier increased the storage properties and bonding performance of wood adhesive in a low-temperature environment [251]. Also, It has also been shown that urea 15% (w/w) can be used as an effective additive for improving storage properties of starch-based wood adhesive

in a low-temperature environment [252].

The addition of montmorillonite to the starch-based wood adhesive was able to improve its overall performance [253]. A urea-oxidised starch wood adhesive also showed an excellent overall performance when a urea content of 50% (w/w, of dry starch basis) and 5.0% (w/w, of dry starch basis) KMnO_4 as the oxidiser were added to the adhesive [254].

Starch nanoparticles show better adhesive properties than starch microparticles [255]. The addition of silica nanoparticles (10%) into reinforced starch-based wood adhesive resulted in an increase of bonding strength by 50.1% in the dry state and 84.0% in wet state, and an increase in water-resistance by 20.2% [256].

Polyurethane adhesives synthesised from potato starch and natural oils by a transesterification reaction were found superior to the commercially available wood adhesive [257].

Another starch-based wood adhesive was prepared using dry esterification. After esterification, whereas the crystal structure types of native starch had not changed, the thermal stability had decreased, and more uniform distribution of adhesive at the bonding interface was achieved [258].

Very good internal bond strength and thickness swelling values were found when low-density particleboards were made using an adhesive system based on sour cassava starch [259]. Organic siloxane-modified starch-based wood adhesive via oxidised cassava starch and then grafted copolymerisation with acrylamide, butyl acrylate monomer, and vinyltrisopropoxysilane showed to increase the bonding strength and water-resistance. This was due to the starch-based adhesive multi-alkoxy silane reacting with the hydroxyl groups of the starch molecules and the two being crosslinked in the emulsion [260]. The addition of organic siloxane increases the bonding strength and water-resistance of cassava starch-based wood adhesive by reducing the content of the hydroxyl on the starch molecules [261].

Starch-based wood adhesive graft copolymerised with vinyl acetate at 90°C showed improved performance [262]. Performance of a high starch content wood adhesive can be enhanced by combining lauryl sodium sulphate with alkylphenol ethoxylates [263].

In conclusions, most of the modified starch-based wood adhesives satisfy international requirements on mechanical properties as well as physical properties such as water-resistance. The mobility and storage stability of starch-based adhesives can be enhanced by adding sodium dodecyl sulphate, sucrose, fatty acid esters and urea. Smaller starch particles showed to lead to better adhesive properties. The addition of nanoparticles into starch-based adhesives increases bonding strength as well as water-resistance.

4.20 Tannins Adhesives

Tannins can be sourced from wood, leaves, bark and plant fruits [2] and have been used industrially for five decades as an alternative to petroleum-derived phenolic resin for interior and exterior wood panels [264]. They are polyhydroxyphenols, and soluble in water, alcohols,

Figure 4.5: Commercial industrial particleboard panels after 15 years of unprotected exposure to the weather at 1500 meters of altitude in a high UV radiation area. Melamine-formaldehyde on the left, tannin-para-formaldehyde on the right [168].

and acetone [265]. Black wattle (*Acacia mearnsii*) bark was used to extract wattle tannins and used as a wood adhesive in Australia in the 1960s[266].

According to the phenolic nature of tannins, they can be classified into two groups as hydrolysable tannins and condensed tannins (90% of the total world production of commercial tannins) [168]. The phenolic composition of sumac root barks is higher in condensed tannins than in hydrolysable tannins [267], Similarly, Tunisian Aleppo pine barks are richer in condensed tannins than in hydrolysable tannins [268].

Tannins can be used as exterior grade weather-resistant wood adhesives cross-linked with formaldehyde [7]. As most phenolic adhesives, tannin-based adhesives emit formaldehyde at very low levels [269]. Chestnut (*Castanea sativa*) shell tannin extracts mixed with tris(hydroxymethyl)nitromethane, glyoxal and hexamine used as hardeners, showed better results than formaldehyde-free wood adhesive [270, 271, 272]. Tannin-phenol-formaldehyde adhesive cures faster than the commercial phenol-formaldehyde adhesive, which leads to shorter press time and therefore to an increase in productivity [273] and the same result were obtained with phenol-urea-formaldehyde-tannin too [274].

Tannins exhibit a similar reactive potential as phenol as a result of the phenolic type subunits contained in them. This increases the reactivity towards formaldehyde of 10 to 50 times due to the increase in hydroxyl substitutions. Formaldehyde reacts with tannins the same as it reacts with phenols forming methylene bridges. This causes a noticeable improvement in water and weather resistance [275]. Biocomposites made with pre-treated flax and tannins have shown to be highly resistant to mould growth [276]. Commercial industrial particleboard

panels made using either melamine-formaldehyde or tannin paraformaldehyde were exposed to the weather at 1500 *m* of altitude with high UV exposure for 15 years. Significant damages were observed to the edges of the melamine-formaldehyde particleboard panels, while tannin para-formaldehyde panels remain unchanged [168] as shown in Fig. 4.5.

A phenol-tannin-formaldehyde resin prepared using 50% tannin from acorns of valonia oak and phenol-formaldehyde resins showed comparable performance to PF only resins [277]. Modified onion skin tannin extract resins cured at ambient conditions satisfied the strength and durability requirements of the International Standards Organisations [278].

Purified pine bark tannins and food-grade, non-toxic, slow-reacting lignin-derived aldehydes were used for the preparation of adhesives capable of bonding wood particleboard. The resulting adhesive satisfied the relevant European standards [279].

4.20.1 Tannin-Hexamethylenetramin (Hexamine) adhesives

Hexamine ($C_6H_{12}N_4$) is one of the most common formaldehyde scavengers used in wood processing industries to minimise formaldehyde emissions from wood-based panels [280]. Hexamine is considered a non-formaldehyde-yielding compound and used as a hardener in tannin adhesives [281]. Tannin-hexamine⁷ adhesives, with hexamine being a non-formaldehyde yielding compound, are cheap and commercially available. They emit extremely low formaldehyde [6]. The main decomposition and re-composition mechanism of hexamine rather proceeds through reactive intermediates than directly forming formaldehyde. The use of hexamine as a hardener of tannin and tannin-hexamine adhesives makes them significantly environmentally friendly and the formaldehyde emissions, when measured in a chamber, have proven to be so low to be limited exclusively to what is generated by the wood itself. So, wood panels made with such type of adhesives are truly an E0⁸ panel [7]. Steam injection presses have shown better results for 'exterior grade boards' using tannin-hexamine adhesives. Hexamine is a reactive cross-linker that has also been used with corn flour-mimosa tannin-based adhesives (50:50), with resulting wood products showing good mechanical properties [282]. The chemical reaction between hexamine and tannin is shown in reaction 4.1. The mass proportion of tannin powder and hexamine ground was 5:1 [283].

Where, $n = 3 - m$,

Zinc salt has been used as catalysts in tannins and hexamine-based adhesives for better results and faster press time [7]. Resin mixtures of tannin and hexamine have been tested according to Japanese standards, JIS A 5908, and results are reported in Table 4.2. [284].

Corn-starch-tannin with hexamine as a wood adhesive resin was used to make plywood panels in order to compare the mechanical properties such as modulus of rupture (MOR), modulus of elasticity (MOE), dry tension strength, veneer failure and formaldehyde emission with those of commercial phenol formaldehyde [285]. The corn-starch-tannin adhesive

⁷hexamine is a non-formaldehyde-yielding compound

⁸Wood-based panel with no emission of formaldehyde whatsoever

Table 4.2: The results of thick laboratory panels bonded with Tanzanian mimosa tannin and hexamine. The total duration of steam injection was 60 seconds [284].

Tannin type	Hexa- mine	pH	Resin load	Board thickness	Press time	Board density	Dry IB strength	IB 4 h boil	24h cold water swelling	FE
	(%)		(%)	(mm)	(sec)	(kg/m ³)	(Mpa)	(Mpa)	(%)	(mg/L)
Mimosa-O	5	7.0	7	40	330	0.75	0.37		17.10	0.0
	5	8.0	7	40	330	0.75	0.57		14.40	0.0
	5	9.0	7	40	330	0.75	0.58		14.10	0.0
	5	10.0	7	40	330	0.74	0.73		12.80	0.0
Mimosa-T	5	10.0	7	25	380	0.85	0.95		12.00	0.0
	10	10.0	7	25	380	0.84	0.71		13.80	0.0
	15	10.0	7	25	380	0.81	0.78		15.00	0.0
	5	10.0	5	25	380	0.85	0.83	0.06	15.30	0.0
	5	10.0	7	25	380	0.83	0.82	0.07	12.00	0.0
	5	10.0	9	25	380	0.85	0.98	0.09	10.00	0.0
	5	10.0	7	40	380	0.75	0.78		12.00	0.0
Require							≥ 0.30		≤ 12.00	≤ 0.3

Table 4.3: MOR, MOE, dry tensile strength and formaldehyde emission results for plywood panels prepared with the experimental adhesive compared to results obtained with a phenol-formaldehyde resin and with wood alone. Six replicates of each adhesive. SD: Standard deviation [285].

Adhesives	MOR, MPa Mean \pm SD	MOE, MPa Mean \pm SD	Dry tension strength, MPa Mean \pm SD	Veneer Failure (%)	FE, <i>mg/m²/h</i>
Commercial phenol-formaldehyde	48 \pm 6.14	3310 \pm 866	2.07 \pm 0.04	> 95	2.62 \pm 0.19
Corn-starch-tannin	42 \pm 3.77	3122 \pm 544	1.86 \pm 0.22	> 80	0.20 \pm 0.08
Wood only control	-	-	-	-	0.17 \pm 0.04

Figure 4.6: Dry IB strengths as a function of tannin solution pH of laboratory particleboard prepared with four different tannin extracts without any aldehyde hardener, using only the lignocellulosic substrate-induced tannin autocondensation [288].

substituted by hexamine showed comparatively better mechanical properties to meet the international standard specifications [285] as shown in Table 4.3. Equal proportions of tannin/hexamine and non-purified glyoxalated lignin formulation shows a dry IB strength of $0.52 \pm 0.05 \text{ MPa}$ ⁹ and dry tensile strength of $1.2 \pm 0.20 \text{ MPa}$ ¹⁰ [286, 287].

4.20.2 Hardening by tannin autocondensation

Tannin autocondensation is done in the absence of aldehydes [288] and is an acid-catalysed oxidative condensation. Although the viscosity increases in the reaction, gelling does not generally occur. However, in the presence of a small amount of dissolved silica catalyst and some other catalysts and on a lignocellulosic surface, gelling takes place [6].

The dry internal bond (IB) strength of interior particleboards prepared using Pecan and Pine tannins showed 0.8 MPa when pH was 13 satisfying German industrial standards (DIN 68763) requirements. The IB requirement for DIN 68763 is 0.35 MPa or above. Nevertheless, Mimosa and Quebracho tannin could not achieve this as depicted in Fig.4.6 [288].

Dry strength of wood panels bonded with tannins was increased with autocondensation reactions. However, the exterior grade performance of the panels remained unchanged as it mainly depends on poly-condensation reactions with aldehydes rather than autocondensation reactions [289].

Tannin autocondensation was shown to increase by adding boric acid into induced quebracho tannin. This decreased the pressing time and cure temperature increasing the modulus of elasticity [290].

⁹European Norm EN 314-2 requirement is ≥ 0.35

¹⁰EN 314-2 requirements is ≥ 1.0

Particleboards bonded with aningre (*Aningeria spp.*) tannin adhesives have satisfied the particleboard dry IB strength requirements for panels for general purposes used in dry environments of the standard (Norm NF EN 312-2: 1996) [291].

Shear refinement (290 *rpm* and 5 *min*, optimal conditions) was done for corn starch–mimosa tannin wood adhesives to reduce the viscosity (from 100,000 *Pa s* to 458 *Pa s*) while mechanical properties remained the same [292].

A polenta corn-starch-mimosa tannin-UF (10:4:86; mass ratios) adhesive mixture exhibited better mechanical properties and also less formaldehyde emission than boards made from commercial UF resins [293].

Extraction of condensed tannins from grape pomace was tested using a mixture of water-sodium hydroxide at 120 °C. Promising properties for wood adhesive applications were obtained by using 10% of NaOH [294, 295]. Similar results were obtained with 5% of aqueous NaOH extract of maritime pine *Pinus pinaster* [296]. Combination of 70% tannin, 21% pMDI and 9% of glyoxal shows dry IB strength 0.6 *MPa* with low formaldehyde emissions of 0.6 *mg/100g* [297].

Condensed tannins such as wattle (Mimosa) extract could partially be modified through hydrolysis of a benzyl ether link and the consequent opening of the flavonoid heterocyclic ring, through sulphitation. These sulphited tannin adhesives demonstrated to be useful in applications, such as particleboard manufacture [298].

Barbatimao tannin adhesive as a substitute for PF during plywood production had a significant effect on the water absorption, wet shear strength, and modulus of perpendicular elasticity [299]. In another study, a novel wood adhesive was made by mixing procyanidin-type condensed tannin and polyethylenimine [300].

In conclusions, the advantage of using tannins as a bio-based adhesive is that they can be cross-linked by formaldehyde in a polycondensation reaction in order to get an exterior grade weather-resistant wood adhesive. Resin made by adding 50% of tannins into PF can show comparable performance to PF only resin. This can minimise cost and formaldehyde emissions. The combination of tannin and hexamine shows improved performance as a non-toxic wood adhesive.

4.21 Unsaturated oil adhesives

Unsaturated vegetable oils consist of at least one double bond. So, they can be used as wood and wood composite adhesives by oxidising the double bonds followed by their carbonation [301]. Resin can be prepared by using linseed oil, which can be used as a wood adhesive or surface-coating material [302]. Epoxidation of linseed oil double bond followed by cross-linking with a cyclic polycarboxylic acid anhydride builds up its molecular weight by adding carboxylic groups into it. These can then react with hydroxyls of wood cell walls by adjoining one wood cell to another [7]. Cross-linking can be varied by the addition of specialised catalysts and preparing the samples at a range of temperature (120 °C - 180 °C) and the resulting wood products shows high water tolerance. The high costs and the long pressing time required are the main disadvantages of linseed oil wood adhesive [303].

On the other hand, it has been shown that hydroxyl fatty acid of oilseed crop has great potential application in adhesives [304].

These resins have major disadvantages in the wood adhesive industry such as slow hot-pressing time, relatively high price and unfavourable environmental profile [7].

Bio-resins based on soybean oils were developed as a replacement of polyester resins. These liquid bio-resins were obtained from plant and animal triglycerides by functionalising the triglyceride with chemical groups¹¹ that can make them polymerisable. Soy oil-based resins have a strong affinity for natural fibres, and this could make them a better fibre-matrix interface as determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). These resins can be considered as a candidate replacement for phenol-formaldehyde, urethane, and other petroleum-based binders in particleboard, MDF, oriented strand board (OSB), etc [305].

Cashew nutshell liquid consists mainly of cardanol. It has phenolic nuclei and an unsaturated fatty acid chain as shown in Fig. 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Chemical structure of cardanol.

So, cardanol's dual nature implies a potential as natural raw material for water-resistant resins and polymers. Double bonds in the chain can be used to form hardened networks. Nevertheless, the modifications of the alkenyl chain need several reaction steps, which are too expensive for the commercial wood adhesive industry [7]. Unsaturated oil such as sunflower oil is a commonly available material. Following ozonolysis and reduction of sunflower oil and after the co-reaction of the obtained non-volatile long-chain aldehyde with flavonoid tannins from radiata pine (*Pinus radiata*), the resulting adhesive was used to make particleboards, which showed to contain a relatively low amount of formaldehyde [306]. Ozonolysis and reduction of soybean oil produced aldehyde oil, malonaldehyde, capraldehyde and pelargonaldehyde, which can be used as wood adhesives [307].

Urea Formaldehyde and acrylic-epoxidised soy oil (ASEO) were used to make wheat straw particleboard with different resin content levels and different pressing times. The mechanical and physical properties of ASEO-bonded particleboards show better results than UF-bonded boards, especially in internal bonding and thickness swelling [308]. Jatropha oil is

¹¹epoxy, carboxyl, hydroxyl, vinyl, amine

a non-edible oil and has 78.5% unsaturated fatty acids and was used to make Jatropha oil-based polyurethane wood adhesive. It has shown better shear strength, and its response to hot water, acid, and alkali was superior compared to palm oil-based wood adhesives [309]. Wood adhesives prepared from softwood bark residues pyrolysis oil developed for exterior-grade oriented strand board (OSB) have shown significantly improved internal bond strength and thickness swelling [310].

In conclusions, ozonolysis and reduction of unsaturated long-chain oils can produce aldehyde oils. However, the major issues with unsaturated oil-based adhesives are slow hot-press time, high costs of oil and unfavourable environmental profile.

4.22 Seed meal (seed flour) wood adhesive

Finely grounded untreated seed meals (defatted meals), water-washed meals and their protein isolate can be used as a wood adhesive [311]. However, the adhesive viscosity and the hydrodynamic volume of its components should be small enough for the adhesive to be able to penetrate the wood. Although soy flour is economically viable, its adhesive strength is much lower than that of commercial soy protein isolate [312]. Water washing can enrich the protein content by 12% to 25% in the washed meal of water-insoluble fraction [313]. Water washed or phosphate buffer washed cottonseed meals has shown better water-resistance than cottonseed protein isolate. This is a low-cost and environmentally friendly protein-based adhesive, which does not incorporate corrosive alkali and acid solutions for the extraction of its protein isolate [314]. Tung oil increased the adhesive strength of water washed cottonseed meal and of its protein isolate by 19.9% and 21.1%, respectively. In addition to that, the water-resistances were increased by 46.6% and 41.3%, respectively [315].

The increase in the percentage of mechanical properties of protein isolate from a water-washed meal is lower when compared with the economic effort that has to be made to produce protein isolate from the defatted meal. Usage of water washed seed meals as wood adhesive gives economic benefits compared to protein isolates.

4.23 Miscellaneous Wood Adhesive

PF, pMDI, epoxy and starch resin/adhesive made by blending or synthesising bio-oil are used to manufacture plywood, OSB, particleboard and flakeboard [316]. Glyoxal-monomethylol urea prepared by synthesising the non-volatile and non-toxic aldehyde glyoxal and monomethylol urea was used to make plywood panels. The results showed the dry shear strength of 0.90 *MPa* satisfying the China National Standard GB/T 9846.3-2004 [317].

Another study showed that the addition of 20% to 30% of animal glue into melamine-formaldehyde adhesives does not deteriorates the mechanical properties of wood-based composites. This can lower the cost of resin adhesive [318].

Locust bean gum, guar gum, xanthan gum and tamarind gum were used as wood adhesives. The gum dispersion in commercial poly(vinyl acetate) proved that it can be used as

a binder for wood adhesives [319].

Amazonic White Pitch (*Protium heptaphyllum*) studied as an environmentally friendly wood adhesive showed a shear strength higher than the tensile strength [320].

An adhesive made using peanut meal, sodium dodecyl sulphate and glycol diglycidyl ether fulfilled the requirements for interior used plywood [321].

Pea (*Pisum sativum L.*) protein as a valid alternative to soy proteins resulted to be a wood adhesive with improved water-resistance when an additive was included in the mixture [55]. Vanillin is a bio-based epoxy, which showed properties close to the current Bisphenol A-based industrial adhesive [322].

In conclusions, different types of biopolymers can be used as wood adhesive directly or when blended with some other wood adhesives. Consideration of their chemistry and changing the physical parameters during the process of manufacturing can deliver better performance of wood-based panels.

4.24 Conclusion and future perspectives

This paper has reviewed potential non-toxic and/or bio-based wood adhesives that can be used directly or in combination with synthetic adhesives in order to achieve mechanical and physical properties that satisfy the international standards or are similar to the industrially used reference adhesives such as urea-formaldehyde. In addition to that, the usage of bio-based wood adhesives, either way, reduces or eliminates the toxic formaldehyde emission satisfying the formaldehyde emission requirement of the international standards. This allows opportunities for particleboard manufacturer to re-manufacture the panels over and over again. Although some synthetic wood adhesives such as pMDI that do not emit formaldehyde show better performance than the formaldehyde-based ones, they are economically not viable in the industrial scale.

Even though soy-based wood adhesives are the major constituent of the bio-based wood adhesive sector and are economically viable, their physical properties need to be improved. A number of ongoing research studies are currently focusing on the enhancement of the water-resistance of soy-based wood adhesive.

The main advantage of bio-based wood adhesives is that they can be used as a wood adhesive directly or blended with some other bio-based or synthetic wood adhesives to enhance the mechanical and/or physical properties of wood panels. Such hybrid adhesive formulations are much easier to adapt to the current wood adhesive manufacturing lines in the wood panel industries. The non-toxic adhesives with their potential advantages and blendabilities are shown in Table 4.4.

4.24.1 Future challenges and perspectives

In general, the interaction between different types of biopolymers and some other compounds that can be blended to make adhesives can contribute to the adhesive strength of the resulting

Table 4.4: Non-toxic, bio-based wood adhesive with potential advantages and blendability.

Adhesive	Potential advantage	Can be blended with
Lignin	Abundant and low cost [7, 324, 173]	Tannin [7, 186], glyoxal [324, 192], PF [189], pMDI [6, 7], Hexamine [7].
Tannin	Weather-resistant [7]	Glyoxal, hexamine [270, 271, 272], PF [273, 299], corn-starch [285], phenol-urea-formaldehyde [274].
Canola protein	Second largest oilseed crop product [56, 57]	Hydrophilic bentonite, surface modified nanoclay [211].
Wheat gluten	Abundant, inexpensive [12].	Alkaline solutions [16], UF [18].
Cotton-seed protein	Higher shear strength [129]	Starch, xylan, cellulose [135], guanidine hydrochloride GuHCl, sodium dodecyl sulfonate, urea, and alkali [134].
Soy-based	Low cost [62]	Maleic anhydride, polyethylemine [66], CaCO ₃ [67], lignin [68], blood, casein [70], glyoxalated lignin, tannin [72], hydroxymethyl phenol [77], POCl ₃ [88], polyethyleneimine, NaOH [83], sodium sulfite and sodium dodecyl sulfate [85], epichlorohydrin ammonium hydroxide, NaOH [90].
Geopolymer	Pozzolanic by-product	Silica fume [140].
Unsaturated oil	Good for exterior-grade applications [310]	UF and acrylic-epoxidised soy oil [308].
Xylan	By-product in pulp industry [150]	Poly(vinyl alcohol), poly(vinylamine), glyoxal, hexa(methoxymethyl) melamine [151].
Starch	Readily available [223, 224, 225]	Sucrose fatty acid esters [231], sodium dodecyl sulphate [238], quebracho tannin, PF resins [240], polyvinyl alcohol with hexamethoxy-methylmelamine [241], γ -Methacryloxypropyl trimethoxy silane [242], H ₂ O ₂ , a silane coupling agent and an olefin monomer [248], grafting monomers vinyl acetate [246], glutardialdehyde [245], urea [252], silica nanoparticles [256], polyurethane [257], acrylamide, butyl acrylate monomer, and vinyltriisopropoxysilane [260], lauryl sodium sulphate with alkylphenol ethoxylates [263].

resins. As a result of this, future research study can have the possibilities of adding chemical modifications to the innovative bio-based resins by considering their chemical structures. In addition to the chemical structures, other factors such as thermal degradation and ability to make mechanical interlockings play a major role in the bonding of wood. Nanometre length scale wood adhesive interactions should also be considered when mechanical interlocking is concerned [323].

Formaldehyde emissions of synthetic adhesives can be minimised up to international standards by incorporating bio-based adhesives into them without degrading the physical and mechanical properties of the resulted wood-based panels. This is mostly due to the bio-based wood adhesives behaving as formaldehyde scavengers. Pizzi et al 2013 [325] has classified future challenges of bio-based wood adhesive into four sections.

1. Performance and application compared to synthetic adhesives,
2. Cost compared to synthetic adhesives,
3. Supply of raw materials,
4. Natural resistance to change and resistance to destroy the existing synthetic wood adhesive market.

New research is also needed to reduce the press time, increase the water and moisture resistance, find cheaper raw materials and alternative products, recycle and reuse and reduce the emissions in hybrid wood adhesive systems [325].

Identification of the type of protein that gives the best adhesive properties has not been discovered yet. Although the cost of the plant seed meals is low, extracting protein isolate is expensive. The adhesive properties of water washed and/or buffer washed plant seed meal fractions can be compared with that of protein isolate of the same plant seed. It will also be necessary to find alternatives for using human consumable plant products as a bio-based wood adhesive when future global food security is concerned [326].

Another issue identified is that a noticeable bio-based adhesive strength loss was seen after 12 months of storage [327]. New research studies are needed to overcome the durability problems in bio-based adhesives and a systematic approach is needed to transfer bio-based adhesive to the commercially available productions [326].

Ultimately, the end-user of wood-based panels should be satisfied with the cost, quality, durability and the desired quantity. In order to do that, a sustainable manufacturing approach that can compete with the existing market should be implemented.

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Chapter 5

Methodology

“The woods seemed all answer and
healing and more than enough to live for”

Josephine Winslow Johnson

Wood adhesives in the wood-based panel industry are being tested against the mechanical and physical properties of the wood-based panels produced. Wood-based panels are made by varying different parameters as in Table 1.1 in Chapter 1 in order to achieve optimal results for mechanical and physical properties. In this work, laboratory-scale particleboards were made to validate the adhesive formulations. The research and development sector on the industrial scale makes bigger samples compared to the university lab-scale samples. Nevertheless, the results for mechanical and physical properties of particleboard samples produced in this work with novel bio-based adhesives are compared against the international industrial standards for the validation of the binders.

In this study, three different hot-press systems were used to manufacture particleboard samples.

1. Laboratory scale manual hot-press system to make lower density particleboard samples at Cranfield University.
2. Laboratory scale hydraulic hot-press system to make higher density particleboard samples at Cranfield University.
3. Industrial scale hydraulic hot-press system to make higher density three-layer particleboard samples at Kastamonu particleboard factory in Adana Turkey.

5.1 Industrial Scale Samples

The cross-section of industrial-scale particleboard samples consists of a core-layer in the middle and two surface layers. Approximately equal masses of wood particles are used in

Figure 5.1: Industrial-scale particleboard pre-press and hot-press in continuous-press system [4].

every three layers. The wood particle size of the core-layer is between 1 *mm* and 5 *mm*. Wood particles below 1 *mm* are used for the two surface layers.

Each type of wood particles is dried in order to reduce the moisture content below 5%. They are then being mixed with the adhesives using a blade-grinder at 1000 *rpm*. If the adhesive formulation is a powder, water or a liquid chemical such as NaOH solution is added until it reaches a moisture content of at least 15%. Higher moisture content can burst the sample during the heat curing process.

5.1.1 Press factor

The press factor is defined in the wood-based panel industry as in Eq. 1.3 in Chapter 1. It plays a significant role in some adhesive formulations [1]. In general, reducing the press factor reduces internal bond (IB) strength. Higher press factors such as 32 *s/mm* – 37.5 *s/mm* are being used for bio-based adhesive formulations as they are not as volatile as the synthetic adhesives [2].

5.1.2 Resin content

The resin content (adhesive content) of the surface-layer is assumed to be 10% while that of core-layer is 8% when synthetic resins are used on the industrial scale three-layer samples. However, the bio-based resin content used in the wood adhesive sector is much higher than that of synthetic resin. This is one of the main disadvantages of using bio-based wood adhesive industrially. It is needed to have 50% (wt) of lignin-based wood adhesive to make wood composites. The high content of bio-based resins is incorporated due to poor solubility, when dry adhesives and liquid chemicals are mixed, increase in viscosity, poor storage stability and decreasing the curing rate. The percentage of resin content depends on the type of the bio-based adhesives [3]. In this study, 35% (wt) of resin content was used in order to achieve the relevant industrial standards of the samples.

Figure 5.2: Industrial-scale particleboard sample preparation with alkali-treated wheat gluten with sodium alginate resin at [Kastamonu](#) particleboard factory in Adana Turkey.

5.1.3 R & D samples

Research and development centres working on the wood-based panel industries use a batch-press method for making research samples, while the continuous-press as shown in Fig. 5.1 was used when they were commercially produced. In order to manufacture the panels tested in this work, the dried wood particles and the liquid wood adhesive mixture for the core-layer and the surface-layers were made at the same time in order to make samples that were not influenced by the shelf life of the adhesive formulation. If the wood adhesive was a powder, it was mixed with dried wood particles first and water or the recommended solution was mixed afterwards by spraying until the moisture content of the final mixture reaches between 15% - 18% (wt.). An industrial-scale cake mixer was used for mixing purposes. A high moisture content of the wood particles and adhesive mixture leads to bursting at high temperature and pressure. On the other hand, a sufficient amount of bonding was not formed when the moisture content was lower than 15%. Then one part of the surface-layer mixture was poured and levelled inside a frame of 1500 mm × 1500 mm. The core-layer was then poured and levelled on top of that. Finally, the other part of the surface layer was then poured and levelled as in Fig. 5.2a and Fig. 5.2b.

The frame was then removed with care and the three-layer sample was placed on the pre-heated (up to 180°C) hydraulic hot-press machine shown in Fig. 5.2c. Then the sample

was pressed up to a certain thickness (18 *mm*) or up to certain pressure (5 *MPa*) and held it for a certain period of time (10 *min*) for the curing process to happen as in Fig. 5.2d. Usually, the press time for particleboard samples made using synthetic adhesive was about 5 *min*. The press factor for the synthetic adhesive was around 15 *s/mm*. After that, the sample was dried in air for at least 24 hours before the mechanical and physical tests. Tests were then done, and results compared against international industrial standards. The industrial scale manufacturing process of wood-based panels has been mentioned in section 1.12.

5.2 Laboratory Scale Samples

In this work, laboratory scale particleboard samples were made using a single homogenous layer of wood particles. By considering the surface qualities and better mechanical and physical properties, 1 *mm* wood particles were used to make samples. In this work first, the wood particles were oven-dried at 130°C for 3 hours at 800 *mbar* pressure in order to reduce the moisture to 5%. Dried wood particles were then mixed with the resin formulation using a paint mixture while adding a spray of water or a chemical liquid until the right moisture content was reached. A paint mixer drill or a cake mixer was used to give it a proper unique mix. The quality of the mixing was an important processing parameter that can significantly improve the performance of the final product of particleboard samples made using bio-based adhesives [5].

5.2.1 Direct Hot-press Method

An aluminium mould was used to make the samples by considering the heat conductivity of the material and avoiding bursting out. The size of the mould was designed according to the requirements of the industrial standards. Samples needed to be a minimum size of 200 *mm* × 50 *mm* × 10 *mm* strips of samples in order to get the modulus of rupture (MOR) and modulus of elasticity (MOE) according to the Japanese industrial standards JIS A 5908. The sample size for the internal bond test should be 50 *mm* × 50 *mm*. By considering the dimensional requirements and the above factors, the size of the mould was designed as 210 *mm* × 210 *mm*.

The wood-resin mixture was poured into the mould and levelled, and then the piston was placed on the sample and the mould was then positioned on the heated plate and the pressure was applied on top of the piston of the mould. After a certain period of time, the sample was taken off and left for cooling and it was cut for mechanical and physical testing.

5.2.2 Pre-press followed by Hot-press Method

The sample was pre-pressed in between two aluminium sheets and then it was pressed using a hydraulic hot press. Pre-pressing consolidates the cold sample and encourages the transfer of wet adhesive formulation into wood particles [6]. In the continuous process of manufacturing particleboard, pre-press (cold-press) was done prior to the hot-press. Most of the commercially made particleboards were made by using the continuous process that contains the pre-press section as in Fig. 5.1a and the hot-press section as in Fig. 5.1b. However, at laboratory-scale,

Figure 5.3: Laboratory-scale particleboard sample preparation.

a mould was used for pre-pressing and hot-pressing. Laboratory-scale particleboard sample preparation used in this study is shown in Fig. 5.3.

5.3 Testing of samples

Hot-pressed samples were kept for one day to reach their constant weight. Then they were cut to size as in Fig. 5.4 according to industrial standards specification for physical and mechanical tests. A rectangular piece of the sample was first used for the 3-point flexural test and then each piece was being used for the thickness swelling test and moisture content test. Three of the square shape samples were being used for the density test first and then for the IB test. The remaining square shape samples were stored for future tests to assess the biodegradation of the samples with time.

Moisture content test and the thickness swelling test of samples were performed as mentioned in sections 3.3.2 and 3.3.1 following the method in Fig. 3.3. Bending strength (MOR), bending Young's modulus (MOE) and internal bond (IB) were evaluated by the methods mentioned in the sections 3.2.1, 3.2.2 and 3.2.3 respectively.

Figure 5.4: Cutting to the size of the particleboard for physical and mechanical tests.

5.4 Taguchi design of experiments

Based on the results of physical and mechanical tests, Taguchi design of experiments was used to see the behaviour of input parameters. The software 'MINITAB 16' was used for the analysis. The optimal composition of dry adhesive contents could be evaluated by using the Taguchi design of experiments in order to maximise the physical and mechanical properties of the adhesive formulation.

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Chapter 6

Alkali-treated wheat gluten with sodium alginate as a bio-based wood adhesive for interior grade particleboard

“Nature soothes us. Nature heals us, and something more, the woods are a place of power. Any woods that are still surviving on this planet, those are powerful areas to have kept themselves free from the encroachment of the industrial societies of our earth.”

Frederick Lindemann

Abstract

Formaldehyde emission coming out from most of the synthetic wood adhesives available is considered human carcinogenic. Usage of depleting petrochemicals and emission of greenhouse gases during the life cycle of wood-based panels are some other disadvantages of using synthetic adhesives. Most of the bio-based adhesives are biodegradable and can be derived from agricultural and industrial by-products. The formaldehyde emission can be minimised by replacing synthetic adhesive with bio-based adhesives. In this study, virgin wood particles and recycled wood particles from used particleboard made using synthetic adhesives were used to make particleboards with the bio-based resin formulation. The mechanical properties such as bending strength and internal bond strength of the particleboards made by the use of bio-based adhesives were taken. Wheat gluten (WG) as the main constituent, was mixed with NaOH as an alkali treatment in order to break its disulphide bonds. The results showed that the alkali-treated WG indicating of secondary interaction with sodium alginate can be used as a bio-based wood adhesive because the mechanical properties of the resultant wood particleboards satisfy ‘Type 8 Base particleboard Decorative particleboard’ according to

Japanese industrial standards JIS A 5908:2015.

Keywords: Sodium alginate, wheat gluten, bentonite, particleboard.

6.1 Introduction

It has been revealed that the formaldehyde emission coming out from furniture made using synthetic wood adhesives is toxic for human beings due to its carcinogenic nature [1]. Although the wood itself emits formaldehyde, its contribution is insignificant [2]. Formaldehyde emission coming out from furniture can be minimised by using bio-based wood adhesive formulations as an alternative to synthetic wood adhesives in the manufacturing process of furniture and wood-based panels by optimising the indoor air quality [3]. Sodium alginate, wheat gluten and bentonite were considered as raw materials for the wood adhesive formulation in this study. The objective of this study is to validate whether the bio-based binder of alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate with virgin wood particles and re-cycled wood particles would satisfy industrial standards.

The basic raw material for the production of sodium alginate (SA) is brown algae [4]. Alginates are unbranched polysaccharides and complex carbohydrate polymers derived from brown seaweeds [5]. Tens of million tons (frozen weight) of seaweeds are harvested from offshore and onshore [6]. Alginates are used in industrial applications considering their properties of gelling, viscousifying and stabilising [7]. SA has been used as a biodegradable additive in the papermaking industry with polyamideamine-epichlorohydrin to increase the mechanical properties of the cycled fibres [8]. SA needs to be blended or modified or copolymerised with some other biopolymers in order to be used as a structural scaffold [9].

The chemical structure of SA shown in Fig. 6.1 shows the ability to react with wood cell wall hydroxyl groups when SA is dissolved in water.

Bentonite is a highly viscous binder [11] used in the production of moulds for scaffolds due to its high thermal stability [12, 13]. Alkaline bentonite binder can be used in roasted-pellet production [14]. The addition of bentonite has enhanced the strengths of green pellet [15]. By considering these factors, bentonite was selected for this study as an additive for the bio-

Figure 6.1: Chemical structure of sodium alginate molecule [9, 10].

Figure 6.2: A structural model for wheat gluten [27, 28].

based wood adhesive formulation. Wheat gluten (WG) is the rubbery mass that remains after the wheat dough is water washed to remove starch granules [16]. WG is an abundant protein source [17] that can be obtained as a by-product from wheat starch processing [18]. It consists of acid dispersible glutenin having elastic properties, alcohol soluble gliadin having viscous properties [19]. WG complex mixture comprises 80% wheat protein, and the rest is lipids, polysaccharides, and minerals [18, 19]. Rigid bio-based materials can be made using wheat gluten by high-temperature compressions [20]. Wheat gluten can also be blended with some other polymers at high temperatures in order to manufacture bioplastics [21].

Natural adhesives can be made using WG due to its ability to film-forming and its thermoplastic properties. WG adhesives are being used to produce pressure-sensitive medical bandages and adhesive tapes [22]. As an elastomeric protein, wheat gluten possesses cohesive and unique viscoelastic properties showing the suitability for material applications such as wood adhesives [23, 24]. Gluten protein can be divided into two groups according to molecular weight as high-molecular-weight (HMW) and low-molecular-weight (LMW) glutenin subunits [25, 26].

HMW and LMW subunits are connected with disulphide bonds in wheat gluten structure as shown in Fig. 6.2. Gluten consists of hundreds of proteins. These proteins are present as monomers, oligo or polymers linked with inter-chain disulphide bonds [16, 27, 28]. The solubility of protein progressively increases with alkaline pH values [29]. Degradation of disulphide bonds can be done by adding 0.2M NaOH at 25°C [30]. Disulphide bonds dominate the crosslinks at 130°C and the non-disulphide bonds are contributing to the protein network at 150°C [31]. WG is not dispersible in water due to its high amount of non-polar amino acids, but it is dispersible with alkali and acid as its isoelectric point is 7.3 [19, 32]. A mixture of WG and 0.2M NaOH as a

wood adhesive applied on wood panels and heated at 130°C for 15 minutes under a pressure of 0.7 MPa has provided the optimum bond line thickness and the highest bond strength of 7.07 MPa [33].

WG mixed with starch (50/50), grafted with methylmethacrylate, crosslinked with citric acid and nanofilled with TiO₂ has exhibited excellent thermal stability, water-resistance and mechanical properties [34]. WG can also be blended with synthetic wood adhesives. In order to improve physical properties such as water absorption and thickness swelling of high-density particleboard using reed instead of wood particle, 80% of WG was modified with urea-formaldehyde resin alone as well as with the addition of 1% and 2% boric acid as a fungicide. However, the mechanical properties such as modulus of rupture, modulus of elasticity and internal bond strength were not changed by adding boric acid [35]. The addition of a small proportion of an isocyanate on hydroxymethylated or glyoxalated hydrolysed gluten protein has made the adhesive even better [36]. The addition of triacetin into a phenol-formaldehyde blended WG resin showed an increase in the internal bond strength by over 30% [37].

Two-steps WG dispersion in wood, which consisted of drying the glued chips in-between the first and the second addition, has been shown to be more beneficial compared to the one-step process [32]. Dispersion concentration, viscosity and the application method were the main factors affecting wheat gluten dispersion into wood particles. However, the effect of drying temperature, presence of crosslinkers, dispersing agent and type of wood species seemed to affect minimally WG dispersion into the wood particles [38]. Improved bond strength and water resistance were achieved by using wood adhesives of hydrolysed WG treated at 90°C and finally dispersed in 0.1 M NaOH(aq) [23]. Bioproducts such as cups, plates and boxes were made by using banana fibre-wheat gluten [39]. Aqueous NaOH has the ability to activate wood surfaces effectively to give them strong adhesive bonds [40].

Nowadays, most bio-based wood adhesives satisfying industrial standards are expensive due to small-scale production and the high production cost. Wheat gluten as a by-product [41] as well as a co-product [42, 43] in the wheat starch industry is readily available and comparatively less expensive than other bio-based wood adhesives such as tannin.

In this study, compared to the amount of WG used in the adhesives mixture, a smaller amount of sodium alginate and NaOH are required to prepare the adhesive formulation. They are readily available and relatively less expensive. Therefore, it is economical to use them to prepare an adhesive formulation to make interior grade particleboard satisfying industrial standards.

This research study was carried out to illustrate that alkali-treated wheat gluten indicating of secondary interaction with sodium alginate can be used as a bio-based wood adhesive to fabricate interior grade particleboard with the appropriate bending strength and internal bond strength.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Materials

Wheat gluten was purchased from [Buy Whole Foods Online Ltd.](#) Sodium alginate was bought from [Sigma Aldrich](#). Bentonite and NaOH were bought from [Fisher Scientific](#). [Kastamonu Entegre](#) in Adana Turkey provided 1 mm virgin wood particles. Re-cycled wood particles of size 1 mm were provided by [French Inst. of Tech. for Forest-based and Furniture Sector](#).

6.3 Preparation of samples

Wood particles were dried in a vacuum oven at 130°C for 3 hours until the moisture becomes less than 5%. Mixtures of wheat gluten, sodium alginate and bentonite were mixed with the wood particles (virgin and recycled) by changing various parameters. 1M NaOH solution was sprayed into the mixture until the moisture content of the mixture was 18%. It was measured by using a wood moisture meter. The samples were hot-pressed for 15 min at 150°C at the pressure of 1.4 MPa. The dimension of the particleboard samples prepared was 210 mm × 210 mm × 10 mm. Samples were cut and underwent 3-point-bend-test and internal bond (IB) test using the 5/100 kN Instron 5500R Electro-mechanical machine. An environmental scanning electron microscope (E-SEM) was used to analyse the composition of samples. Small pieces of particleboard samples were gold coated prior to the E-SEM analysis. The resin itself was analysed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) technique to evaluate chemical bonding and the nature of indicating secondary interaction.

6.3.1 Taguchi design of experiments

Based on the number of variable parameters such as the amount of wood particles, bentonite, sodium alginate and wheat gluten, a relevant Taguchi orthogonal array was made. The software [MINITAB 16](#) was used to analyse the experimental results. This was helpful to reduce the number of experimental trials necessary for the optimisation of the material.

6.3.2 Environmental scanning electron microscopy analysis

Samples for E-SEM was prepared by crushing both types of particleboard samples. They were then gold coated. [FEI XL30](#) machine was used for the analysis.

6.3.3 X-ray diffraction analysis

In-situ preparation of samples of wheat gluten, sodium alginate and the appropriate mixture of wheat gluten and sodium alginate was mixed with 1M NaOH solution to prepare the samples for x-ray diffraction analysis. Measurements were then performed at room temperature.

6.3.4 FTIR analysis

In this work, FTIR was employed to investigate the absorption characteristics of uncured and cured samples following synthesis to identify the chemical bonds of the compounds and the transformation of their functional groups subjected to curing. FTIR analysis was performed using an attenuated total reflection (ATR) accessory that allows determining the change in chemical functional groups under different process conditions. The degree of chemical stability after curing was evaluated using ATR-FTIR technique which primarily relies on sample path length and depth of penetration of IR evanescent wave from ATR sampling interface into a thin layer of the sample surface. It should be noted that the test sample should be in direct contact with the ATR crystal plane enabling effective penetration of IR evanescent wave, e.g., a higher volume of interaction with sample to enhance the absorbance. As the sample can be solid, porous and powder having an irregular shape, a high-pressure clamp with a swivel tip was adapted to deform the solid surface to improve its contact with the ATR window. This allows for resolving the shoulder peaks of the main bonds having lower intensity. In addition, the accuracy of measurements depends on the refractive index contrast of the ATR prism and the test sample. The refractive index analysis of wheat gluten and sodium alginate was beyond the scope of this paper.

In this work, FTIR equipment, model Jasco 6200 was used in conjunction with PIKE MIRacle ATR accessory, and ZnSe crystal plate was fitted as ATR sampling interface. Initially, the set-up was calibrated in the air to reduce the effect of environmental conditions before the sample assessments over a wide wavenumber range from 4000 cm^{-1} to 550 cm^{-1} . The ATR-FTIR absorbance spectra of uncured and cured resins of alkali-treated wheat gluten, indicating secondary interaction with sodium alginate liquid and solid form respectively, and wheat gluten in powder form were compared in FTIR analysis in Figures 6.7 and 6.8.

6.4 Results and discussion

6.4.1 Statistical analysis

Taguchi design of experiments method was used to evaluate the influence on the modulus of rupture (bending strength) of compositions of the resin mixture. It showed that an increase in the quantity of bentonite in the resin reduced the modulus of rupture of the sample. While increasing the quantity of wheat gluten, the bending strength of the samples increased as shown in Fig. 6.3 based on Table 6.1. By considering the Taguchi design of the experiment chart, the weight proportions of wood particle, wheat gluten and sodium alginate were chosen as 62%, 31% and 7% (w/w) respectively in order to achieve optimal bending strength. The concentration of NaOH needed was 1M in order to minimise the agglomeration of the resin mixture.

6.4.2 E-SEM analysis

The adhesive resin was used to prepare particleboards using virgin wood particles and recycled wood-based panel particles. Both particleboards were made of the same size.

Table 6.1: The table of changes of quantities of adhesive components and the resulted bending strength for Taguchi analysis. Detailed tables are Table C.1 and Table C.2.

Particleboard number	Wood particles (g)	Bentonite (g)	Sodium alginate (g)	Wheat gluten (g)	Bending strength (MPa)
09	200	45	30	0	4.21
10	200	40	35	0	4.43
11	200	29	57	0	4.80
12	200	43	57	0	5.20
13	200	29	71	0	5.88
14	200	43	71	0	6.20
21	200	31	46	31	6.07
22	200	31	31	46	6.65
23	200	15	62	31	6.22
24	200	15	31	62	7.03

Figure 6.3: Taguchi experiment design analysis for the inputs.

Figure 6.4: E-SEM images of particleboard samples prepared using virgin wood particle and recycled wood particles.

Significantly increased amounts of N and O were observed in the recycled wood particleboard, which is due to the presence of urea-formaldehyde as observed by the composition analysis of EDX using E-SEM. Wood cell lumens were also observed on E-SEM images of virgin wood particleboard samples as shown in Fig. 6.4, but not in the particleboards made using recycled wood-based panel particles, which are comparatively higher density and have different mechanical properties.

6.4.3 X-ray diffraction analysis

The resin was subjected to X-ray diffraction analysis to evaluate its crystallinity and results were compared to that of alkali-treated WG and sodium alginate separately. The crystallinity indexes (CI) as shown in Eq. 3.18 were then compared by using the diffraction curves as shown in Fig. 6.6 taken from computer calculation from the original diffraction patterns shown in Fig. 6.5. The graphic analysis software OriginPro 2021b was used to get smooth curves. The intensity of the trough between secondary crystalline peaks is taken as the intensity of the amorphous fraction (I_{am}). The peak intensity corresponding to the crystalline fraction (I_{200}) is the intensity of the main crystalline peak [44]. The Table 6.2 represents the 2θ values of the peaks and their crystalline planes of XRD analysis of sodium alginate.

Table 6.2: The 2θ values of the peaks and their crystalline planes of XRD analysis of sodium alginate.

The reference	2θ of the peak	The crystalline plane
Abid et al., 2021 [45], Sundarrajan et al., 2012 [46]	30°	200
Abid et al., 2021 [45], Sundarrajan et al., 2012 [46]	13°	110

Figure 6.5: XRD patterns of alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate and their mixture.

Figure 6.6: XRD analysis of alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate and their mixture using smooth curves.

Table 6.3: Crystallinity indexes of samples calculated by using Eq. 3.18.

Sample	I_{200}	I_{am}	CI%
SA	632	165	74
WG+SA	467	225	52

The incorporation of alkali-treated WG into SA has increased the crystallinity index of the alkali-treated mixture (WG+SA) as shown in Table 6.3. The lower the crystallinity index implies higher in the amorphous fraction of the sample. When the amorphous fraction of the polymer is higher, it becomes less brittle [44].

6.4.4 FTIR analysis

FTIR analysis of cured and uncured resins of alkali-treated wheat gluten indicating of secondary interaction with sodium alginate are shown in Fig. 6.7 in full range and Fig. 6.8 in detail. Two major peaks can be observed in the uncured sample.

Figure 6.7: FTIR analysis of wheat gluten, alkali-treated WG and sodium alginate cured and uncured resins (full range).

Figure 6.8: FTIR analysis of wheat gluten, alkali-treated WG and sodium alginate cured and uncured resins.

Table 6.4: FTIR assignments for wheat gluten and uncured resin mixture.

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Remarks	Reference
1638	Stretching frequency of C=O of amide group	[47].
1530	Stretching C=N, C=C, C-N stretching and N-H bending	[48, 49, 50].
1440	C-O-H bending,	[51].
1235	Phosphate vibration, C-O stretch	[48, 52, 53].
1150	C=O, P=O, P-O-C (P-O-P) asymmetric stretching	[48, 54].
1075	Symmetric stretching of phosphodiesteres	[55].
1030	C-O-C stretching, S=O sulfoxide stretching	[56, 57].

Table 6.5: FTIR assignments for cured resin mixture.

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Remarks	Reference
1610	Aromatic C=C	[59].
1410	Stretching vibration of COO-, S=O stretching	[60, 58].
1310	Stretching of C-N bonds	[61, 62].
1140	C-O-C anti-symmetric stretching, S=O Sulfone	[63, 51].
1120	Strong (O-CH ₂) , Mannose-6-phosphate	[64, 65].
1080	Symmetric phosphate stretching (P=O stretching, and P-O-C (P-O-P) bonds)	[48, 54].
945	=NOH oxime N-O	[57].

As mentioned in Table 6.4, C-O-C stretching of sodium alginate and, S=O sulfoxide stretching of partially bonded sulfoxide which arise from indicating of secondary interaction of LMW/HMW with sodium alginate were observed at 1030 cm^{-1} of the uncured resin curve. Followed by the heat treatment, the intensity of the peak at 1030 cm^{-1} of the cured sample increased and the peak was also broadened as shown in Fig. 6.8 representing the possibility of formation of more C-O-C stretchings and S=O sulfoxide stretchings during the heat treatment indicating of secondary interaction of sodium alginate and sub-units of wheat gluten. Also, the peak at 1440 cm^{-1} which shows C-O-H bending of wheat gluten has shifted to 1410 cm^{-1} in the cured and the alkali-treated uncured WG and SA showing newly formed S=O sulfonyl groups. A significant increase in the intensity of the peak 1410 cm^{-1} can be seen after performing heat treatment which is likely to produce more sulfonyl groups [58]. This indicates secondary interactions between LMW/HMW of wheat gluten protein with sodium alginate. These interactions increase the thermoset adhesive properties of the binder. The hypothesis is that these secondary interactions are likely to contribute in increasing the thermoset adhesive properties of the binder.

The possibility of the formation of sulfoxide and sulfonyl bonds reveals that wheat gluten subunits are separated due to alkali treatment and make some sort of interaction with ionised sodium alginate. FTIR analysis had established that the curing had promoted additional peaks showing the possible reactivity after heat treatment and enabled functionalisation as expected.

The resin of alkali-treated WG and SA was used to make particleboard samples using virgin wood particle and recycled wood-based panel particles of the same size. Wood cell lumens were also seen on E-SEM images of virgin wood particleboard samples as shown in Fig. 6.4, but not in the samples made using recycled wood-based panel particles which have comparatively higher density and different mechanical properties.

The bend strengths and the internal bond values of virgin and recycled wood samples obtained are presented in Table 6.6. IB strength of both types of particleboard samples is much higher than the IB strength requirements of JIS A 5908:2015 due to their higher density. IB

Table 6.6: Mechanical properties of particleboard samples made with alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate. Detailed tables are Tables C.3 and C.4.

Type of wood particles	Density ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	IB strength (MPa)	Bending strength (MPa)	JIS A 5908:2015
Virgin	732.28±2.44	0.52±0.00	8.08±0.15	Type 8
Re-cycled	915.81±6.40	1.29±0.01	18.09±0.07	Type 18

strength is interrelated with material density.

Particleboard samples made by using virgin wood particles satisfy 'Type 8 Base particleboard Decorative particleboard' according to JIS A 5908:2015, while those made with re-cycled wood particles satisfy 'Type 18'. The particleboards made by using re-cycled wood particles have more than two times higher IB value due to the high density and the less porous nature. Wood cells of re-cycled wood particles were filled with synthetic adhesives already used. FTIR analysis shows the indication of secondary interaction of alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate whereas XRD shows higher bonding strength of the mixture of alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate having a lower crystallinity index compared to the individual components. Mechanical tests have revealed that the bio-based adhesives can satisfy industrial standards, according to JIS A 5908:2015. There is no requirement for thickness swelling for Type 8 particleboards, but for type 18, it should be less than 12%. The thickness swelling achieved in this study for both types of particleboard was 22%.

The use of bentonite as a hardener in the wood adhesive reduced the bending strength and increased thickness swelling. This corresponds to the brittle and swelling nature of bentonite clay. After having conducted Taguchi experiment design analysis, bentonite was taken off as a hardener although it penetrates through wood cell walls and makes mechanical interlocks.

6.5 Conclusion

The disulphide bonds between LMW and HMW proteins subunits can be broken by the addition of aqueous NaOH. In an aqueous medium, -ONa and -OH of sodium alginate can ionise to O^- , Na^+ and H^+ ions. Some of the ionised O^- of sodium alginate can make bonds by indicating of secondary interaction with unbonded disulphide of low and high molecular weight subunits of wheat gluten. The rest of ionised O^- can make bonds with hydroxyl groups of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin of wood cell walls. The proteinaceous nature of wheat gluten works as a bio-based wood adhesive. As can be seen from the comparative study, an improvement in both the mechanical and physical properties were obtained when the resin was used with recycled wood panel particles which contain urea-formaldehyde adhesives already used. This can reveal that proteinaceous wood adhesive can be used to re-manufacture wood-based panels as proteinaceous adhesives can be blended with synthetic wood adhesive. This can divert the wood-based panel industry from a linear

economy to a circular economy.

The research was carried out based on bend strength and internal bond strength as an initial step using an experimental design approach. A comprehensive thermal, rheological analysis such as TGA/DTG, DSC and DMA can be done to characterise the resin behaviour, but this was out of the scope of this paper. Physical properties such as water-resistance of the adhesive formulation can be improved in further future research.

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Chapter 7

Incorporating additives for the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate binder

“In the woods, we return to reason and faith.”

Ralph Waldo Emerson

Abstract

Non-formaldehyde-based, renewable, bio-based and environmentally friendly alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate wood binder mainly consists of proteins. Although the binder satisfies Japanese industrial standards, incorporation of appropriate non-formaldehyde yielding additives or additives can increase mechanical and/or physical properties of the binder. Most of the additives used in bio-based adhesives are synthetic chemicals rather than bio-based chemicals. In general, the incorporation of a small percentage of 1% - 2% of additives significantly increases the adhesive properties of bio-based wood binders. The additives sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and polyethylenimine used in this study showed an increase in mechanical and physical properties of the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate wood binder. Results also revealed that the additives can be used with all types of wood particles. Nevertheless, better mechanical and physical properties have been observed in samples made with recycled wood particles as compared to those made with virgin wood particles.

Keywords: sodium dodecyl sulphate, polyethylenimine, sodium phosphate, diacetin.

7.1 Introduction

Wheat gluten, the major constituent of the binder in this study contains a high content of proteins that have been used for making bio-based wood adhesives since early civilisation. The strength and durability of the adhesive bond, resistance to moisture [1] and cost-effectiveness are the main disadvantages of protein-based wood adhesives [2]. Chemical modification of proteinaceous adhesives with appropriate additives has the potential to eliminate the disadvantaged factors [3]. In this study, seven different types of additives were identified (sodium dodecyl sulphate, polyethylenimine, glyoxal, sodium phosphate, sodium sulphate, diacetin and tannin) by considering the proteinaceous nature of the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate wood binder.

Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) is a well-known additive used in protein-based wood adhesives such as soy-protein isolate to mainly improve water-resistance [1]. SDS is an ionic detergent that binds with protein molecules, masking their native charge and providing the protein molecules with the overall charge of the ionic detergent. This can increase the degree of protein unfolding by moving some interior hydrophobic side chains outward. So, they can interact with the hydrophobic moieties of detergent molecules and form micelle-like regions to increase hydrophobicity and, at the same time, to enhance the water-resistance of the protein-based wood adhesive [4]. SDS is also used as an additive to increase the bonding performance of protein-based wood adhesives [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. However, its incorporation in the adhesive also rises the viscosity of protein-based adhesives [10].

Polyethylenimine is used as an additive to enhance the mechanical properties of lignin and tannin [11], modified ammonium lignosulfonate [12], and procyanidin-type condensed tannin [13]. It has also been shown to increase the water-resistance of lignin and tannin [11], maleic anhydride soy protein isolate [14], and soybean flour [15]. In addition, to increase water-resistance, polyethylenimine demonstrated the ability to shorten the pressing time (by 1 *min*) [16].

Glyoxal is widely used as an additive in all types of wood adhesives due to its capacity of giving clear adhesive resins [17]. It is mainly used with tannin and lignin wood adhesives to enhance their mechanical properties due to the crosslinking reaction which forms a hard network [18]. It has been reported that incorporation of soybean protein with glyoxal was able to enhance the water-resistance of the resulting adhesive [19].

Sodium sulphate, sodium phosphate and diacetin were selected here as additives as, due to their molecular structure and the composition of the adhesive formulation, they are able to form bonds with the hydroxyls of wood cells.

Finally, tannin was employed in this study as a bio-based additive to evaluate the behaviour of the resulting resin.

7.2 Methodology

7.2.1 Materials

Wheat gluten was purchased from [Buy Whole Foods Online Ltd.](#) Sodium alginate and tannin were bought from [Sigma Aldrich](#). Sodium dodecyl sulphate, polyethylenimine, glyoxal, sodium sulphate, sodium phosphate diacetin and NaOH were bought from [Fisher Scientific](#). [Kastamonu Entegre](#) in Adana Turkey provided 1 mm virgin wood particles. Re-cycled wood particles of size 1 mm were provided by [French Inst. of Tech. for Forest-based and Furniture Sector](#).

7.2.2 Methods

First, particleboard samples were made with virgin wood particles as explained in Chapter 6 by adding 1% (w/w) of the additive to each sample. Then the same procedure was used to make samples with recycled wood particles. Variable parameters such as adhesive content, curing temperature, and pressure used in the particleboard manufacturing industry were kept constant throughout the samples making procedure. Dried samples were then cut to size and tested for physical and mechanical properties.

7.3 Results and Discussion

Laboratory-scale particleboard samples were made in this study by using virgin and recycled wood particles of the same size in order to compare changes in mechanical and physical properties of the samples with the incorporation of additives. Two reference samples were used to compare the increments (↑) and decrements (↓) in the mechanical properties such as bending strength (modulus of rupture - MOR), modulus of elasticity - MOE, density and internal bond - IB and also physical properties such as moisture content - MC and thickness swelling TS. The increments and decrements of the properties due to the incorporation of additives with the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate binder with virgin and recycled wood particles are shown in Table 10.5 and Table 10.6 respectively. The colour codes are used to compare the increments and decrements within the same property. Increments of mechanical properties and decrements of physical properties indicate the best additives and these are shown in green. The colour code red shows decrements of mechanical properties and increments of physical properties demonstrating a poor performance of the binder. The intensities of the colours shown in the tables implies the effectiveness of incorporating the additive on the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate wood adhesive.

Table 7.2: Effect of additives on physical and mechanical properties of particleboards made by using recycled wood particles and the bioadhesive formulation. Increments and decrements are compared to the control sample which contains no additives. Detailed tables are Tables C.7 and C.8.

Additive added (1% by mass)	MOR (MPa)	MOE (MPa)	Density ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	IB (MPa)	MC (%)	TS (%)
Control	18.09±0.07	3209.98±31.45	915.81±6.40	1.29±0.01	11.72±0.26	9.07±0.60
SDS	↑by 4.65	↑by 767	↑by 11	↑by 0.22	↓by 2	↓by 4
Sodium sulfate	↓by 1.43	↓by 108	↑by 21	↑by 0.02	↑by 1	↑by 0
Polyethylenimine	↑by 8.52	↑by 918	↑by 10	↑by 0.84	↓by 1	↓by 2
Glyoxal	↑by 5.01	↑by 411	↑by 21	↑by 0.21	↑by 0	↑by 1
Sodium phosphate	↑by 2.77	↑by 321	↑by 31	↑by 0.07	↑by 1	↓by 0
Diacetin	↑by 3.43	↑by 299	↑by 12	↑by 0.32	↑by 1	↓by 1
Tannin	↑by 1.12	↓by 98	↑by 10	↓by 0.21	↑by 1	↑by 1

Excellent	Very good	Good	Poor	Very poor	Very very poor
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Figure 7.1: The proposed hypothesis for interaction between amino acids of WG protein and the linkage of SDS.

Figure 7.2: The possible reaction between polyethylenimine and carboxylic groups of amino acids in wheat gluten protein forming a peptide bond (PEI - polyethylenimine, WGP - wheat gluten protein).

SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate) is one of the most used additives with proteins and starch-based adhesives to enhance water-resistance and mechanical properties. Chen et al, 2019 [20] found that 2% of SDS can significantly increase the properties of the starch-based adhesive formulation.

The proposed hypothesis interaction synthesis of SDS with the amino acids of the backbone of all the types of gliadins, LMW and HMW glutenins subunits of wheat gluten protein (the interaction between amino acids of WG protein and hydrophobic linkage of SDS) has been shown to give additional strength to the adhesive formulation enhancing its mechanical properties [21] as shown in Fig. 7.1. As a result of the interaction of amino acids of WG proteins with hydrophobic linkages of SDS, the water-resistance of the binder increases. The possible interaction can also increase the thermoset adhesive properties of the binder.

Sodium sulphate was chosen as an additive because of its -ONa component capable to make bonds with wheat gluten and the wood cells. However, when used in this work, it showed to decrease in mechanical and physical properties of the resulting samples. This can be due to the inability of -ONa to reach the backbone of glutenin subunits.

Blending the resin formulation with polyethylenimine (PEI) exhibited the highest increase in mechanical and physical properties (Tables 10.5 and 10.6). Amine (-NH₂) groups of polyethylenimine can react with carboxyl functional group (-COOH) of amino acids of wheat gluten protein (WGP) polymer to cross-link each other forming a peptide bond. The chemical reaction is shown in Fig. 7.2. and the chemical structure of a branch of polyethylenimine, depicted in Fig. 7.3, consists of many amine groups, which can crosslink several carboxyl groups of amino acids of wheat gluten by forming peptide bonds during the hot press procedure. This mechanism of crosslinking of protein of wheat gluten makes strong and durable bonds between hydroxyl groups of wood cell walls. Strong durable bonds enhance mechanical properties and density. This also leads to an increase in physical

Figure 7.3: Branched structure of polyethylenimine [22].

Figure 7.4: The possible reaction between glyoxal with an amino group of amino acids of wheat gluten protein (WGP).

properties such as water-resistance.

Glyoxal the smallest dialdehyde is vastly used to increase the mechanical properties of bio-based wood adhesives. Glyoxal does not emit toxic formaldehyde and is used as an alternative to formaldehyde [23]. It has also been used to enhance the water-resistance of soy protein wood adhesive [19]. In this study, when tried with both virgin and recycled wood particles, glyoxal was showed to increase the mechanical properties of the resulting boards (Tables 10.5 and 10.6). However, glyoxal seemed to reduce the physical properties by increasing the value of thickness swelling for both types of wood particles. Dialdehydes same as aldehyde that can have the ability to react with amino groups of amino acids of wheat gluten protein and makes more hydroxyl groups that can react with the hydroxyl groups of wood cell walls as shown in Fig. 7.4. This gives more strength to the protein type adhesive formulations. Hydroxyls and -ONa groups of sodium phosphate, when this was used as an additive, have can help to increase the properties of the adhesive slightly, and have been shown to produce samples with better properties than sodium sulphate (Tables 10.5 and 10.6). The chemical structures of both have similarities. The crosslinking reactions between wood hydroxyls and the functional groups of protein molecules can rarely take place due to the small link between sodium phosphate and sodium sulphate.

Diacetin, as a diester, can react with amine groups of wheat gluten protein resulting in alkanes with hydroxyl groups. The resultants then can react either with the hydroxyls of wood cell walls directly by bonding two wood particles together or with the carboxylic end of the wheat gluten protein, crosslinking the WGP, as shown in Fig. 7.5. Nevertheless, diacetin blocks the amino group. Therefore, in this work, it did not seem to produce a significant increase in the performance of the adhesive formulation comparatively to SDS and polyethylenimine (Tables 10.5 and 10.6). Tannin is a well-known bio-adhesive and it has been used as an additive in the study. A significant effect could not be observed by its use for both virgin and recycle

Figure 7.5: The possible reaction of diacetin with amino groups of wheat gluten protein (WGP) and the resultant with carboxylic groups of WGP.

particles.

Generally, when the same additives were used either with virgin particles or recycled wood particles, taken from particleboards made from synthetic adhesives, a similar trend in properties was observed (Tables 10.5 and 10.6), demonstrating that the additives had the same effect on samples made with either type of wood particles.

7.4 Conclusion

The results have validated that additives that can be used with the bio-based adhesive formulation behave in the same way regardless of the type of wood particles utilised. Nevertheless, when additives are incorporated into the bio-based adhesive, the changes in physical and mechanical properties are more enhanced in samples made by using recycled wood particles. Polyethylenimine, SDS, diacetin and sodium phosphate as additives showed positive results increasing physical and mechanical properties, while tannin and sodium sulphate showed decreasing them. Glyoxal increased only the mechanical properties of the binder. In conclusion, the addition of only 1% of some of the additives studied here showed an enhancement of mechanical and physical properties. Therefore, it is likely that increasing further the quantity of the additives into the bio-based wood adhesive can help in the future to achieve the desired mechanical and physical properties of wood-based panels.

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Chapter 8

Exploration of Re-manufacturability of Particleboard by using Bio-based Adhesives

“The whole wood seemed running now, running hard, hunting, chasing, closing in round something or somebody? In a panic, he began to run too, aimlessly, he knew not whither.”

Kenneth Grahame

Abstract

Wood-based panels mainly including particleboards are made by using virgin wood particles taken from low-grade and twisted logs of wood and formaldehyde-based wood adhesives. As wood-based panels can be used as substitutes for solid wood in the furniture industry, it gives economic and ecological benefits by reducing the number of trees that need cutting for furniture needs. On the other hand, synthetic adhesives such as urea-formaldehyde, phenol-formaldehyde or melamine-formaldehyde used in wood-based panels emit formaldehyde, which is toxic for the manufacturer as well as the final users. In addition, the re-manufacturing of recycled particleboards using crushed materials and synthetic formaldehyde-based adhesives is very limited, as this produces an extremely high emission of formaldehyde. In this study, a bio-based wood adhesive was investigated for the re-manufacturing of particleboards by using both virgin and recycled wood particles for several cycles. The mechanical and physical properties were tested against Japanese industrial standard, JIS A 5908:2015. The result showed that the first cycle of re-manufacturing of particleboards using the bio-adhesive formulation achieved industrial standards revealing opportunities for a circular economy in the wood-based panel industry. Further cycles of re-manufacturing reduce the mechanical properties of the wood-based panels.

Keywords: Bio-based adhesives, re-manufacturability, recyclability, particleboard, wood-based panels.

8.1 Introduction

Wood wastes such as shavings, sawdust, low-grade logs, twisted and bowed logs constitute from 7% up to 40% - 50% in the furniture manufacturing industry. They can be counted as virgin wood wastes [1]. Demolished furniture and wood-based panels comprise more than 10% of the total recycled wood waste, which contains formaldehyde adhesives used in it. These have been re-used as biofuel for energy generation [2] or dumped as landfills damaging the environment [3]. Therefore, an economical, efficient and environmentally-friendly recycling process is needed to achieve the increasing demands of the wood-based panel industry [4]. Wood-polymer composites can be made by using recycled wood wastes [5]. Re-manufacturing wood-based panels from recycled wood particles that contain synthetic adhesive is limited due to the high content of toxic formaldehyde in the final product. However, usage of bio-based wood adhesives can act as formaldehyde scavengers by reducing formaldehyde emission of the resulting wood-based panels [6].

In the wood processing and furniture industry, the waste, as shown in Fig. 8.1, ends up in landfills, when only the black arrows are considered. This is the 'linear economy', which should be converted to a 'circular economy' [7] with the green arrow, by using the non-formaldehyde-based adhesive formulation, as the waste contains already formaldehyde. A circular economy in the wood processing industry would answer the shortages in wood supply and would save more trees on the planet [8].

Bio-based wood adhesives were used to bond veneers to wood furniture by early Egyptians. Synthetic adhesives have taken over, as they are more effective and cheaper [9]. However today, it has been found that formaldehyde emission causes nasopharyngeal cancer in human beings [10, 11, 12]. The main formaldehyde sources are: i) the formaldehyde compounds contained in the wood material; ii) The formaldehyde deriving from the resins used to prepare the wood-based panels; and iii) the formaldehyde released during structural degradation of wood-based panels [13]. When using recycled wood particles there is a need to use a higher amount of synthetic adhesives to obtain an optimal bonding strength in the

Figure 8.1: Potential circular economy diagram for the wood-based panel industry.

resulting particleboards [14]. Therefore, the formaldehyde emission is increased when recycled wood particles are used [15].

In this study, particleboards made using bio-based adhesives were crushed and re-manufactured with bio-based adhesive repeatedly to validate the re-manufacturability of particleboard by using the bio-based wood adhesive formulation described in Chapter 6. Crushed wood particles from particleboards made using synthetic adhesives were also incorporated in the same process to validate the re-manufacturing process by using the same adhesive formulation.

8.2 Methodology

8.2.1 Materials

Wheat gluten was purchased from [Buy Whole Foods Online Ltd.](#) Sodium alginate was bought from [Sigma Aldrich](#). Bentonite and NaOH were bought from [Fisher Scientific](#). [Kastamonu Entegre](#) in Adana Turkey provided 1 mm virgin wood particles. Re-cycled wood particles of size 1 mm were provided by [French Inst. of Tech. for Forest-based and Furniture Sector](#).

8.2.2 Methods

An already optimised and studied bio-based wood adhesive formulation of alkali-treated wheat gluten with sodium alginate (Chapter 6) was used as the adhesive formulation to re-manufacture laboratory-scale particleboards. Virgin wood particles (1 mm) and re-cycled wood particles (1 mm) were oven-dried at 130°C for two hours to reduce the moisture content below 5%. Wood particles and the dry adhesive mixture were mixed in a closed container and then 0.2M NaOH was sprayed until the moisture content reached 20%. Dry adhesive content, moisture content and the wood particle content (w/w/w %) were kept constant in each experimental trial. The mixture was then placed in an aluminium mould and a silicone mould releasing agent was applied. The sample was then pre-pressed at room temperature. The samples were then subjected to a hot-press treatment for 10 min and allowed to cool down. Samples were then cut to size as depicted in Fig. 5.4 for mechanical and physical tests according to Japanese industrial standards (JIS A 5908:2015). Environmental scanning electron microscope (E-SEM) analysis was used to evaluate the adhesive properties and element analysis.

In order to study the re-manufacturability, particleboard samples made by using virgin wood particles and bio-adhesives were crushed by hammering and sieved to 1 mm and were labelled as “B”. The crushed particle of particleboards made by using virgin wood and synthetic adhesive provided by ‘French Inst. of Tech. for Forest-based and Furniture Sector’ were labelled as “S”. The sample made by using a mixture of 50% by weight from both types of wood particles was labelled as $B_{50} + S_{50}$. $(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}$ denotes the samples made by using crushed particles of $B_{50} + S_{50}$ with bio-based adhesives.

In the first cycle, “ B_{100} ” denotes that particleboards made by using 100% of crushed and sieved to the size of “B”. The second cycle of re-manufacturing, “ $(B_{100})_{100}$ ” denotes the

particleboard made by using 100% of crushed and sieved to the size of “ B_{100} ”. Consequently in the third cycle, “[$(B_{100})_{100}$] $_{100}$ ” denotes particleboard made by using 100% of crushed and sieved to size of “ $(B_{100})_{100}$ ”.

8.3 Results and Discussion

The bending strength, density, internal bond and thickness swelling reading of 0th (“ B ” - the particleboard made by using virgin wood particles and bio-based adhesives) to 3rd cycles of re-manufacturing of the fully bio-based system were compared with industrial standards to illustrate the possibilities of re-manufacturability.

8.3.1 Bending strength

The bending strength of the first cycle of both systems as shown in Table 8.1 satisfied JIS industrial standards. However, in the second and third cycle, this was not achieved. Samples become more brittle due to the high adhesive content when the cycle number increased. Therefore, a higher adhesive content seems to reduce the bending strength (Table 8.1).

As Chapter 6 illustrates, the bending strength of the particleboard sample made with 100% recycled wood particles was 18.09 MPa. It showed a higher value than the particleboard sample made with 100% virgin wood particles which showed the bending strength of 8.08 MPa. In general, the bending strengths of each cycle of Table 8.1b are higher than that of Table 8.1a. This is due to the synthetic adhesive content in the bio-based and synthetic system. An increased amount of nitrogen in the samples of the mixed system was discovered by elemental analysis performed by E-SEM as shown in Table 8.2. Nitrogen is deriving from the melamine and the urea contained in the formaldehyde-based adhesives as shown in Fig. B.3 and B.4 and used to manufacturing the synthetic wood particles.

Table 8.1: Bending strengths of particleboard samples of each cycle. Detailed tables are Table C.9 and Table C.10.

(a) Fully bio-based system.			(b) Bio-based and synthetic system.		
Cycle	Bending strength (MPa)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?	Cycle	Bending strength (MPa)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?
B	8.08±0.15	✓			
B_{100}	9.05±0.33	✓	$B_{50} + S_{50}$	11.4±0.46	✓
$(B_{100})_{100}$	6.59±0.12	✗	$(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}$	7.16±0.01	✗
$[(B_{100})_{100}]_{100}$	3.80±0.19	✗	$[(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}]_{100}$	4.62±0.12	✗

Table 8.2: Elemental analysis of samples made with virgin wood particles and recycled wood particles.

Samples made with	Element percentages														
	C	N	O	Na	Mg	Al	Si	P	S	K	Ca	Ti	Fe	Cl	Total
virgin wood particles 1	54.20	8.45	34.12	2.31				0.09	0.34	0.08	0.42				100
virgin wood particles 2	56.26	5.10	37.31	0.51			0.11		0.18	0.12	0.41				100
virgin wood particles 3	38.20		33.70	0.31	2.36	1.43	4.07	0.59	0.17	0.16	9.56	0.50	8.96		100
recycled wood particles 1	44.33	13.81	39.84	1.30					0.41		0.30				100
recycled wood particles 2	45.28	12.99	40.85	0.55					0.12		0.13			0.07	100
recycled wood particles 3	46.77	14.32	38.36	0.25					0.14		0.17				100

Table 8.3: Densities of particleboard samples of each cycle. Detailed tables are Table C.9 and Table C.10.

(a) Fully bio-based system.			(b) Bio-based and synthetic system.		
Cycle	Density ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?	Cycle	Density ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?
B	732 ± 2.44	✓			
B_{100}	793 ± 1.76	✓	$B_{50} + S_{50}$	846 ± 6.27	✓
$(B_{100})_{100}$	876 ± 9.25	✓	$(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}$	884 ± 7.34	✓
$[(B_{100})_{100}]_{100}$	913 ± 8.98	✗	$[(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}]_{100}$	926 ± 3.24	✗

8.3.2 Density

The density of each sample increased as the cycle number increased as shown in Table 8.3. E-SEM images as in Fig. 8.2 show that the porous nature of sample B is higher than the samples B_{100} . The sample in Fig. 8.2c contains more adhesives than the others. Also, the adhesive content of samples in Fig. 8.3 increased with the cycle number. As a result of these facts, the densities of the samples of both systems increase when the cycle number increased.

8.3.3 Internal Bond strength

Internal bond strengths (IB) of each sample of both systems are reported in Tables 8.4a and 8.4b. IB increased when the cycle number increases. This is due to the density related to internal bond strength. The higher the density, the more closely packed the bond are. Therefore, a higher amount of adhesive content has increased the internal bond strength as the cycle number also increases. In general, the IB values are higher in the samples made with recycled wood particles compared to virgin wood particles.

8.3.4 Thickness swelling (TS)

Tables 8.5a and 8.5b illustrate the thickness swelling values of both systems with the cycle number. As the samples become less porous with each cycle, they adsorb a smaller amount of water which therefore reduces the thickness swelling value. A significant difference for TS between the two systems can't be seen in Tables 8.5a and 8.5b.

8.4 Conclusion and future works

Re-manufacturability of particleboard by using bio-based adhesive formulation was tested with virgin wood particles and wood particles derived from crushed particleboards made using

Figure 8.2: E-SEM analysis of fully bio-based system.

Table 8.4: Internal bond strengths of particleboard samples of each cycle. Detailed tables are Table C.9 and Table C.10.

(a) Fully bio-based system.			(b) Bio-based and synthetic system.		
Cycle	IB strength (MPa)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?	Cycle	IB strength (MPa)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?
B	0.52 ± 0.00	✓			
B_{100}	0.62 ± 0.01	✓	$B_{50} + S_{50}$	0.98 ± 0.01	✓
$(B_{100})_{100}$	0.74 ± 0.01	✓	$(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}$	1.13 ± 0.01	✓
$[(B_{100})_{100}]_{100}$	0.91 ± 0.00	✓	$[(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}]_{100}$	1.16 ± 0.01	✓

(a) E-SEM images of samples of particleboard made using $B_{50} + S_{50}$.

(b) E-SEM images of samples of particleboard made using $(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}$.

(c) E-SEM images of samples of particleboard made using $[(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}]_{100}$.

Figure 8.3: E-SEM analysis of partially bio-based system.

Table 8.5: Thickness swelling of particleboard samples of each cycle. Detailed tables are Table C.9 and Table C.10.

(a) Fully bio-based system.			(b) Bio-based and synthetic system.		
Cycle	TS (%)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?	Cycle	TS (%)	JIS Type 8 satisfied?
B	12 ± 0.49	✓	$B_{50} + S_{50}$	10 ± 0.57	✓
B_{100}	12 ± 0.12	✓	$(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}$	9 ± 0.34	✓
$(B_{100})_{100}$	10 ± 0.76	✓	$[(B_{50} + S_{50})_{100}]_{100}$	8 ± 0.61	✓
$[(B_{100})_{100}]_{100}$	9 ± 0.06	✓			

synthetic wood adhesives. Increasing the number of recycling cycles decrease thickness swelling, bending strength and increased the density and internal bond strength. Samples became more fragile and less ductile when the number of recycling cycles increased due to the high content of adhesives in the samples. Nevertheless, the sample B_{100} and the sample $B_{50} + S_{50}$ satisfied the industrial standards by considering mechanical and physical properties. This can reveal that re-manufacturing of particleboards by using virgin wood or recycled wood can be done without using formaldehyde-based synthetic wood adhesives for one cycle. This process is not going to increase the formaldehyde emission when a bio-based adhesive formulation is used. This can turn the linear economy of the wood-based panel industry into a circular economy.

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Chapter 9

Tannins Extracted from Olive Seed Flour as Bioadhesives for Manufacturing Wood-based Panels

“Wood burns because it has the proper stuff in it; and a man becomes famous because he has the proper stuff in him.”

Johann Wolfgang von Goethe

Abstract

The olive seed is a by-product in the olive oil production industry. Biuret test and ferric chloride test revealed that water or alkali NaOH extractions of olive seed flour is rich in proteins and tannins. Both proteins and tannins are well-known bio-based wood adhesives in the wood-based panel industry. In general, tannins-based wood adhesives show better mechanical and physical properties of particleboards than that of proteins-based wood adhesives. This paper explores different methods of extracting tannins from olive seed flour against the tannins yield and explore their applications as bio-based adhesives in wood-based panels. Once investigated, the physical and the mechanical properties of wood-based panels made using bio-adhesives based tannins extracted from olive seed flour revealed that the resulting products satisfy the Japanese industrial standards JIS A 5908:2015.

Keywords: Bioadhesives, Olive seed flour, Tannins, Wood-based panels.

9.1 Introduction

Olive mill waste *alperujo* contributes to significant environmental issues in Mediterranean areas where 97% of total olive production in the world takes place [1]. The olives industry

Figure 9.1: Cross section of olive fruit [15].

produces more than 30 million cubic metres of *Alperujo* which is highly toxic due to the high concentration of aromatic compounds [2]. The toxicity of the effluent coming from the olive oil industry is attributed to the high content of phenolic components (from 1.5 g l^{-1} to 8 g l^{-1}). [3]. *Alperujo* is a powerful source of phenolic compounds compared with olive oil [4]. Natural highly polymerised phenolic compounds such as tannins are available in olive mill wastes [5]. The olive seed can be removed from olive stone by crushing. Olive stone flour is used as fillers to give smooth-flowing powder mixture [6]. A cross-section of olive is shown in Fig. 9.1. Tyrosol and hydroxytyrosol can be found in olive stones, and verbascoside and nuzhenide can be found in olive seeds. Both seeds and stones contain oleuropein [7, 8]. Some mills remove the stone from the olive pulp. Currently, the stone is used as an energy source as it contains high calorific power [9] and activated carbon [10]. Olive stones contain a high amount of lignocellulosic materials such as lignin. The phenolic compounds contained in the olive stones can be extracted [7]. In addition, sugars were identified by enzymatic hydrolysis in the olive stone's fibrous part [11]. High-added value compounds such as proteins, fats, phenols, free sugars, phenolics, hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin are contained in the olive stone [11]. Furfural, which is used as a lignin-crosslinking agent [12] in wood glue, can be produced by using acid hydrolysis of olive stones [13]. Olive stone flour has been used as a cheaper reinforcing filler in a polypropylene matrix [14].

It has been reported, that a phenol-formaldehyde wood adhesive can be developed by using olive stones [16]. The olive kernel could replace 15% of base resin in a phenol-formaldehyde wood adhesive exhibiting better adhesive properties compared to the commercial phenol-formaldehyde wood adhesives [1]. Thermogravimetric analysis has indicated that there is no thermal degradation of the olive stones up to 195°C . It has also been shown that the resistance to fungi of wood particleboard made by adding olive stone powder was increased [17]. Tannin is a well-known bio-based adhesive used in the wood panel industry. It has been found that liquid effluent of *alperujo* consists of tannins in addition to polyphenols, polyalcohols, pectins, and lipids [18]. It is a renewable resource obtained as a

by-product of the agriculture industry [19]. In another study, HCl has been used to extract tannins as the soluble components from olive seed [20].

The adhesion properties of olive stone fibre reinforced polystyrene can be enhanced by treating the fibres with 4% of NaOH solution before production of the composite. The alkaline treatment remarkably improved the tensile strength and reduced hydrophilic nature of olive seed fibre [21].

Tannin, so-called tannic acid, is a well-known bio-based wood adhesive that can be used even in exterior grade applications due to its high water-resistance property [22, 23, 24, 25, 26]. Tannins from different types of biomasses can be extracted by using different extraction methods such as extraction with organic solvents, hot water, ionic liquids, supercritical fluids, pressurised hot water or subcritical water, by microwave and by ultrasound [27]. Seed extractions showed component of tannin (gallic and ellagic acid derivatives) available in it [28, 29].

In this study, tannin was extracted from olive seed flour by using a refluxing method. It was then used as a bio-based wood adhesive to make particleboards by using virgin wood particle and recycled wood particles, and their mechanical and physical properties were investigated.

9.2 Methodology

Firstly, the availability of tannins in olive seed flour was qualitatively tested and this was then followed by a quantitative test. Extracted tannins were then mixed with wood particles to make particleboard samples. They were then subjected to mechanical and physical tests and the values compared to industrial standards.

9.2.1 Materials

Olive seed flour from netuxa.com and FeCl_3 , Whatman No 1 Filter papers, Kaolin, Gelatine solution, Indigo Carmine were purchased from Fisher Scientific UK Ltd. Kastamonu Entegre in Adana Turkey provided 1 mm virgin wood particles. Re-cycled wood particles of size 1 mm were provided by French Inst. of Tech. for Forest-based and Furniture Sector.

9.2.2 Methods

In order to extract tannins from olive seed flour, the flour was added either to distilled water or 0.1M NaOH in a ratio of 1:25 (w/w). The tannins extraction was then performed by using a reflux method with a magnetic stirrer at 90 °C for 2 hours as shown in Fig. 9.2a. The reflux was done by adding 500 g of water or 0.1M NaOH with 20 g of olive seed flour. The suspension that could take out for filtration was 200g. It was then cooled and filtered through a Whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrate was then tested with 2-3 drops of 5% (w/v) aqueous solution of ferric chloride for the formation of greenish precipitate indicating the presence of tannins in the

(a) Refluxing of olive seed flour.

(b) Qualitative test for the existence of tannin of the extract. The green precipitate when ferric chloride is added to the extract is in right.

Figure 9.2: Extraction and qualitative test of olive seed flour.

(a) Indigo-carmin and the extract mixture.

(b) End point of the titration against KMnO_4 .

Figure 9.3: Qualitative analysis for available tannin.

sample as shown in Fig. 9.2b. The quantitative analysis of tannin was performed by the Official Methods of Association of Analytical Chemists [30]. First, 5 ml of an aliquot of the extract was mixed with 12.5 ml of indigo-carmin solution with 375 ml of distilled water. Then the mixture was titrated against standardised 0.1N KMnO_4 solution (3.16 g of KMnO_4 in 1 l of purified water) of 'Y' ml until the blue colour of the indigo-carmin becomes final yellow at the endpoint as in Figures 9.3a and 9.3b. The 'Y' amount of KMnO_4 was used to calculate the concentration of total tannins and the concentration of other related compounds (non-tannins) in the same extract were estimated as explained below.

To determine the concentration of non-tannins in the extract, another 50 ml of an aliquot of the extract was mixed with 25 ml of gelatin solution, 50 ml of acidic NaCl solution (25 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 added to 975 ml of saturated NaCl solution) and 5 g of powdered kaolin. The mixture was then shaken for 15 min and filtered through Watman No. 1 filter paper. Then 12.5 ml of the filtrate was mixed with 12.5 ml of the indigo-carmin solution and 375 ml of distilled water. The mixture was then titrated KMnO_4 solution of 'X' ml until the final yellow endpoint.

The volume of KMnO_4 used to titrate the exact amount of tannin in 1 ml of the extract

can be taken from the difference of $\frac{Y}{5}$ and $\frac{X}{12.5}$ [31]. The equations 9.1 and 9.2 were used to estimate the tannin concentration of olive seed flour extract.

$$1 \text{ ml of standard KMnO}_4 \text{ solution} = 0.595 \text{ ml of } 0.1N \text{ Oxalic acid} \quad (9.1)$$

$$1 \text{ ml of } 0.1N \text{ Oxalic acid} = 0.0042 \text{ g of tannin} \quad (9.2)$$

The ratio between oven-dried wood particles and the dry adhesives used was 20:7 (wt.) respectively. Therefore it is needed to have 70 g of dry adhesive powder to mix with 200 g of oven-dried wood particles as already mentioned in Chapter 5. In order to achieve a yield of 70 g of dry tannins, 933 g of olive seed flour was used for the extraction with NaOH. The filtrate of the extraction was then heated until its mass was reduced to 120 g, consisting of 70 g of tannin and 50 g of water, which was necessary to increase the moisture content of the final wood particle and adhesive mixture up to 20%. Afterwards, the thick extract was mixed with the oven-dried virgin wood particles to make the first particleboard sample. The mixture was then hot pressed to make a particleboard sample. The cured particleboard was cut to size as in Fig. 5.4 for physical and mechanical tests overall values compared against JIS A 5908:2015. Then the same procedure was done for recycled wood particles.

9.3 Results and Discussion

Tannins extraction from olive seed flour was done using distilled water as well as with 0.1M NaOH to compare the tannin yield. The yield of the extraction of tannins performed using NaOH was better than that carried out with distilled water extraction as shown in Table 9.1.

The mechanical and physical properties of particleboard samples made with virgin and recycled wood particles were reported in Table 9.2. In general, usage of recycled wood particles exhibited better results for mechanical and physical properties of the particleboard satisfying industrial standards. This is due to the already present synthetic adhesive content in the recycled wood particles. The density of particleboard samples made by using recycled wood particles is higher in value than the samples made of virgin wood particles. This is due to the less porous nature of recycled wood particles. Less porous nature also reduced the moisture content and thickness swelling of recycled wood particles. An increase in the elastic modulus of recycled wood particleboards indicates a more brittle material than virgin wood made particleboards. Previously used synthetic adhesive content in recycled wood particles is also the causes for the increase in internal bond strength.

9.4 Conclusion and future works

Tannins are a well-known bio-based wood adhesive used at the industrial level. In most cases, they are blended with some other synthetic adhesives to enhance their properties. Tannins

Table 9.1: Comparison calculation of tannin yields from distilled water and 0.1M NaOH extraction methods.

Solvent	Distilled water	NaOH
Y (ml)	12.5	18.5
X (ml)	7.5	9.0
KMnO ₄ used for tannin + other compounds in 1 ml of the extract (ml)	2.5	3.7
KMnO ₄ used for other compounds in 1 ml of the extract (ml)	0.6	0.72
KMnO ₄ used for tannin in 1 ml of the extract (ml)	1.9	2.98
Tannin in 1 ml of the extract (g) ^a	0.00475	0.007447
Tannin in 1 g of olive seed flour (g) ^b	0.04748	0.074470
The percentage of tannin available in olive seed flour (%)	4.8	7.5

$$^a \left(\frac{Y}{5} - \frac{X}{12.5} \right) \times 0.0042 \times 0.595$$

^b 20 g of olive seed flour gives the suspension of 200 ml at the end of the reflux.

Table 9.2: Mechanical and physical properties of particleboard samples made by using 65% of virgin wood particles and 35% of tannins and other compounds extracted from olive seed flour by using 0.1M NaOH extraction. Detailed table is Table C.11.

Property	Virgin wood particles	JIS Type 8 satisfied?	Recycled wood particles	JIS Type 8 satisfied?
Bending strength (MPa)	7.8±0.10	✗	10.9±0.06	✓
Elastic modulus (MPa)	1854±57.15	✗	2152±63.25	✓
Density (kg m ⁻³)	698±10.23	✓	802±5.43	✓
Internal bond strength (MPa)	0.17±0.00	✓	0.22±0.00	✓
Moisture content (%)	15±1.06	✗	11±0.14	✓
Thickness swelling (%)	15±0.35	✓	12±0.43	✓

can be blended with formaldehyde-based adhesives, as well as with non-formaldehyde-based adhesives such as pMDI. The results in this study have shown that tannins extracted from olive seed flour can be used without blending with synthetic adhesives to make particleboards with recycled wood particles, which satisfied the industrial standards. However, it seems necessary to blend tannins with synthetic additives or adhesives to manufacture boards with virgin wood particles to achieve industrial standards

The olive seed tannins resin content used in this study was 35% as shown in Table C.11. An increase in the resin content could enhance the mechanical and physical properties of the samples to achieve JIS standards for virgin wood particles.

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Chapter 10

Summary of the Results

“A bad historian is even more dangerous than dead documentary wood”

Norman Davies

10.1 Introduction

Possible additives for adhesive formulations can be found with the support of literature. In this work, the crosslinking mechanism has been mostly used to enrich the thermostatic properties of the adhesive formulations rather than thermoelastic properties. Samples of particleboards were made using two or more combinations of adhesive compounds by varying their dry content to achieve the best mechanical and physical properties.

10.2 Sodium alginate and bentonite system - System 1

Sodium alginate (SA) extracted from brown algae was identified as the main wood binder due to its phenolic type chemical structure, carboxylic type -ONa segment and polysaccharide nature as shown in Fig. 6.1. SA can make a bond with the hydroxyl groups of the secondary layer of wood cell walls. The polysaccharide nature, which gives withstanding power to seaweeds against sea currents, can hold one wood cell wall to another.

Bentonite is a nanoclay that can penetrate wood cells and make mechanical interlocks during the curing process when it is used as a wood adhesive. Bentonite is a well-known highly viscous binder used in industries due to its high thermal stability. The chemical structure of bentonite is shown in Fig. 10.1.

The statistical analysis Taguchi design of experiment performed in this work by varying dry content of oven-dried virgin wood particles, sodium alginate, and bentonite revealed that 60% to 70% of wood particles (w/w) in the input mixture showed better mechanical and

Table 10.1: Sodium alginate and bentonite system 'System 1'. The detailed table is Table C.1

Particleboard number	11	12	13	14
Virgin wood particles (wt.)	70%	65%	65%	60%
Sodium alginate (wt.)	20%	20%	25%	25%
Bentonite (wt.)	10%	15%	10%	15%
Average MOR (MPa)	4.80 ± 0.11	5.20 ± 0.13	5.88 ± 0.09	6.20 ± 0.07
Average MOE (MPa)	864.76 ± 54.90	1254.45 ± 16.89	1024.13 ± 8.03	1522.36 ± 45.28
Average density (kg/m ³)	702.92 ± 1.27	745.87 ± 2.71	719.32 ± 0.93	756.41 ± 5.32
Average IB (MPa)	0.12 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.00	0.12 ± 0.00	0.14 ± 0.00
Average MC (%)	14.26% ± 1.02%	15.50% ± 0.18%	18.61% ± 0.54%	22.98% ± 0.38%
Average TS (%)	21.33% ± 0.49%	27.08% ± 0.49%	22.92% ± 0.18%	29.47% ± 0.17%

physical properties of the resulting products. In this study, four particleboards were made by varying input parameters and the test results are shown in Table 10.1. All the other manufacturing parameters such as press factor, press temperature, and the applied pressure were kept unchanged.

An increment of the bending strength (MOR) of the particleboards were seen in the results of Taguchi experimental design analysis when the sodium alginate and bentonite adhesive content was increased, though none of them satisfied the industrial standards as shown in Table 10.1. Meanwhile, an increase in bentonite showed to increase the bending Young's modulus (MOE) demonstrating a more brittle nature of the resulting particleboards. An increase in bentonite in the formulation also showed an increase in density due to its penetration into wood cells. This has affected the internal bond (IB) value which increased when increasing bentonite content in the adhesive formulation. The major disadvantage of bentonite is the increase in moisture content and thickness swelling due to its water absorbent nature. The cations in the bentonite clay, as shown in Fig. 10.1, can retain water by using ion hydration. This increases the amount of water in the final cured and dried particleboard samples increasing their moisture content. During the thickness swelling (TS) test, the cations can swell more increasing consequently the TS value.

The Japanese industrial standards JIS A 5908:2015 does not require thickness swelling value for 'Type 8 Base particleboard Decorative particleboard' classification for interior grade particleboard. Nevertheless, all the particleboard samples tested using 'System 1' in Table 10.1 did not satisfy the industrial standard JIS A 5908:2015. They only satisfied the density requirement.

10.3 Alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate and bentonite system - System 2

Wheat gluten can be used as a binder when it is treated with acid or alkaline solution, which minimises its agglomeration nature. NaOH is used as an alkali treatment that can denature and unfold the secondary helical structure of proteins. This gives the adhesive formulation an added

Figure 10.1: Structure of bentonite

Table 10.2: Alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate and bentonite system 'System 2'. The detailed table is Table C.2

Particleboard number	21	22	23	24
Virgin wood particles (wt.)	65%	65%	65%	65%
Sodium alginate (wt.)	15%	10%	20%	10%
Wheat gluten (wt.)	10%	15%	10%	20%
Bbentonite (wt.)	10%	10%	5%	5%
Average MOR (MPa)	6.07 ± 0.01	6.65 ± 0.02	6.22 ± 0.01	7.03 ± 0.02
Average MOE (MPa)	1047.13 ± 12.66	1409.82 ± 4.60	1107.31 ± 3.19	1762.52 ± 22.28
Average density (kg/m ³)	728.14 ± 2.37	725.95 ± 0.94	708.41 ± 4.97	703.30 ± 2.67
Average IB (MPa)	0.13 ± 0.00	0.14 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.00	0.15 ± 0.00
Average MC (%)	14.91% ± 0.13%	14.14% ± 0.11%	13.48% ± 0.27%	12.34% ± 0.51%
Average TS (%)	20.06% ± 0.20%	19.46% ± 0.87%	15.85% ± 0.27%	13.83% ± 0.09%

Table 10.3: Alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate system 'System 3'. The detailed table is Table C.3

Particleboard number	31	32	33	34
Virgin wood particles (wt.)	65%	65%	65%	65%
Wheat gluten (wt.)	20%	25%	30%	35%
Sodium alginate (wt.)	15%	10%	5%	0%
Average MOR (MPa)	7.24 ± 0.04	7.78 ± 0.05	8.08 ± 0.15	7.53 ± 0.02
Average MOE (MPa)	1851.88 ± 26.29	1911.18 ± 18.99	2080.90 ± 17.75	1860.69 ± 17.17
Average density (kg/m ³)	721.47 ± 5.50	724.83 ± 2.12	732.38 ± 2.44	732.58 ± 2.06
Average IB (MPa)	0.15 ± 0.00	0.19 ± 0.00	0.52 ± 0.00	0.31 ± 0.00
Average MC (%)	10.75% ± 0.09%	10.30% ± 0.33%	8.57% ± 0.31%	7.88% ± 0.39%
Average TS (%)	12.97% ± 0.27%	13.15% ± 0.10%	12.10% ± 0.49%	12.30% ± 0.12%

water resistance. In addition to that, NaOH gives better surface quality to the particleboard samples. The cross-link reaction has been illustrated in section 6.4.4 in Chapter 6.

In this work, alkali-treated wheat gluten has been incorporated to make four particleboards in the adhesive formulation 'System 2' as shown in Table 10.2. The dry masses of virgin wood particles were kept constant in all four particleboards. In general, the higher the amount of bentonite increased the moisture content and the thickness swelling. A higher amount of wheat gluten increased MOR and MOE more as compared with increasing the amount of alginate. This can show that proteinous polysaccharide nature of wheat gluten can have ability to bind wood particles together rather than that of sodium alginate.

The increase in sodium alginate content in the adhesive mixture increased the thickness swelling and moisture content of the particleboard sample. As carboxylic acid hydrates, the hydration of -COONa of sodium alginate as depicted in Fig. 6.1, is the reason for showing poor physical properties.

The particleboard number 24 in Table 10.2 satisfies the IB requirement, as well as the moisture content (MC) requirement of JIS and particleboard 23 satisfies the MC requirement of JIS A 5908:2015.

10.4 Alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate system - System 3

Four particleboards were manufactured and tested without employing bentonite, as this seemed to increase thickness swelling and moisture content. The wheat gluten content of the adhesive mixture was increased, as this showed better adhesive properties in the 'system 2'. All the other parameters such as press factor, press temperature, and pressure were kept constant for all the samples.

As shown in Table 10.3, particleboard number 33 has achieved the highest MOR, MOE,

Table 10.4: Alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate system with recycled wood 'System 4'. The detailed table is Table C.4

Particleboard number	41	42	43	44
The type of wood particles	65% (wt.) of Type A	65% (wt.) of Type B	65% (wt.) of Type C	65% (wt.) of Type D
The binder (wt.)	35%	35%	35%	35%
Average MOR (MPa)	9.05 ± 0.00	6.59 ± 0.10	18.09 ± 0.07	7.79 ± 0.09
Average MOE (MPa)	2157.52 ± 46.50	2730.70 ± 38.71	3209.98 ± 31.45	3432.10 ± 41.53
Average density (kg/m ³)	793.01 ± 4.70	875.60 ± 2.22	915.81 ± 6.40	999.47 ± 5.52
Average IB (MPa)	0.62 ± 0.00	0.74 ± 0.01	1.29 ± 0.01	0.84 ± 0.01
Average MC (%)	10.64% ± 0.04%	13.74% ± 0.97%	11.72% ± 0.26%	15.15% ± 0.24%
Average TS (%)	11.99% ± 0.42%	15.28% ± 0.21%	9.07% ± 0.60%	13.42% ± 0.14%

and IB out of all the systems tested, therefore satisfying JIS Type 8 requirements. In general, though, a higher amount of wheat gluten showed better mechanical properties, and the combination with sodium alginate in the 6:1 mass ratio resulted in an enhanced cross-linking. Wheat gluten proteins consist of macropolymers of monomeric gliadin (α -gliadins, γ -gliadins, and ω -gliadins) and long polymeric glutenins (high and low molecular weight subunits) cross-linked with disulphide bonds which can be broken with alkali treatment to minimise agglomeration. These macropolymers and uncross-linked long polymers can be cross-linked with a small mass of sodium alginate. As a result of this, the wheat gluten to sodium alginate mass ratio for complete cross-link was found to be 6:1, as this produced samples with the best mechanical properties among all the samples made.

The water-absorbent nature of sodium alginate can be seen in thickness swelling test results. The decrease in the content of sodium alginate in the samples can reduce thickness swelling.

10.5 Alkali-treated wheat gluten, sodium alginate system with recycled wood - System 4

Alkali-treated wheat gluten cross-linked with sodium alginate bio-based wood binder was used to make particleboards using recycled wood particles. Four different types of recycled wood particles (Type A, B, C and D, as explained below) were used for the study and the mechanical and physical properties of particleboards made were investigated and are reported in Table 10.4.

Type A wood particles

Wood particles taken by crushing particleboards made by using virgin wood particles with the bio-based binder. Crushed wood particles were sieved to the size of 1 mm.

Type B wood particles

Wood particles taken by crushing particleboards made by using Type A wood particles with the bio-based binder. Crushed wood particles were sieved to the size of 1 mm.

Type C wood particles

Wood particles taken by crushing particleboards made by using virgin wood particles with the synthetic commercial binder. Crushed wood particles were sieved to the size of 1 *mm*.

Type D wood particles

Wood particles taken by crushing particleboards made by using Type C wood particles with the bio-based binder. Crushed wood particles were sieved to the size of 1 *mm*.

The particleboard 41 in Table 10.4 satisfied all the physical and mechanical property requirements of 'Type 8' of JIS 5908:2015. This can reveal that particleboards manufactured using bioadhesives can be re-manufactured using bioadhesives satisfying industrial standards. However, particleboard 42 showed a more brittle nature due to the increase in MOE. This is due to the high content of the adhesive. The bending strength of the sample does not satisfy industrial standards.

The particleboard 43 satisfied the 'Type 18' requirements of JIS, except for the MOR value that did not meet the standard. This shows that the usage of the bio-based wood adhesive formulation is more suitable for re-manufacturing particleboards by using recycled particles made by using synthetic adhesives. The re-manufacturing process needs to be limited to one cycle when the industrial standards are concerned. The samples become more brittle in the second cycle due to the high adhesive content.

10.6 The binder with additives - System 5 and 6

As reported in Chapter 7, the incorporation of 1% of additives into the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate binder resulted in a significant influence on its performance. Table 10.5 shows the detailed figures for samples made with virgin wood particles and Table 10.6 shows that of the recycled wood particles. Sodium dodecyl sulphate exhibited promising results with the binder as its long chain can have the ability to make bonds with the backbone of the gliadins of wheat gluten protein. These graft copolymerisation reactions can increase the number of bonds made with the hydroxyl groups of wood cell walls increasing the performance of the binder. Polyethylenimine can have the ability to make peptide bonds with many of the carboxylic groups of the amino acid of wheat gluten proving as the best out of all the additives used. Glyoxal by reacting with the amino groups of the wheat gluten proteins can increase the performance of the adhesive formulation. Diacetin also showed positive results with the reaction of amino groups and the resultant with carboxylic groups of the wheat gluten protein.

10.7 Tannin extracted from olive seed flour - System 7

Olive (*Olea europaea* L.) seed was chosen as a non-food natural source to prepare an adhesive in this study as wheat gluten and sodium alginate are also being used in the food processing industry. The olive seed contains a high amount of phenolic component in it [1]. Although it also contains proteins, its extraction process is complex and expensive. As tannin shows better adhesive properties and resistance to moisture than protein-based adhesives, the extraction of

Table 10.5: Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 5 - virgin wood particles). The detailed tables are Tables C.5 and C.6

Particleboard number	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58
Additive used	Control sample	SDS	Sodium sulfate	Polythylenimine	Glyoxal	Sodium phosphate	Diacetin	Tannin
Average MOR (MPa)	8.08 ± 0.15	11.99 ± 0.02	7.46 ± 0.03	14.40 ± 0.04	11.14 ± 0.13	9.80 ± 0.05	10.85 ± 0.06	8.51 ± 0.13
Average MOE (MPa)	2080.90 ± 17.75	2516.40 ± 32.41	2014.27 ± 23.41	2863.57 ± 4.61	2387.79 ± 96.09	2326.43 ± 35.82	2333.44 ± 2.99	2016.26 ± 9.82
Average density (kg/m ³)	732.38 ± 2.44	764.94 ± 0.40	736.35 ± 3.52	756.42 ± 2.19	760.37 ± 3.59	775.92 ± 3.24	782.81 ± 5.42	766.14 ± 1.67
Average IB (MPa)	0.52 ± 0.00	1.14 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.00	1.47 ± 0.01	0.62 ± 0.00	0.74 ± 0.01	1.29 ± 0.01	0.84 ± 0.00
Average MC (%)	8.57% ± 0.31%	7.19% ± 1.03%	9.29% ± 0.97%	10.29% ± 0.29%	8.80% ± 0.26%	9.40% ± 0.94%	8.84% ± 1.14%	9.43% ± 1.43%
Average TS (%)	12.10% ± 0.49%	9.26% ± 0.33%	12.69% ± 0.67%	9.41% ± 0.94%	12.80% ± 0.03%	11.37% ± 1.10%	10.18% ± 0.16%	12.47% ± 0.82%

Table 10.6: Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 6 - recycled wood particles). The detailed tables are Tables C.7 and C.8

Particleboard number	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68
Additive used	Control sample	SDS	Sodium sulfate	Polythylenimine	Glyoxal	Sodium phosphate	Diacetin	Tannin
Average MOR (MPa)	18.09 ± 0.07	22.74 ± 0.12	16.66 ± 0.19	26.61 ± 0.43	23.10 ± 0.05	20.86 ± 0.11	21.52 ± 0.22	19.21 ± 0.14
Average MOE (MPa)	3209.98 ± 31.45	3977.24 ± 21.52	3101.59 ± 56.52	4127.52 ± 16.97	3621.28 ± 22.93	3530.92 ± 18.32	3508.79 ± 37.85	3111.53 ± 37.92
Average density (kg/m ³)	915.81 ± 6.40	926.90 ± 6.73	937.01 ± 9.18	926.48 ± 3.32	937.29 ± 4.57	946.95 ± 0.53	927.55 ± 6.14	925.60 ± 3.98
Average IB (MPa)	1.29 ± 0.01	1.51 ± 0.00	1.27 ± 0.01	2.13 ± 0.01	1.50 ± 0.01	1.36 ± 0.01	1.61 ± 0.00	1.50 ± 0.01
Average MC (%)	11.72% ± 0.26%	9.50% ± 0.39%	13.30% ± 0.05%	10.98% ± 0.94%	11.95% ± 0.71%	12.88% ± 0.19%	13.34% ± 2.00%	12.69% ± 0.41%
Average TS (%)	9.07% ± 0.60%	4.67% ± 0.34%	9.19% ± 1.06%	7.26% ± 0.36%	9.81% ± 0.74%	9.07% ± 0.62%	9.40% ± 0.76%	8.77% ± 0.09%

olive seed tannin from olive seed flour was carried out in this work. Alkali-extraction of olive seed flour was the most effective extraction that showed a promising yield of tannins compared to the water and acid extraction from olive seed flour. NaOH extraction showed to increase organic matter (a large source of carbon-based compounds) content of phenolic compounds [2]. The increase in organic phenolic compounds in a wood adhesive mixture increases the number of chemical bonds made with wood cell hydroxyl groups, increasing the mechanical performance of particleboards.

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Chapter 11

Conclusion and future work

“Wood burns faster when you have to cut and chop it yourself.”

Harrison Ford

11.1 Conclusions

Consumer-driven demand for greener wood adhesives has increased enormously due to the environmental and human health concerns of synthetic adhesives that have been used for decades. This has caused an increment in research interest in the wood processing industry. However, the cost and failure in moisture durability have been limiting the market acceptance of purely bio-based wood adhesives [1]. The ability to blend almost all the bio-based wood adhesives with all the types of synthetic wood adhesives gives promising results by lessening formaldehyde emission up to the limits of the industrial standards without downgrading the mechanical and physical properties of the wood-based panels.

Protein derived wood adhesives are one of the major sources of bio-adhesives used in industrial and research sectors by using protein modification methods such as crosslinking, denaturation, chemical modification, enzyme modification and nanoparticle addition in order to improve their adhesion and importantly the water-resistance of the adhesive formulation. Wheat gluten (WG) is a co-product [2, 3] as well as a by-product [4] of the starch manufacturing process. WG consists of two water-insoluble proteins called glutenins and gliadins. Gliadins contain low-molecular-weight proteins, and glutenins consist of high-molecular-weight proteins. In this study, as reported in Chapter 6, NaOH was used to degrade the disulphide bonds of these proteins to make them soluble. They were then cross-linked with sodium alginate to make a thermoset adhesive that can react with the hydroxyl groups of wood cell walls. The adhesive formulation showed good results with virgin wood particles, but even better results with recycled wood particles, which already contained formaldehyde.

The formaldehyde content in recycled wood particles makes the re-manufacturing of wood-based panels using cost-effective formaldehyde-based synthetic adhesives, such as

urea-formaldehyde, impossible due to the inability to meet the formaldehyde emission requirements of the industrial standards. In Chapter 8, the bio-adhesive formulation developed in this work was used to make particleboards both with virgin wood particles and recycled wood particles.

in equal amounts. The boards satisfied all the industrial standards in the first cycle of re-manufacturing. Therefore, Chapter 8 reveals the potential of the usage of the bioadhesive formulation for re-manufacturing of wood-based panels.

The resin formulation was further improved by incorporating additives 1% (w/w) as mentioned in Chapter 7. Polyethylenimine as an additive to the adhesive showed the best increase in mechanical properties. Other than sodium sulphate and tannin, SDS, glyoxal, sodium phosphate and diacetin exhibited industrially attractive results, as additives when incorporated with the alkali-treated wheat gluten and sodium alginate bio-based adhesive formulation. The whole formulations can be taken as commercially competitive and as a sustainable innovative bio-based wood adhesive formulation for virgin wood particles as well as for recycled wood particles by moving the existing linear economy in wood processing industry into a circular economy.

In Chapter 9, the olive seed, which is a non-food by-product of the olive oil industry was used to extract tannins from it. Although olive seed flour extracts contain proteins, their extraction process is more complex and expensive than extracting tannins. Tannins as a bio-based wood adhesive in general, exhibit better physical properties than proteins-based bio-adhesives. Tannins extracted from the olive seed flour as a bio-based wood adhesive produced particleboard, which satisfied industrial standards when particleboards were made with recycled wood particles. This reveals the potential of utilising waste wood and the waste by-product of the olive oil industry to make particleboard with industrial standards.

Europe is self-sufficient for wood [5]. Diverting waste from landfill is a great concern in the European Commission (EC) by moving the linear economy into a circular economy. Wood packaging waste is widely targeted by European Union looking for potentials for recycling with both economic and environmental benefits [6]. As shown in this study and in Fig. 8.1, the waste in the olive seed industry and the waste of the wood industry can be used to make wood-based panels by reducing waste amount reaching landfill. This would represent a big constituent of the eco-innovation process that promotes the circular economy [7, 8].

Not only the combination of bio-based wood adhesives and recycled wood particles would contribute to a circular economy, but it would also reduce the number of cut down trees, in addition, it would reduce the consumption of petrochemicals that are needed in the production of formaldehyde-based synthetic wood adhesives, minimising as well toxic formaldehyde emission that causes nasopharynx cancer in humans. The formaldehyde emission is higher when the indoor furniture or the wood-based products made using formaldehyde-based synthetic adhesives are new. So, the consumers are advised to keep their windows open for extra ventilation, which is not practical during the winter months. In general, fully bio-based wood adhesives are good in mechanical properties and can be used for indoor applications. The main drawbacks are the poor physical properties and the higher price as compared to the formaldehyde-based adhesives such as UF. Incorporating non-formaldehyde-based additive with bio-based wood adhesives can improve their physical properties.

Figure 11.1: Incorporating bio-based wood adhesive formulations (in brown) into existing production lines (in black) of wood-based panels that synthetic adhesives are used.

Blending bio-based wood adhesives with formaldehyde-based adhesives strengthens their properties by reducing the formaldehyde emission of the final product. Almost all the bio-based wood adhesives can be blended with synthetic wood adhesives as all their structures are polymers or monomers. The blending can give extra strength to the final product due to its ability to cross-link.

11.2 Future work

The alkali-treated WG and SA binder can be further developed by incorporating more additives and/or synthetic adhesives in further research. In addition to wheat gluten, the glutes of rye, barley, triticale can be tested by considering their cost-effectiveness.

Incorporating nanomaterials with protein-based wood adhesives is widely investigated in research to improve physical and mechanical properties. There is a greater potential of enhancing panel performance by adding nanomaterials into the alkali-treated WG and SA binder.

While olive seed flour is used to extract tannin, there is a possibility of using the olive stone instead to make a biocomposite. This can address the significant environmental issue of olive mill waste *alperujo* in the Mediterranean area.

Catalysts, in general, can reduce the applied pressure, curing temperature and/or curing time without damaging panel performance. This can give a greater advantage for the manufacturer reducing the production cost. Incorporating a catalyst in the bio-adhesives developed in this study can have the promising potential of reducing the manufacturing cost of the wood-based panel.

Incorporating bio-based adhesive formulations into the existing manufacturing routes as shown in Fig. 11.1 would reduce the formaldehyde emission of the final wood-based panels. The mixing of bio-adhesives with additives and mixing of the adhesive formulation with liquid chemical or water should be done 'in-situ' as the storage life of bio-based adhesives are comparatively shorter than that of synthetic adhesives in the adaptation process. As a result of incorporating bio-based wood adhesives, the hot press time should be increased due to the

increase in press factor. A star cooler system is recommended for the drying in the air process. The process would also take a longer period of time due to the less volatile nature of bio-based wood adhesives as compared with synthetic wood adhesives.

Future research in the bio-based wood adhesive industry should focus on the following targets in order to eliminate or minimise the main drawbacks identified so far:

- Identifying new bio-based materials as raw materials for adhesives,
- make use of by-product as raw materials for bio-based adhesives,
- introducing bio-sourced synthetic adhesives,
- shorter the press time,
- enhancing bond strength,
- increase moisture resistance,
- lower the thickness swelling,
- minimising energy requirement for the production,
- incorporating wood preservatives with the adhesive formulations,
- reducing volatile organic compounds in the final wood composite,
- life cycle analysis of wood-based panels made by using bio-based adhesives,
- moving towards binderless bonding and wood welding,
- working towards a zero environmental footprint.

Long-term research and developments are needed in order to address the drawbacks in the wood adhesive industry.

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List of Publications

List of published papers

- [1] Ajith K. A. Gedara, Iva Chianella, Jose L. Endrino, Qi Zhang, [Adhesiveless Bonding of Wood – A Review with a Focus on Wood Welding](#). *BioResources* 16(3) 1-23, Gedara et al (2021), DOI: 10.15376/biores.16.3.Gedara
- [2] Ajith K. A. Gedara, Iva Chianella, Jose L. Endrino, Qi Zhang, [Tannins Extracted from Olive Seed Flour as Bioadhesives for Manufacturing Wood-based Panels](#), *International Conference on wood Adhesives, Chemistry and Technology - Venice, Italy 12-13 August 2021*

List of accepted papers

- [1] Ajith K. A. Gedara, Jose L. Endrino, Qi Zhang, Non-toxic wood binders for manufacturing engineered wood panels: Challenges and Future opportunities - A Perspective, *International Journal of Adhesive and Adhesion*
- [2] Ajith K. A. Gedara, Debabrata Bhattacharyya, Jose L. Endrino, Qi Zhang, Alkali treated wheat gluten cross-linked with sodium alginate as a bio-based wood adhesive for interior grade particleboard, *International Journal of Adhesive and Adhesion*

Appendix A

Enhancing mechanical and physical properties of bio-based wood adhesives. A Review

“When the uncarved wood is split, its parts are put to use. When the sage is put to use, he becomes the head.”

Laozi

Abstract

Most of the bio-based wood adhesives have lower mechanical and physical properties compared to most traditional synthetic adhesives such as phenol-formaldehyde (PF), melamine-formaldehyde (MF), urea-formaldehyde (UF) and melamine-urea-formaldehyde (MUF). This greatly limits their applications. The higher market price and the higher adhesive quantity needed are other factors that limit the manufacturing of wood-based panels with bio-based wood adhesives. Incorporation of additives, cross-linkers, dispersing agents and hardeners individually or in combination into bio-based adhesives increases mechanical and physical properties of the formulations. Although most of the additives are synthetic, they do not increase the formaldehyde emissions of the final wood-based panels. Some additives reduce the curing temperature or pressure without influencing mechanical or physical properties of the samples. This can reduce the manufacturing cost by easing the curing mechanism and retaining functional properties of the adhesive formulation in the wood-based panel industry.

Keywords: Bioadhesives, additives, water-resistance, wood-based panels.

A.1 Introduction

Bio-based wood adhesives can be composed of several components such as polymers, oligomers and fillers. The functional properties, polymerisation and curing mechanisms of the adhesives are based on their composition. Additives are being incorporated in bio-based or synthetic wood adhesives in order to satisfy the end-user requirement, the application, processing requirements, industrial standards and finally the cost [1].

For example, wood gap-filling and adhesive properties of polymeric 4,4'-methylene diphenyl isocyanate (pMDI) can be increased drastically by adding lignin-containing cellulose nanofibril as an excellent reinforcing material [2]. In addition, it has been shown in another example, that the ultrasonication technique can be used as an effective way to disperse nano-clay in a PVA matrix in order to enhance the mechanical properties of PVA wood adhesive [3]. Additives are also suitable to either absorb, quench, or block UV radiation which affect wood degradation [4].

The major challenges in manufacturing bio-based wood adhesives are enhancing their mechanical and physical properties to achieve relevant industrial standards and to compete with the synthetic wood adhesives currently available in the market. Incorporating additives within the adhesive formulation plays a major role in the wood adhesives industry as they can act as the binding agents for the biomass raw materials [5].

A.1.1 Enhancing the mechanical properties of bio-based wood adhesives

A database of bio-based wood adhesives and the additives (enhancers) that can be incorporated to enhance their mechanical properties is shown in Table A.1. The blended additive or the additives mixed with the bio-based wood adhesive are mostly synthetic.

Table A.1: Mechanical property enhancers that can be incorporated with bio-based wood adhesives.

Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Acrylated epoxidized soy oil	Urea formaldehyde [6].
Aluminophosphate inorganic adhesive	$Al(OH)_3$ and H_3PO_4 [7].
Bagasse lignin	Phenol formaldehyde [8].
Bark of radiata pine (<i>Pinus radiata</i>)	Two-stage extraction with hot water and one-stage extraction with NaOH aqueous (pH 8.3) solution followed by a one-stage washing with hot water [9].
Bark-derived bio-crudes	Neat phenol formaldehyde resole [10].
Bio-ethanol biorefinery residue	Phenol formaldehyde [11, 12].
Canola protein	Graphite Oxide nanoparticles [13].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Canola protein	NaHSO ₃ [14].
Canola protein	SDS [15, 16].
Carbohydrate	Cottonseed proteins [17].
Carboxymethyl starch	Urea formaldehyde [18].
Cassava starch	Hydrogen peroxide, acrylamide, butyl acrylate, and an organic siloxane [19].
Cassava starch	Polycarboxylic acid, citric acid or 1,2,3,4 butane-tetracarboxylic acid [20].
Cassava starch (oxidised)	urea-glyoxal [21].
Caster oil based polyurethane	Polyol and aromatic isocyanate [22].
Caster oil based polyurethane	TiO ₂ nanoparticles [23].
Cellulose nanofibers extracted from rice straw	Urea formaldehyde [24].
Chestnut (<i>Castanea sativa</i>) shell tannin extracts	Tris(hydroxymethyl)nitromethane, glyoxal and hexamethylenetetramine [25, 26].
Chicken feather	Styrene-butadiene elastomer [27].
Chitosan	Glutaraldehyde [28].
Chitosan	NaOH-treated adherends and 1% (vol/vol) glycerol [29].
Chitosan	Phenolic compounds and laccase [30].
Condensed flavonoid tannins from Maritime Pine (<i>Pinus pinaster</i>), Mimosa (<i>Acacia mearnsii</i>), and Radiata Pine barks, and Quebracho (<i>Schinopsis lorentzii</i> and <i>balansae</i>) wood	First reaction with dimethyl carbonate and then with hexamethylenediamine [31].
Condensed Protein Isolate	Addition of H ₃ PO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄ , CaO, or CaHPO ₄ [32]
Condensed tannins from <i>Pinus radiata</i> bark	Chemical modification with propylene oxide [33]
Corn flour/NaOH	Mimosa tannin/hexamine [34].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Corn starch	Acid-hydrolysis using vinyl acetate, ammonium persulfate, sodium bicarbonate, sodium dodecyl sulfate, sodium hydroxide, acetone, and hydrochloric acid [35].
Corn starch	Esterification and polyisocyanate prepolymer cross-linking [36].
Corn starch	Tannin [37, 38].
Corn starch	Urea formaldehyde [39].
Corn starch	Vinyl acetate and butyl acrylate using ammonium persulfate as initiator [40].
Corn starch	Vinyl acetate and butyl acrylate [41].
Corn Starch and tannin	Phenol formaldehyde [42].
Cottonseed	Amino acids, fatty acids, and other organic molecules with cationic or anionic charges. Aspartic acid, glutamic acid, acetic acid, butyric acid, and adipic acid [43].
Cottonseed meal	Pure UF resin [44].
Cottonseed protein	Alkali, guanidine hydrochloride, sodium dodecyl sulfate, and urea [45].
Cottonseed protein	Polysaccharide (starch, xylan, or cellulose) [46].
Cottonseed protein isolate	Carboxy-methyl cellulose (66%), pectin blends (50%), poly(vinyl sulfate) (30%) [47].
Cottonseed protein isolate	Cellulose nano fibre [48].
Crude glycerol-based polyols (waste stream of the biodiesel production process)	Polyurethane [49].
Defatted soy flour	1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid [50].
Defatted soy flour	Acid salt and alkali [51].
Defatted soy flour	Enzymolyzed by Viscozyme L [52].
Defatted soy flour	Viscozyme L [53].
Demethylated kraft lignin	Polyethylenimine [54].
Depolymerised lignin (4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and syringaldehyde)	Phenol under alkaline condition [55].
Desulfurized kraft lignin	Hexamethylene diamine [56].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Desulfurized kraft lignin	Triethyl phosphate [57].
Dialdehyde Cellulose	1M HCL, hydroxylamine hydrochloride and NaOH to get the pH of 3.5 [58]
Dry starch	Urea [59]
Epoxidized canola oil	Phthalic anhydride [60].
Epoxidized rubber seed oil	Triethylenetetramine [61].
Esterified kraft lignins	Maleic anhydride, succinic anhydride, and phthalic anhydride in acetone solutions [62].
Fermentation residues obtained by growing the anaerobic cellulolytic bacterias	Phenol formaldehyde [63].
Fibrillated bark adhesives	Phenol formaldehyde [64].
Fresh cattle blood	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, Lime water, sodium azide, NaOH, Sodium Silicate, Aluminum dihydrogen, Ammonia [65].
Furfuryl alcohol	Commercial tannin [66].
Furfuryl alcohol	Spent-liquor [66].
Geopolymer binder from pozzolanic by-product fly ash	Silica fume [67].
Glucose and sucrose	Dimethyl carbonate and hexamethylene diamine [68].
Glucose or sucrose	Triacetin (glycerin triacetate) and with hexamethylene diamine [69].
Glyoxalated wheat straw lignin solution	Mimosa tannin and hexamine [70].
Ground-decayed-wood flour with with NaOH	Sodium borohydride [71].
High amylose starch	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate [72].
High amylose starch	Sucrose fatty acid esters [73].
High starch content wood adhesive	Lauryl sodium sulfate combined with alkylphenol ethoxylates [74].
Hydrocolloidal glucomannans, chitosan or chitin	A mixed combination of these [75].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Hydrolysed chicken feather (in NaOH)	Hydrolysed chicken blood (in H ₂ SO ₄) [76].
Hydroxyl liquid natural rubber polyols	Modified poly(ethylene terephthalate) with polymeric MDI [77].
Hydroxymethyl furfural (formed by the dehydration of certain sugars)	Urea modification and adding urea formaldehyde [78].
Hydroxymethylated or glyoxalated hydrolysed gluten protein	Tannin/hexamine or small proportion of pMDI [79].
Isolated lignins	Sulfonation, methylation, phenolation, alkoxylation, acrylation, and many others [80].
Isolated soy protein	Chestnut tannin modification [81].
Konjac glucomannan	Chitosan and polyvinyl alcohol [82].
Konjac glucomannan	Chitosan [83].
Kraft lignin	Phenol formaldehyde [84, 85].
Kraft lignin	Polyaminoamide–epichlorohydrin resin [86].
Kraft lignin	Polyethylenimine [87].
Kraft pine lignin	Oxypropylation [88].
Lignin	Conjugation with natural rubber latex [89].
Lignin	Demethylation and oxidation [90].
Lignin	Enzymatically modification [91].
Lignin	Enzyme solution (after filtration of the mycelium) [92].
Lignin	Extraction with sulphuric acid [93].
Lignin	Furfural [94].
Lignin	Glycerol (Biodiesel) [95].
Lignin	Glyoxal and phenol [96].
Lignin	Glyoxal and urea [97].
Lignin	Glyoxal under an alkaline medium [98].
Lignin	Glyoxal [99, 100, 101].
Lignin	Ionic liquid [102].
Lignin	Methylation [103].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Lignin	One-component polyurethane systems [104].
Lignin	Phenol formaldehyde [105, 11, 106].
Lignin	Phenol formaldehyde and ionic liquid modification [107].
Lignin	Phenol [108].
Lignin	Phenol, glyoxal and epoxy resin [109].
Lignin	Phenolate modification [110].
Lignin	Phenol-formaldehyde [111].
Lignin	pMDI [112].
Lignin	Tannin/hexamine and glyoxylation of lignin [113, 92].
Lignin	Triacetin [112].
Lignin (obtained from <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> wood)	Methylation or phenolation reaction [114].
Lignin and tannin	Glyoxal and hexamine [115, 116].
Lignin and tannin	Glyoxal [117].
Lignin and tannin	Polyethylenimine [118].
Lignin-based aldehyde precursors	Vanillin [119].
Lignin-rich fibre	Laccase-amino acid treatment [120].
Lignins from oil palm biomass	Phenol formaldehyde [121].
Liquefied olive stone	Wood pyrolysis oil derived from hardwood and condensed tannin extracted from the bark of Black Wattle tree [122].
Liquefied wood using glycerol/diethylene glycol	Melamine–formaldehyde and melamine–urea–formaldehyde resins [123].
Loblolly pine milled-wood lignin	Alkali in the presence of formaldehyde or lignin model compounds [124].
Locust bean gum	Brown liquor [125].
Mangium tannin	Phenol Resorcinol Formaldehyde [126].
Maillard- reacted chitosan	Glucose [127].
Methylolated lignin	pMDI [112].
Microbial extracellular polysaccharide	Surface wetting agent monorhamnolipid [128].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Mimosa tannin	Hexamine solution [70].
Modified ammonium lignosulfonate	Polyethylenimine [129].
Modified soy protein	Formaldehyde based adhesives [130].
Multihydroxy Soybean Oil	pMDI [131].
Mycelium of fungi	Cellulose nanofibrils [132].
Natural rubber latex	Amine modification and reinforcement effect of soy protein nanoparticles [133].
Natural rubber latex	Polyvinyl alcohol [134].
Oil palm-extracted starch	Glutardialdehyde [135].
Oil palm starch	Epichlorohydrin modification and urea formaldehyde [136].
Ozonised Sunflower Oil	α -D-Glucose [137].
Peanut meal	Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) [138].
Phenol-rich fraction of crude bio-oil	Phenol formaldehyde [139].
Pine bark tannin	Phenol urea formaldehyde [140].
Pine Tannin	Melamine formaldehyde, phenol formaldehyde and diisocyanate [141].
Pine Tannin	Synthesise with different aldehyde [142].
Pinus pinaster bark (1% NaOH extract)	Resoles and phenolic acids [143].
Polenta cornstarch	Mimosa tannin and urea formaldehyde [144].
Polyester polyols synthesised from potato starch and natural oils	Toluene 2,4-diisocyanate [145].
Procyanidin-type condensed tannin	Polyethylenimine [146].
Potato starch/chitosan	Citric acid [147].
Protein	Commercial synthetic adhesives [148].
Protein	Expose to OH, COOH, NH ₂ and SH [149].
Protein extracted with acetic acid from distillers dried grains with solubles	Glutaraldehyde modification [150].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Proteins extracted from <i>Spirulina platensis</i> and <i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Denaturation with NaOH and chemical cross-linking [151].
Pulp and paper secondary sludge	Urea formaldehyde [152].
Purified soy protein isolate	Polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin [153].
Pyrolysis bio-oils	Phenol formaldehyde [154, 155].
Rice bran	Urea formaldehyde [39].
Sesame Protein	Urea and zinc oxide [156].
Soda bagasse lignin	1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate ([Emim] [OAc]) ionic liquid [157].
Soda lignin modified by 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate	Urea formaldehyde and polymeric 4, 4 diphenyl methane diisocyanate (pMDI) [107].
Softwood bark residues pyrolysis oil	Phenol [158].
Sour cassava starch	Chitosan [159].
Soy flour	Aldehyde phenol [160].
Soy flour	Co-polymerisation with a resole phenol-formaldehyde resin [161].
Soy flour	Glyoxalated lignin or tannin [162].
Soy flour	NaOH, NaCl [163].
Soy flour	NaOH, ammonia and epichlorohydrin derived from renewable glycerol [164].
Soy flour	Polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin [165].
Soy flour	Reacting with NaOH for 1 hour below 100 °C [166].
Soy protein	Hyperbranched polysiloxane-terminated cardanol side group with tannic acid [167].
Soy protein	Biomass lignin [168].
Soy protein	Laccase/TEMPO-modified lignin [169].
Soy protein	Melamine epichlorohydrin prepolymer [170].
Soy protein	NaCl, Na ₂ SO ₄ or Na ₂ SO ₃ [171].
Soy protein	Polyacrylate copolymers [172].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Soy protein	Polyurethane Elastomer [173].
Soy protein	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate [174].
Soy protein	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate [175].
Soy protein	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate and Sodium Dodecylbenzene Sulfonate [176].
Soy protein	Thermal alkali degradation, thermal acid treatment, and cross-linking [177].
Soy protein	Triglycidylamine and modified sepiolite [178].
Soy protein	Trypsin modification [179].
Soy protein	Urea and Guanidine Hydrochloride [180].
Soy protein	Urea or Alkali or heat modification [181].
Soy protein concentrate	Alkali modification [182].
Soy Protein concentrate	Gelatin resin [183].
Soy protein concentrate	Montmorillonite [184].
Soy Protein concentrate	Silane, (3-iso-cyanatopropyl)triethoxysilane [185].
Soy protein isolate	Condensed tannins modified by hexamine [186].
Soy protein isolate	Epoxidized oleic acid [187].
Soy protein isolate	Ethylene glycol [188].
Soy protein isolate	Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) [189].
Soy protein isolate	Sodium dodecyl sulfate and guanidine hydrochloride [190].
Soy protein isolate	Thermal modification [191].
Soy protein isolate	Triglycidylamine and oxidated soybean soluble polysaccharide [192].
Soy protein isolate	Urea, sodium dodecyl sulfate and propanetriol [193].
Soy-based	Acrylic ester [194].
Soy-based	Borax (sodium tetraborate) [59].
Soy-based	Carboxymethyl Cellulose [195].
Soy-based	Chemical modifications including alkali denaturation, surfactant denaturation, organic solvent denaturation, enzymatic treatment, epoxy groups crosslinking, formaldehyde compounds crosslinking, acylation and silanation [196].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Soy-based	Melamine urea formaldehyde [197].
Soy-based	Nanoparticle modification using cellulosic nanofibers, inorganic nanoparticles and nano-clays [196].
Soy-based	Physical modification including compression, high temperature treatment, ultrasound treatment and blending with hydrophobic additives [196].
Soy-based	Pretreated graft copolymerisation reaction at 90 °C [198].
Soy-based	Urea modification, adding chestnut extracts and hexamine, and adding tannins [199].
Soybean flour	γ -amino, γ -glycidyl, or γ -methacryloyloxy-propyltrimethoxysilane [200].
Soybean flour	Hydroxymethyl Melamine Prepolymer [201].
Soybean flour	Phenol-formaldehyde and isocyanate [202].
Soybean meal	5,5-dimethyl hydantoin polyepoxide [203].
Soybean meal	Diethylene glycol diglycidyl ether [204].
Soybean meal	Ethylene glycol diglycidyl ether and diethylenetriamine [205].
Soybean meal flour	Commercial epoxy resin [206].
Starch	CA20 or BTCA80 (more suitable) [207].
Starch	Isocyanate [208].
Starch	Montmorillonite [209].
Starch	Nanofillers [210].
Starch	Nano-TiO ₂ [211].
Starch	Resorcinol dialdehyde and formaldehyde [212].
Starch	Silica nanoparticles [213].
Starch	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate [214, 215, 216].
Starch	Urea formaldehyde [217].
Starch	Urea-oxidation, KMnO ₄ as the oxidiser [218].
Sucrose, dimethyl carbonate and hexamethylene diamine	Silane coupling agent [219].
Tannin	Boric acid [220].
Tannin	Formaldehyde [221].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Tannin	Formaldehyde and furfural [222].
Tannin	Furfural [223].
Tannin (minosa or pine)	Furfural alcohol [224].
Tannin	Glyoxal and then isocyanates [225].
Tannin	Glyoxal and triacetin [226].
Tannin	Glyoxal [226].
Tannin	Hexamine [227, 228].
Tannin	Hyd-BzAld [229].
Tannin	Impregnation of natural nonwoven fibre [230].
Tannin	MDI methylene diphenyl diisocyanate [231].
Tannin	Organosolv alfa lignin [93].
Tannin	Paraformaldehyde [226].
Tannin	Phenol formaldehyde [232, 233].
Tannin	Phenol/resorcinol/formaldehyde [234].
Tannin	pMDI and glyoxal [226].
Tannin	Polyethylenimine [235].
Tannin	PVAc [236].
Tannin	Trishydroxymethyl nitromethane [228].
Tannin and urea	Phenol formaldehyde [237].
Tannin extract	Glucose and periodate [238].
Tannin fortified by aminoplastic resin	Commercial polymeric MDI [239].
Tannin-furfuryl alcohol	Polyethyleneimine [240].
Tannin-glyoxalated Kraft lignin (TGKL)	Phenol formaldehyde [241].
Thick spent sulfite liquor (TSSL)	Wheat flour [242].
Urea-glyoxalated lignin-formaldehyde	Sodium-montmorillonite [243].

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Bio-based adhesive	Mechanical property enhancer
Valonia oak (<i>Quercus aegylops</i>) acorn tannin extract	50% of phenol [244].
Variety of carbohydrates - from glucose to polymorphic hemicelluloses	Phenol formaldehyde [75].
Vegetable polyflavonoid tannin extract	Phenol–formaldehyde [101].
Water washed cottonseed meal	Cottonseed protein isolate and residues after protein extraction [245].
Water washed cottonseed meal	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate, guanidine hydrochloride [246].
Western red cedar (<i>Thuja plicata</i>) tree bark	pMDI (B-pMDI) [247].
Wheat gluten	Boric acid as a fungicide [248].
Wheat gluten	Formaldehyde, glyoxal and glutaraldehyde (cold setting) [249].
Wheat gluten	Glutaraldehyde [250].
Wheat gluten protein	Polypropylene [251].
Wheat gluten protein hydrolysates	Phenol formaldehyde [252].

A.1.2 Enhancing water-resistance of bio-based wood adhesives

In general, bio-based wood adhesives exhibit poor performance in terms of water-resistance. Mixing synthetic adhesives with bio-based adhesives can enrich the mechanical properties, especially it can increase their water-resistance, which otherwise represent a disadvantage in many applications [253]. Apart from that, non-adhesive materials are added to the adhesive formulations to enhance mechanical/physical strengths, thermal properties and adhesion performance [1].

Isocyanate (pMDI) is one of the main additives to the UF resins to improve their water-resistance [254]. Additives such as glutaraldehyde are used to increase the water-resistance of the synthetic urea formaldehyde wood adhesive [255].

It has been shown that by adding hydrochloride salt of hydrolysed waste nylon fibre obtained from ladies' stockings, the water-resistance of UF resin can be increased [256]. Furthermore, the addition of succinaldehyde to UF resins [257] and the addition of nano-clay into PVA [258] improve the water-resistance of wood adhesive joints. The water-resistance of particleboard prepared can also be increased by adding biomasses such as Tetra Pak residues [259].

In another study, improved water-resistance was shown to decrease the formaldehyde emission when UF resin was modified with blocked pMDI (blocked with an aqueous sodium bisulphite solution) [260].

The water-resistance of the adhesive formulation is one of the main physical properties that needs consideration. In general, bio-based wood adhesives exhibit poor performance in terms of water-resistance. Water-resistance enhancers that can be added to bio-based wood adhesives are shown in Table A.2.

Table A.2: List of Bio-based adhesives and enhancers added to increase water-resistance.

Bio-based adhesive	Water-resistance enhancer
<i>Acacia mangium</i> bark powder	Citric acid [261, 262].
Camelina protein	Depolymerised lignin [263].
Camelina protein	Polymeric amine epichlorohydrin [264].
Canola protein	NaHSO ₃ [265].
Canola protein	Graphite Oxide nanoparticles[13].
Canola protein	Nanomaterials [266].
Cassava starch	Bio-oil [267].
Cassava starch	Polycarboxylic acid, citric acid or 1,2,3,4 butane-tetracarboxylic acid [20].
Chicken feathers fibre	Phenol formaldehyde [268, 269].

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Bio-based adhesive	Water-resistance enhancer
Chitosan	Xanthan Gum [270].
Condensed tannins (Mimosa) extract	Sulphitation and metabisulphitation [271].
Cornstarch and poly(vinyl alcohol) with hexamethoxymethylmelamine (Cymel 323)	Latex (UCar 443) [272].
Cottonseed meal	Water washing and phosphate buffer (35 mM Na ₂ HPO ₄ /NaH ₂ PO ₄ , pH 7.5) washing [273, 274].
Cottonseed protein	GuHCl, Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate, and urea [275].
Cottonseed protein	Nanocellulose [48].
Cottonseed protein	Phosphorus-containing additives [276].
Cottonseed protein isolate	Carboxy-methyl cellulose and pectin blends [47].
Defatted soy flour	Acid hydrolysis of carbohydrates [277].
Defatted soy flour	Acid salt and alkali [51].
Defatted soy flour	Enzymolyzed by Viscozyme L [52].
Defatted soy flour	MgO [278].
Defatted soy flour	Viscozyme L [53].
Demethylated kraft lignin	Polyethylenimine [279].
Distiller's Dry Grain and Solubles	Isocyanate-containing cross-linking agents [280].
Keratin extract	Urea formaldehyde [281].
Kraft lignin	Acid washing [282].
Kraft lignin	Polyaminoamide–epichlorohydrin resin [86].
Lignin	Chitosan [283].
Lignin	Demethylation and oxidation [90].
Lignin	Phenol formaldehyde [284].
Lignin and tannin	Polyethylenimine [118].
Lignin cleavage products	Dimethyl sulfoxide [285].
Liquefied white birch bark in water/ethanol (50:50, v/v)	HTL-oil [286].

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Bio-based adhesive	Water-resistance enhancer
Maleic anhydride soy protein isolate	Polyethylenimine [287].
Mangrove tannin	Phenol resorcinol adhesive [288].
Maucronata tannin	Phenol resorcinol formaldehyde [288].
Pine bark polyphenols	Hexamine [289].
Pine tannin	Small percentages of pMDI, paraformaldehyde or hexamethylenetetramine [290].
Potato starch/chitosan	Citric acid [147].
Proteinaceous waste of slaughterhouses	Polyamideamine-epichlorohydrin [291].
Proteins extracted from <i>Spirulina platensis</i> and <i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Denaturation with NaOH and chemical cross-linking [151].
Rapeseed flour	Hydrolysis by sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions of 3%, 5%, and 7%. Phenol formaldehyde [292].
Soda lignin modified by 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate	Urea formaldehyde and polymeric 4, 4 diphenyl methane diisocyanate (pMDI) [107].
Sodium silicate	Polyvinyl alcohol [293].
Sorghum lignin	Soy protein adhesives (SPA) based on soy protein isolates (SPI) or modified soy protein [294].
Soy based adhesive	Chestnut and mimosa tannin extracts [81].
Soy based adhesive	Epoxy resin and melamine formaldehyde [295].
Soy based adhesive	Tannic acid [296].
Soy flour	Epichlorohydrin, NH ₄ OH and NaOH [297].
Soy flour	NaOH, ammonia and epichlorohydrin derived from renewable glycerol [164].
Soy flour	PVA [298].
Soy protein	5% Polyamide–Epichlorohydrin [299].
Soy protein	Alkali modification [300].
Soy protein	CaCO ₃ [301].
Soy protein	Organosilicon–acrylate microemulsion and epoxy synergistic interfacial enhancement [302].

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Bio-based adhesive	Water-resistance enhancer
Soy protein	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate [174].
Soy protein	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate [175].
Soy protein	Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate and Sodium Dodecylbenzene Sulfonate [176].
Soy protein	Trimethylolpropane triglycidyl ether, NaOH, $-NH_2$, COOH, $-OH$ [303].
Soy protein	Trypsin modification [300].
Soy protein	Urea and Guanidine Hydrochloride [180].
Soy protein	Urea modification [181].
Soy protein isolate	Amide linkage by grafting cysteamine [304].
Soy protein isolate	Epoxidized oleic acid [187].
Soy protein isolate	Ethylene glycol [188].
Soy protein isolate	Grafting dopamine [305].
Soy protein isolate	Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) [189].
Soy protein isolate	Undecylenic acid [306].
Soybean flour	γ -amino, γ -glycidyl, or γ -methacryloyloxy-propyltrimethoxysilane [200].
Soybean flour	Acid-salt solution 3.0 g, treatment time 33 min and treatment temperature 29 °C [307].
Soybean flour	Hydrated lime and sodium silicate solution [308].
Soybean flour	NaOH, acetic anhydride and polyethylenimine [309].
Soybean flour	Polyamidoamine [310, 311].
Soybean flour/acetic anhydride	Polyethylenimine and NaOH [309].
Soybean meal	5,5-dimethyl hydantoin polyepoxide [203].
Soybean meal	Lignin-based resin [312].
Soybean meal	Natural fibre-reinforcement [313].
Soybean meal	Polyethyleneglycol diacrylate as crosslinker [314].
Soybean meal	Sodium dodecyl sulfate and modified polyacrylic acid solution [315].
Soybean meal	Soy bean soluble polysaccharide [316].

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Bio-based adhesive	Water-resistance enhancer
Soybean meal	Triglycidyl isocyanurate, diethylenetriamine, succinic anhydride, and NaOH [317].
Soybean meal	Triglycidylamine, sepiolite [178].
Soybean meal flour	Cellulose nano-whiskers, sodium hydroxide, and polyethylene glycol [318].
Soybean meal flour	polyacrylamide, sodium dodecyl sulfate [206].
Soybean protein	Hydrochloric acid, various crosslinkers, namely glyoxal, polyisocyanate, a glyoxal–polyisocyanate combination, water-borne epoxy latex and modified polyamide [319].
Soybean protein	Thermo-chemical treatment of soybean protein in the presence of 1 wt% sodium sulphite and 1 wt% sodium dodecylsulfate [320].
Starch	Carboxy-methyl [321].
Starch	Comonomer [322].
Starch	Dodeceny succinic anhydride [323].
Starch	Isocyanate [324, 325].
Starch	Polymer Isocyanate [326].
Starch	Silica nanoparticles [213].
Starch	Vinyltriisopropoxysilane [327].
Starch-based	Prea–formaldehyde, melamine–formaldehyde, and resorcinol–formaldehyde precondensates, poly(vinyl alcohol), and poly(vinyl acetate) [59].
Sucrose, dimethyl carbonate and hexamethylene diamine	Silane coupling agent [219].
Sweet soroghum bagasse	Citric acid [328, 329].
Sweet soroghum bagasse	Citric acid and sucrose [330].
Tannin	Furfuryl alcohol-glyoxal and epoxy resins [331].
Tannin	Hyperbranched poly (amine-ester) [241].
Tannin	Impregnation of natural nonwoven fibre [230].
Tannin	Polyethylenimine [235].
Tannin and urea	Phenol formaldehyde [237].
Tannin-furfuryl alcohol	Polyethyleneimine [240].

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Bio-based adhesive	Water-resistance enhancer
Vegetable proteins	Poly(vinyl acetate) or poly(vinyl alcohol) [332].
Waste protein	Polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin [333].
Water washed cottonseed meal	Tung oil [334].
Water-washed cottonseed meal	Vinavil 2259 L [335].
Wheat flour	Hydroxymethyl melamine prepolymer [336].
Wheat gluten	Avoid over penetration into the wood [337].
Whey protein	Phenol formaldehyde oligomers [338].

A.1.3 Usage of catalyst

Catalysts are generally used with wood adhesives to reduce the curing temperature, pressure, time and increase the mechanical and physical properties. Hydrolysis or condensation reactions may be controlled by using acidic or basic catalysts [339]. Aluminium salt such as $AlCl_3$ or HCl was used as an acid catalyst in PVAc based wood adhesives to improve moisture and water stability [340]. Some of the catalysts used with bio-based adhesive formulations are mentioned in Table A.3.

Table A.3: Usage of catalyst on bio-based wood adhesives.

Bio-based adhesive formulation	The catalyst	Catalyst used for
Bagasse lignin phenol formaldehyde	10% NaOH	Increase bonding strength [341].
Castor oil (CO) based polyol with partially biobased polyisocyanate	Dibutyltin dilaurate	Higher adhesive strength and thermal stability [342].
Condensed tannins	Na ₂ CO ₃	High internal bond strength [343].
Cornstarch and poly(vinyl alcohol) with hexamethoxymethylmelamine (Cymel 323)	Citric acid	Excellent mechanical properties [272].
Epoxidised sunflower oil	Hydrogen peroxide and acetic acid	Epoxidation followed by higher adhesive strength [344].
Furfuryl alcohol and Spent liquor	Sulfuric acid	Make longer the pot-life [66].
Furfuryl alcohol and Tannin	Sulfuric acid	Cure rapidly [66].
Isolated lignin	Acid catalysed organosolv treatment	Higher bond strength [345].
Kraft lignins	Acid-catalysis of a dispersion of hydroxymethylation	Higher water-resistance [346].
Kraft lignins	With H ₂ O ₂ using Co(salen)	Oxydation of lignin followed by more OH to react with wood [347].
Kraft lignins phenol formaldehyde	NaOH	Increase adhesive strength and decreases gel time [348].

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Bio-based adhesive formulation	The catalyst	Catalyst used for
Larch barks phenolated	Sulfuric acid	Increase storage life and decrease formaldehyde emission [349].
Lignin	Polymerisation catalysed by polyphenoloxidases (laccases) or peroxidases	Graft polymerisation onto the lignin backbone followed by increase in adhesive strength [350].
Lignin and phenol	NaOH	Copolymerisation to produce a lignin-phenol-formaldehyde copolymer that leads to increase in adhesive strength [253, 351, 121].
Liquefied banana pseudo stem	Sulfuric acid	Epoxidation followed by higher adhesive strength [352].
Liquefied beech wood sawdust	Sulfuric acid	Better thermal stability [353].
Liquefied biopolyol	Sulfuric acid	Good adhesion strength [354].
Liquefied grapevine cane (<i>Vitis vinisera</i> L.)	Sulfuric acid	Increase in combined phenol percentage that leads to increase in adhesive strength [355].
Liquefied Sugi <i>Criptmeria Japonica</i> wood meal with poly(ethylene glycol) 400 and glycerin	sulfuric acid	Increase in hydroxyl value and bond durability [356].
Organosolv lignin	50/50 (v/v) water–ethanol and pure ethanol media under sub/supercritical condition in hydrogen atmosphere	Increase in dry and wet strength [357].

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Bio-based adhesive formulation	The catalyst	Catalyst used for
Organosolv lignins obtained from sugar maple bark	Lewis acid FeCl ₃	Increase adhesive strength [358].
Palm oil-based polyester polyol	Dibutyltin dilaurate	Increase chemical and thermal resistance [359].
Phenolated Larch Bark	Sulfuric acid, phosphoric acid	Increase in storage life [349].
Phenol–furfural–glucose	NaOH	Reduce curing temperature [360].
Polyflavonoid Tannins	Dissolving finely divided SiO ₂	Strength performance [361].
Softwood kraft lignin	Base-catalysed degradation (prepared by dissolving 7.50 wt % lignin in 3.75 wt % sodium hydroxide solution)	Achieve similar strength to PF [362].
Stalk lignin (glyozalated)	Sodium hydroxide solution	Improve mechanical strength and water-resistance of plywood [363].
Tannin	Lignocellulosic substrate or by a weak Lewis acid as alkali dissolved silica	Increase internal bond strength [364].
Tannin-sucrose	Citric acid	Reduce reaction temperature [365].
Tannin-sucrose	Sulfuric acid	Accelerate the reaction rate of the curing process and to reduce the curing temperature [366].

A.2 Conclusion and future work

In general, additives or cross-linkers are incorporated to enhance the mechanical and physical properties of particleboards. The additive pMDI showed to be able to enhance physical and mechanical properties of particleboards made from urea-glyoxal synthetic resin [367].

When bio-adhesives are being used in the wood adhesive industry, it is crucial to achieve products that meet industrial standards. Generally, bio-adhesives alone do not satisfy industrial standards especially when physical properties are taken into consideration. The incorporation of additives or cross-linkers is widely used in industries to overcome this issue. Some additives work as a catalyst by reducing curing temperature, curing time and applied press giving additional cost-benefit for the industries. The above databases can be further developed and used for industries and research to improve the mechanical and physical properties of bio-adhesive resins. A crucial factor when selecting the additive or additives is that they should not increase the formaldehyde emission of the final wood assembly.

Appendix B

Chemical structures

Figure B.1: Urea formaldehyde resin structure

Figure B.2: Phenol formaldehyde resin structure

Figure B.3: Melamine formaldehyde resin structure

Figure B.4: Melamine urea formaldehyde resin structure

Appendix C

Tables

Table C.1: Sodium alginate and bentonite system (System 1)

Sodium alginate and bentonite system (System 1)												
Particleboard number	11			12			13			14		
Dry contents (w/w)	70% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			60% (wt.) of virgin wood particles		
	20% (wt.) of sodium alginate			20% (wt.) of sodium alginate			25% (wt.) of sodium alginate			25% (wt.) of sodium alginate		
	10% (wt.) of bentonite			15% (wt.) of bentonite			10% (wt.) of bentonite			15% (wt.) of bentonite		
Sample number	111	112	113	121	122	123	131	132	133	141	142	143
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	50.70	49.52	49.48	49.87	49.99	50.38	50.70	50.47	49.72	50.70	49.72	50.23
Thickness (mm)	10.80	9.96	10.33	9.61	9.70	9.48	9.73	9.68	9.67	9.64	9.87	9.98
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	121.40	108.86	112.54	111.98	105.50	102.54	121.66	124.69	123.77	132.01	130.84	138.23
MOR (MPa)	4.62	4.99	4.80	5.47	5.05	5.10	5.70	5.93	5.99	6.30	6.08	6.22
Average MOR (MPa)	4.80	± 0.11	5.20	± 0.13	5.88	± 0.09	6.20	± 0.07	6.20	± 0.07	6.20	± 0.07
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	12.14	10.89	11.25	11.20	10.55	10.25	12.17	12.47	12.38	13.20	13.08	13.82
P2 (40% of F load)	48.56	43.54	45.02	44.79	42.20	41.02	48.66	49.88	49.51	52.80	52.34	55.29
P1 value	23.50	10.88	11.25	11.21	10.56	10.24	12.17	12.47	12.37	13.19	13.08	13.82
P2 value	94.30	43.55	45.01	44.80	42.19	41.02	48.67	49.89	49.50	52.81	52.33	55.30
d1 value	1.53	1.61	1.56	1.23	1.30	1.27	1.43	1.46	1.48	1.14	1.16	1.15
d2 value	2.49	2.30	2.21	1.75	1.77	1.74	2.08	2.14	2.15	1.60	1.64	1.61
MOE (MPa)	974.31	816.50	803.47	1231.43	1244.56	1287.36	1018.09	1014.26	1040.05	1600.04	1443.21	1523.84
Average MOE (MPa)	864.76	± 54.90	1254.45	± 16.89	1024.13	± 8.03	1522.36	± 45.28	1522.36	± 45.28	1522.36	± 45.28
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	49.43	50.44	49.47	50.34	50.24	49.70	49.98	50.41	50.32	50.24	50.05	50.44
Width (mm)	50.21	50.02	49.97	50.01	49.57	50.10	50.21	49.70	49.99	50.21	49.47	49.76
Thickness (mm)	10.75	10.10	10.24	9.68	9.72	9.43	9.70	9.67	9.69	9.66	9.78	10.00
weight (g)	18.75	17.97	17.74	18.10	18.00	17.64	17.50	17.47	17.50	18.69	18.21	18.83
Density (kg/m³)	702.77	705.19	700.81	742.73	743.60	751.26	718.92	721.10	717.94	766.99	752.01	750.23
Average density (kg/m³)	702.92	± 1.27	745.87	± 2.71	719.32	± 0.93	756.41	± 5.32	756.41	± 5.32	756.41	± 5.32
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	289.00	291.00	299.00	333.86	332.00	320.80	302.50	307.50	306.70	339.00	342.80	334.60
Internal bond - IB (MPa)	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.13
Average IB (MPa)	0.12	± 0.00	0.13	± 0.00	0.12	± 0.00	0.12	± 0.00	0.12	0.14	± 0.00	0.13
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	18.70	18.60	17.67	18.46	18.72	18.91	17.85	18.03	18.61	18.67	18.55	17.73
Mass after dry (g)	16.46	16.00	15.65	16.01	16.23	16.32	15.00	15.34	15.60	15.11	15.07	14.50
Moisture content - MC (%)	13.61%	16.25%	12.91%	15.30%	15.34%	15.87%	19.00%	17.54%	19.29%	23.56%	23.09%	22.28%
Average MC (%)	14.26%	± 1.02%	15.50%	± 0.18%	18.61%	± 0.54%	22.98%	± 0.38%	22.98%	± 0.38%	22.98%	± 0.38%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	10.74	9.95	10.32	9.62	9.69	9.50	9.75	9.67	9.68	9.65	9.88	9.99
Thickness after (mm)	13.13	12.00	12.50	12.14	12.32	12.15	11.96	11.92	11.89	12.51	12.81	12.90
Thickness swelling - TS (%)	22.25%	20.60%	21.12%	26.20%	27.14%	27.89%	22.67%	23.27%	22.83%	29.64%	29.66%	29.13%
Average TS (%)	21.33%	± 0.49%	27.08%	± 0.49%	22.92%	± 0.18%	29.47%	± 0.17%	29.47%	± 0.17%	29.47%	± 0.17%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.2: Alkali-treated wheat gluten cross-linked with sodium alginate and bentonite system (System 2)

Alkali-treated wheat gluten cross-linked with sodium alginate and bentonite system (System 2)												
Particleboard number	21			22			23			24		
Dry contents (w/w)	65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles		
	15% (wt.) of sodium alginate			10% (wt.) of sodium alginate			20% (wt.) of sodium alginate			10% (wt.) of sodium alginate		
	10% (wt.) of wheat gluten			15% (wt.) of wheat gluten			10% (wt.) of wheat gluten			20% (wt.) of wheat gluten		
	10% (wt.) of bentonite			10% (wt.) of bentonite			5% (wt.) of bentonite			5% (wt.) of bentonite		
Sample number	211	212	213	221	222	223	231	232	233	241	242	243
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	49.50	50.18	49.73	49.90	49.93	49.92	50.32	50.24	50.21	49.32	49.36	49.34
Thickness (mm)	10.07	10.08	10.10	9.89	9.90	9.89	10.04	10.03	10.02	10.04	10.05	10.04
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	135.32	137.11	137.36	145.00	143.60	144.32	139.54	139.86	139.73	155.89	155.12	155.25
MOR (MPa)	6.07	6.05	6.09	6.68	6.60	6.65	6.19	6.23	6.24	7.06	7.00	7.02
Average MOR (MPa)	6.07	±	0.01	6.65	±	0.02	6.22	±	0.01	7.03	±	0.02
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	13.53	13.71	13.74	14.50	14.36	14.43	13.95	13.99	13.97	15.59	15.51	15.53
P2 (40% of F load)	54.13	54.84	54.94	58.00	57.44	57.73	55.82	55.94	55.89	62.36	62.05	62.10
P1 value	13.54	13.72	13.73	14.50	14.38	14.43	13.94	13.98	13.97	15.59	15.50	15.52
P2 value	54.10	54.83	54.95	58.20	57.42	57.72	55.81	55.96	55.90	62.35	62.00	62.12
d1 value	1.45	1.42	1.53	1.44	1.37	1.74	1.65	1.58	1.54	1.44	1.47	1.49
d2 value	2.10	2.05	2.19	1.98	1.90	2.28	2.28	2.21	2.17	1.90	1.91	1.93
MOE (MPa)	1041.61	1071.29	1028.48	1414.53	1414.30	1400.63	1101.12	1109.08	1111.74	1718.33	1779.68	1789.56
Average MOE (MPa)	1047.13	±	12.66	1409.82	±	4.60	1107.31	±	3.19	1762.52	±	22.28
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	50.12	50.02	49.29	50.18	50.06	49.82	49.94	50.11	50.54	50.83	49.21	49.57
Width (mm)	49.56	50.17	49.71	49.90	49.92	49.91	50.21	50.24	50.23	49.33	49.35	49.31
Thickness (mm)	10.08	10.07	10.10	9.90	9.89	9.89	10.03	10.04	10.02	10.03	10.02	10.04
weight (g)	18.12	18.42	18.11	18.00	17.90	17.89	18.02	17.93	17.79	17.68	17.23	17.15
Density (kg/m³)	723.69	728.91	731.80	726.12	724.25	727.48	716.50	709.37	699.37	702.99	708.07	698.84
Average density (kg/m³)	728.14	±	2.37	725.95	±	0.94	708.41	±	4.97	703.30	±	2.67
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	321.68	324.51	322.36	355.54	358.98	361.53	325.87	326.44	337.41	366.00	369.64	371.32
IB (MPa)	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.15	0.15	0.15
Average IB (MPa)	0.13	±	0.00	0.14	±	0.00	0.13	±	0.00	0.15	±	0.00
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	20.03	20.61	22.51	23.50	22.50	22.45	21.00	21.21	22.50	22.01	22.02	22.40
Mass after dry (g)	17.40	17.93	19.63	20.61	19.73	19.63	18.59	18.67	19.76	19.73	19.63	19.77
Moisture content (%)	15.11%	14.95%	14.67%	14.02%	14.04%	14.37%	12.96%	13.60%	13.87%	11.56%	12.18%	13.30%
Average MC (%)	14.91%	±	0.13%	14.14%	±	0.11%	13.48%	±	0.27%	12.34%	±	0.51%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	10.07	10.06	10.08	9.91	9.90	9.89	10.04	10.03	10.02	10.03	10.03	10.02
Thickness after (mm)	12.05	12.10	12.12	11.80	11.70	11.98	11.59	11.61	11.66	11.40	11.43	11.41
Thickness swelling (%)	19.66%	20.28%	20.24%	19.07%	18.18%	21.13%	15.44%	15.75%	16.37%	13.66%	13.96%	13.87%
Average TS (%)	20.06%	±	0.20%	19.46%	±	0.87%	15.85%	±	0.27%	13.83%	±	0.09%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.3: Alkali-treated wheat gluten cross-linked with sodium alginate system (System 3)

Alkali-treated wheat gluten cross-linked with sodium alginate system (System 3)												
Particleboard number	31			32			33			34		
Dry contents (w/w)	65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles		
	20% (wt.) of wheat gluten			25% (wt.) of wheat gluten			30% (wt.) of wheat gluten			35% (wt.) of wheat gluten		
	15% (wt.) of sodium alginate			10% (wt.) of sodium alginate			5% (wt.) of sodium alginate			0% (wt.) of sodium alginate		
Sample number	311	312	313	321	322	323	331	332	333	341	342	343
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	49.80	50.1	49.82	49.75	50.14	50.18	49.03	49.34	50.06	49.58	49.72	49.84
Thickness (mm)	10.04	10.1	9.87	9.89	9.93	10.06	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.00	9.99	9.92
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	162.00	165.83	154.52	170.02	171.20	173.78	180.00	178.00	175.50	165.00	165.89	164.98
MOR (MPa)	7.26	7.30	7.16	7.86	7.79	7.70	8.10	8.33	7.81	7.49	7.52	7.57
Average MOR (MPa)	7.24	±	0.04	7.78	±	0.05	8.08	±	0.15	7.53	±	0.02
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	16.20	16.58	15.45	17.00	17.12	17.38	18.00	17.80	17.55	16.50	16.59	16.50
P2 (40% of F load)	64.80	66.33	61.81	68.01	68.48	69.51	72.00	71.20	70.20	66.00	66.36	65.99
P1 value	16.21	16.57	15.45	17.02	17.12	17.37	18.02	17.81	17.54	16.50	16.58	16.49
P2 value	64.82	66.33	61.80	68.00	68.46	69.50	72.01	71.22	70.21	66.02	66.35	66.00
d1 value	1.48	1.42	1.45	1.54	1.53	1.52	1.44	1.45	1.42	1.42	1.46	1.43
d2 value	1.92	1.87	1.88	2.00	2.00	1.97	1.88	1.90	1.84	1.87	1.91	1.90
MOE (MPa)	1849.51	1807.58	1898.55	1943.00	1877.33	1913.22	2049.50	2110.93	2082.28	1872.73	1882.53	1826.82
Average MOE (MPa)	1851.88	±	26.29	1911.18	±	18.99	2080.90	±	17.75	1860.69	±	17.17
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	49.99	49.97	49.98	50.02	50.01	50.00	49.93	49.97	50.05	49.89	50.03	50.04
Width (mm)	49.80	50.1	49.82	49.75	50.14	50.18	49.03	49.34	50.06	49.58	49.72	49.84
Thickness (mm)	10.04	10.1	9.87	9.89	9.93	10.06	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.00	9.99	9.92
weight (g)	18.00	18.02	17.98	17.94	18.02	18.22	18.01	17.93	18.43	18.03	18.21	18.21
Density (kg/m³)	720.16	712.67	731.60	728.94	723.71	721.85	728.40	736.81	731.92	728.91	732.80	736.04
Average density (kg/m³)	721.47	±	5.50	724.83	±	2.12	732.38	±	2.44	732.58	±	2.06
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	365.89	364.35	367.76	478.88	487.53	491.03	1275.54	1284.90	1292.76	777.50	768.43	770.43
IB (MPa)	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.19	0.19	0.20	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.31	0.31	0.31
Average IB (MPa)	0.15	±	0.00	0.19	±	0.00	0.52	±	0.00	0.31	±	0.00
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	19.80	21.01	20.41	19.77	20.10	19.78	19.78	19.93	19.35	19.88	19.90	19.95
Mass after dry (g)	17.86	19.00	18.42	17.95	18.30	17.83	18.23	18.44	17.73	18.34	18.58	18.45
Moisture content (%)	10.86%	10.58%	10.80%	10.14%	9.84%	10.94%	8.50%	8.08%	9.14%	8.40%	7.10%	8.13%
Average MC (%)	10.75%	±	0.09%	10.30%	±	0.33%	8.57%	±	0.31%	7.88%	±	0.39%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	10.04	10.10	9.87	9.89	9.93	10.06	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.00	9.99	9.92
Thickness after (mm)	11.30	11.40	11.20	11.21	11.23	11.37	11.27	11.16	11.22	11.21	11.22	11.16
Thickness swelling (%)	12.55%	12.87%	13.48%	13.35%	13.09%	13.02%	11.58%	13.07%	11.64%	12.10%	12.31%	12.50%
Average TS (%)	12.97%	±	0.27%	13.15%	±	0.10%	12.10%	±	0.49%	12.30%	±	0.12%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.4: Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with recycled wood particles (System 4)

Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with recycled wood particles (System 4)												
Particleboard number	41			42			43			44		
Dry contents (w/w)	65% (wt.) of Type A wood particles			65% (wt.) of Type B wood particles			65% (wt.) of Type C wood particles			65% (wt.) of Type D wood particles		
	35% (wt.) of the binder			35% (wt.) of the binder			35% (wt.) of the binder			35% (wt.) of the binder		
Sample number	411	412	413	421	422	423	431	432	433	441	442	443
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	50.12	50.17	49.78	50.03	50.11	49.96	49.67	50.31	49.82	49.27	50.07	50.14
Thickness (mm)	11.02	10.95	10.97	10.23	10.22	10.12	9.67	9.87	10.19	10.14	10.16	9.95
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	244.54	242.12	240.87	150.54	151.78	154.33	376.45	392.70	414.00	178.03	174.89	172.94
MOR (MPa)	9.04	9.06	9.05	6.47	6.52	6.79	18.24	18.03	18.01	7.91	7.61	7.84
Average MOR (MPa)	9.05	±	0.00	6.59	±	0.10	18.09	±	0.07	7.79	±	0.09
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	24.45	24.21	24.09	15.05	15.18	15.43	37.65	39.27	41.40	17.80	17.49	17.29
P2 (40% of F load)	97.82	96.85	96.35	60.22	60.71	61.73	150.58	157.08	165.60	71.21	69.96	69.18
P1 value	24.46	24.22	24.08	15.05	15.17	15.43	37.64	39.29	41.42	17.80	17.48	17.29
P2 value	97.81	96.82	96.34	60.21	60.72	61.74	150.58	157.09	165.61	71.22	69.95	69.17
d1 value	1.52	1.57	1.87	1.70	1.68	1.66	1.38	2.18	2.10	1.68	1.74	1.73
d2 value	1.93	2.01	2.31	1.96	1.95	1.93	2.03	2.82	2.73	1.94	1.98	1.99
MOE (MPa)	2250.48	2113.54	2108.55	2736.13	2661.10	2794.87	3264.18	3210.50	3155.25	3374.80	3512.81	3408.68
Average MOE (MPa)	2157.52	±	46.50	2730.70	±	38.71	3209.98	±	31.45	3432.10	±	41.53
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	50.01	50.03	49.95	49.91	50.00	50.02	50.02	49.97	49.96	50.02	49.94	49.99
Width (mm)	50.12	50.17	49.78	50.03	50.11	49.96	49.67	50.31	49.82	49.27	50.07	50.14
Thickness (mm)	11.02	10.95	10.97	10.23	10.22	10.12	9.67	9.87	10.19	10.14	10.16	9.95
weight (g)	22.00	21.54	21.79	22.40	22.31	22.22	22.00	22.45	23.51	25.05	25.12	25.12
Density (kg/m³)	796.48	783.71	798.84	876.91	871.27	878.61	915.71	904.76	926.94	1002.41	988.78	1007.23
Average density (kg/m³)	793.01	±	4.70	875.60	±	2.22	915.81	±	6.40	999.47	±	5.52
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	1543.00	1526.60	1553.25	1834.00	1856.00	1886.50	3255.00	3189.00	3212.00	2101.00	2095.00	2079.00
IB (MPa)	0.62	0.61	0.62	0.73	0.74	0.75	1.31	1.27	1.29	0.85	0.84	0.83
Average IB (MPa)	0.62	±	0.00	0.74	±	0.01	1.29	±	0.01	0.84	±	0.01
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	20.31	19.80	20.40	21.20	21.75	22.00	21.65	21.00	20.73	21.90	22.80	22.64
Mass after dry (g)	18.35	17.89	18.45	18.43	19.02	19.67	19.36	18.88	18.49	19.02	19.87	19.59
Moisture content (%)	10.68%	10.68%	10.57%	15.03%	14.35%	11.85%	11.83%	11.23%	12.11%	15.14%	14.75%	15.57%
Average MC (%)	10.64%	±	0.04%	13.74%	±	0.97%	11.72%	±	0.26%	15.15%	±	0.24%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	11.02	10.95	10.97	10.23	10.22	10.12	9.67	9.87	10.19	10.14	10.16	9.95
Thickness after (mm)	12.25	12.31	12.33	11.75	11.80	11.69	10.58	10.65	11.20	11.50	11.50	11.31
Thickness swelling (%)	11.16%	12.42%	12.40%	14.86%	15.46%	15.51%	9.41%	7.90%	9.91%	13.41%	13.19%	13.67%
Average TS (%)	11.99%	±	0.42%	15.28%	±	0.21%	9.07%	±	0.60%	13.42%	±	0.14%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.5: Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 5 - virgin wood particles)

Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 5 - virgin wood particles)												
Particleboard number	51			52			53			54		
Additive used	Control sample			SDS			Sodium sulfate			Polythyleneimine		
Sample number	511	512	513	521	522	523	531	532	533	541	542	543
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	49.03	49.34	50.06	49.78	49.96	50.21	50.20	59.06	50.02	50.24	49.96	50.02
Thickness (mm)	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.20	10.18	10.14	9.87	9.81	9.83	10.11	10.11	9.99
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	180.00	178.00	175.50	275.00	276.00	275.67	161.00	190.00	160.00	328.67	325.00	321.00
MOR (MPa)	8.10	8.33	7.81	11.95	11.99	12.01	7.41	7.52	7.45	14.40	14.32	14.47
Average MOR (MPa)	8.08	±	0.15	11.99	±	0.02	7.46	±	0.03	14.40	±	0.04
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	18.00	17.80	17.55	27.50	27.60	27.57	16.10	19.00	16.00	32.87	32.50	32.10
P2 (40% of F load)	72.00	71.20	70.20	110.00	110.40	110.27	64.40	76.00	64.00	131.47	130.00	128.40
P1 value	18.02	17.81	17.54	27.52	27.63	27.61	16.11	19.10	16.07	32.80	32.50	32.20
P2 value	72.01	71.22	70.21	110.00	110.40	110.27	64.41	76.01	64.03	131.46	130.02	128.41
d1 value	1.44	1.45	1.42	1.46	1.42	1.37	1.37	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.29
d2 value	1.88	1.90	1.84	1.98	1.96	1.89	1.78	1.77	1.76	1.89	1.88	1.86
MOE (MPa)	2049.50	2110.93	2082.28	2533.40	2453.73	2562.07	2059.31	2002.78	1980.71	2863.28	2871.70	2855.74
Average MOE (MPa)	2080.90	±	17.75	2516.40	±	32.41	2014.27	±	23.41	2863.57	±	4.61
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	49.93	49.97	50.05	49.90	50.01	50.00	50.01	49.99	49.98	50.01	49.96	50.00
Width (mm)	49.03	49.34	50.06	49.78	49.96	50.21	50.20	50.06	50.02	50.24	49.96	50.02
Thickness (mm)	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.2	10.18	10.14	9.87	9.81	9.83	10.11	10.11	9.99
weight (g)	18.01	17.93	18.43	19.40	19.44	19.47	18.42	18.00	18.00	19.20	19.00	19.00
Density (kg/m³)	728.40	736.81	731.92	765.68	764.31	764.84	743.38	733.21	732.45	755.86	752.94	760.46
Average density (kg/m³)	732.38	±	2.44	764.94	±	0.40	736.35	±	3.52	756.42	±	2.19
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	1275.54	1284.90	1292.76	2800.00	2865.00	2867.00	1134.00	1131.00	1129.00	3650.00	3700.00	3700.00
IB (MPa)	0.52	0.52	0.52	1.13	1.15	1.14	0.45	0.45	0.45	1.45	1.48	1.48
Average IB (MPa)	0.52	±	0.00	1.14	±	0.01	0.45	±	0.00	1.47	±	0.01
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	19.78	19.93	19.35	20.00	20.00	20.50	21.00	21.00	20.00	21.00	22.00	21.50
Mass after dry (g)	18.23	18.44	17.73	18.43	19.02	19.00	19.36	18.88	18.49	19.02	19.87	19.59
Moisture content (%)	8.50%	8.08%	9.14%	8.52%	5.15%	7.89%	8.47%	11.23%	8.17%	10.41%	10.72%	9.75%
Average MC (%)	8.57%	±	0.31%	7.19%	±	1.03%	9.29%	±	0.97%	10.29%	±	0.29%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.23	10.22	10.12	9.67	9.87	10.19	10.14	10.16	9.95
Thickness after (mm)	11.27	11.16	11.22	11.20	11.10	11.10	11.00	11.00	11.50	11.20	11.20	10.70
Thickness swelling (%)	11.58%	13.07%	11.64%	9.48%	8.61%	9.68%	13.75%	11.45%	12.86%	10.45%	10.24%	7.54%
Average TS (%)	12.10%	±	0.49%	9.26%	±	0.33%	12.69%	±	0.67%	9.41%	±	0.94%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.6: Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 5 - virgin wood particles)

Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 5 - virgin wood particles)												
Particleboard number	55			56			57			58		
Additive used	Glyoxal			Sodium phosphate			Diacetin			Tannin		
Sample number	551	552	553	561	562	563	571	572	573	581	582	583
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	50.10	50.15	50.03	49.97	49.92	50.00	49.60	50.03	50.02	50.02	50.00	50.11
Thickness (mm)	10.02	10.01	10.02	9.97	9.98	9.95	9.96	9.98	10.01	10.10	10.12	10.02
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	255.00	246.00	245.76	214.00	217.50	217.00	236.00	239.00	244.54	198.54	189.50	189.00
MOR (MPa)	11.40	11.01	11.01	9.69	9.84	9.86	10.79	10.79	10.98	8.75	8.33	8.45
Average MOR (MPa)	11.14	±	0.13	9.80	±	0.05	10.85	±	0.06	8.51	±	0.13
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	25.50	24.60	24.58	21.40	21.75	21.70	23.60	23.90	24.45	19.85	18.95	18.90
P2 (40% of F load)	102.00	98.40	98.30	85.60	87.00	86.80	94.40	95.60	97.82	79.42	75.80	75.60
P1 value	25.48	24.60	24.57	21.40	21.76	21.70	23.61	23.95	24.46	19.86	18.93	18.90
P2 value	102.00	98.39	98.30	85.60	87.00	86.80	94.40	95.60	97.82	79.41	75.80	75.62
d1 value	1.45	1.41	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.36	1.35	1.36	1.53	1.56	1.54
d2 value	1.98	1.97	1.89	1.87	1.89	1.87	1.88	1.87	1.89	2.01	2.02	2.01
MOE (MPa)	2416.25	2208.97	2538.16	2327.32	2263.94	2388.02	2334.83	2337.78	2327.70	2031.17	1997.73	2019.88
Average MOE (MPa)	2387.79	±	96.09	2326.43	±	35.82	2333.44	±	2.99	2016.26	±	9.82
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	50.00	50.01	50.03	50.04	50.04	50.03	49.99	49.98	49.97	50.00	49.97	49.98
Width (mm)	50.10	50.15	50.03	49.97	49.92	50.00	49.60	50.03	50.02	50.02	50.00	50.11
Thickness (mm)	10.02	10.01	10.02	9.97	9.98	9.95	9.96	9.98	10.01	10.10	10.12	10.02
weight (g)	19.00	19.00	19.25	19.50	19.30	19.20	19.60	19.40	19.45	19.35	19.30	19.30
Density (kg/m³)	756.89	756.67	767.54	782.19	774.17	771.40	793.66	777.40	777.38	766.03	763.30	769.08
Average density (kg/m³)	760.37	±	3.59	775.92	±	3.24	782.81	±	5.42	766.14	±	1.67
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	1543.00	1526.60	1553.25	1834.00	1856.00	1886.50	3255.00	3189.00	3212.00	2101.00	2095.00	2079.00
IB (MPa)	0.62	0.61	0.62	0.73	0.74	0.75	1.31	1.28	1.29	0.84	0.84	0.83
Average IB (MPa)	0.62	±	0.00	0.74	±	0.01	1.29	±	0.01	0.84	±	0.00
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.70	20.00	21.00	20.00	21.00	21.00	20.60
Mass after dry (g)	18.30	18.40	18.45	18.43	18.45	18.60	18.60	18.90	18.54	19.00	19.70	18.53
Moisture content (%)	9.29%	8.70%	8.40%	8.52%	8.40%	11.29%	7.53%	11.11%	7.87%	10.53%	6.60%	11.17%
Average MC (%)	8.80%	±	0.26%	9.40%	±	0.94%	8.84%	±	1.14%	9.43%	±	1.43%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	10.02	10.012	10.02	9.97	9.98	9.95	9.96	9.98	10.01	10.10	10.12	10.02
Thickness after (mm)	11.30	11.30	11.30	11.00	11.00	11.30	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.20	11.50	11.31
Thickness swelling (%)	12.76%	12.86%	12.77%	10.33%	10.22%	13.57%	10.44%	10.22%	9.89%	10.89%	13.64%	12.87%
Average TS (%)	12.80%	±	0.03%	11.37%	±	1.10%	10.18%	±	0.16%	12.47%	±	0.82%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.7: Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 6 - recycled wood particles)

Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 6 - recycled wood particles)												
Particleboard number	61			62			63			64		
Additive used	Control sample			SDS			Sodium sulfate			Polythyleneimine		
Sample number	611	612	613	621	622	623	631	632	633	641	642	643
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	49.67	50.31	49.82	49.94	50.01	50	49.88	49.21	50.1	50.11	50	50.11
Thickness (mm)	9.67	9.87	10.19	10.2	9.99	10	10.21	10.22	9.89	10.10	10.2	9.91
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	376.45	392.70	414.00	521.00	509.32	504.35	379.45	389.00	360.00	600.00	601.00	600.00
MOR (MPa)	18.24	18.03	18.01	22.56	22.96	22.70	16.42	17.03	16.53	26.41	25.99	27.43
Average MOR (MPa)	18.09	±	0.07	22.74	±	0.12	16.66	±	0.19	26.61	±	0.43
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	37.65	39.27	41.40	52.10	50.93	50.44	37.95	38.90	36.00	60.00	60.10	60.00
P2 (40% of F load)	150.58	157.08	165.60	208.40	203.73	201.74	151.78	155.60	144.00	240.00	240.40	240.00
P1 value	37.64	39.29	41.42	52.11	50.90	50.43	37.94	38.90	36.04	60.05	60.12	60.05
P2 value	150.58	157.09	165.61	208.42	203.72	201.70	151.76	155.63	144.03	240.53	240.43	240.33
d1 value	1.38	2.18	2.10	1.70	1.55	1.47	1.40	1.55	1.61	1.30	1.30	1.28
d2 value	2.03	2.82	2.73	2.32	2.20	2.12	2.00	2.13	2.22	2.01	2.00	2.03
MOE (MPa)	3264.18	3210.50	3155.25	4013.84	3978.57	3939.32	3014.93	3207.79	3082.06	4154.28	4096.05	4132.23
Average MOE (MPa)	3209.98	±	31.45	3977.24	±	21.52	3101.59	±	56.52	4127.52	±	16.97
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	50.02	49.97	49.96	49.91	50.00	50.02	50.02	49.97	49.96	50.02	49.94	49.99
Width (mm)	49.67	50.31	49.82	49.94	50.01	50	49.88	49.21	50.1	50.11	50	50.11
Thickness (mm)	9.67	9.87	10.19	10.2	9.99	10	10.21	10.22	9.89	10.10	10.2	9.91
Weight (g)	22.00	22.45	23.51	23.50	22.90	23.50	24.00	23.10	23.51	23.60	23.45	23.00
Density (kg/m³)	915.71	904.76	926.94	924.34	916.73	939.62	942.14	919.18	949.72	932.23	920.71	926.50
Average density (kg/m³)	915.81	±	6.40	926.90	±	6.73	937.01	±	9.18	926.48	±	3.32
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	3255.00	3189.00	3212.00	3767.00	3756.00	3789.00	3198.00	3080.00	3225.00	5312.00	5343.00	5323.00
IB (MPa)	1.31	1.27	1.29	1.51	1.50	1.51	1.28	1.25	1.29	2.12	2.14	2.12
Average IB (MPa)	1.29	±	0.01	1.51	±	0.00	1.27	±	0.01	2.13	±	0.01
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	21.65	21.00	20.73	21.20	20.70	20.90	22.00	22.02	22.01	20.40	20.36	20.00
Mass after dry (g)	19.36	18.88	18.49	19.23	19.00	19.12	19.42	19.45	19.41	18.33	18.11	18.31
Moisture content (%)	11.83%	11.23%	12.11%	10.24%	8.95%	9.31%	13.29%	13.21%	13.40%	11.29%	12.42%	9.23%
Average MC (%)	11.72%	±	0.26%	9.50%	±	0.39%	13.30%	±	0.05%	10.98%	±	0.94%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	9.67	9.87	10.19	10.2	9.99	10	10.21	10.22	9.89	10.10	10.2	9.91
Thickness after (mm)	10.58	10.65	11.20	10.70	10.50	10.40	11.10	11.00	11.00	10.80	10.90	10.70
Thickness swelling (%)	9.41%	7.90%	9.91%	4.90%	5.11%	4.00%	8.72%	7.63%	11.22%	6.93%	6.86%	7.97%
Average TS (%)	9.07%	±	0.60%	4.67%	±	0.34%	9.19%	±	1.06%	7.26%	±	0.36%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.8: Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 6 - recycled wood particles)

Alkali-treated wheat gluten (30%) cross-linked with sodium alginate (5%) binder with additives (System 6 - recycled wood particles)												
Particleboard number	65			66			67			68		
Additive used	Glyoxal			Sodium phosphate			Diacetin			Tannin		
Sample number	651	652	653	661	662	663	671	672	673	681	682	683
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	49.89	49.87	50.14	49.32	49.63	50.03	49.60	50.12	49.94	49.70	50.01	50.11
Thickness (mm)	10.11	10.08	10.09	10.20	10.21	10.12	10.10	10.15	10.19	10.11	10.13	10.10
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	522.00	522.50	523.00	477.00	475.00	478.50	494.00	489.50	490.00	435.00	432.00	441.00
MOR (MPa)	23.03	23.20	23.05	20.92	20.66	21.01	21.97	21.33	21.26	19.27	18.94	19.41
Average MOR (MPa)	23.10	±	0.05	20.86	±	0.11	21.52	±	0.22	19.21	±	0.14
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	52.20	52.25	52.30	47.70	47.50	47.85	49.40	48.95	49.00	43.50	43.20	44.10
P2 (40% of F load)	208.80	209.00	209.20	190.80	190.00	191.40	197.60	195.80	196.00	174.00	172.80	176.40
P1 value	52.21	52.26	52.32	47.71	47.52	47.87	49.43	48.98	49.00	43.53	43.21	44.11
P2 value	208.82	209.04	209.22	190.83	190.06	191.43	197.62	195.84	196.00	174.21	172.80	176.40
d1 value	1.42	1.50	1.40	1.35	1.39	1.34	1.42	1.55	1.44	1.72	1.71	1.71
d2 value	2.12	2.22	2.11	2.01	2.03	2.00	2.13	2.21	2.11	2.41	2.40	2.39
MOE (MPa)	3661.58	3582.16	3620.10	3495.80	3557.53	3539.41	3446.11	3576.90	3503.36	3106.96	3048.25	3179.39
Average MOE (MPa)	3621.28	±	22.93	3530.92	±	18.32	3508.79	±	37.85	3111.53	±	37.92
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	50.01	50.03	49.95	49.91	50.00	50.02	50.02	49.97	49.96	50.02	49.94	49.99
Width (mm)	49.89	49.87	50.14	49.32	49.63	50.03	49.60	50.12	49.94	49.70	50.01	50.11
Thickness (mm)	10.11	10.08	10.09	10.2	10.21	10.12	10.10	10.15	10.19	10.11	10.13	10.1
weight (g)	23.50	23.80	23.60	23.75	24.00	24.00	23.50	23.30	23.60	23.10	23.60	23.40
Density (kg/m³)	931.64	946.34	933.90	945.92	947.26	947.67	937.82	916.58	928.25	919.10	932.82	924.88
Average density (kg/m³)	937.29	±	4.57	946.95	±	0.53	927.55	±	6.14	925.60	±	3.98
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	3761.00	3745.00	3732.00	3372.00	3362.00	3366.00	3999.00	4002.00	4006.00	3777.00	3726.00	3744.00
IB (MPa)	1.51	1.50	1.49	1.37	1.35	1.35	1.61	1.60	1.61	1.52	1.49	1.49
Average IB (MPa)	1.50	±	0.01	1.36	±	0.01	1.61	±	0.00	1.50	±	0.01
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	20.41	20.40	20.42	20.70	21.10	21.20	21.65	21.00	20.73	21.30	21.60	21.64
Mass after dry (g)	18.30	18.00	18.40	18.40	18.67	18.74	18.54	18.52	18.87	19.04	19.11	19.12
Moisture content (%)	11.53%	13.33%	10.98%	12.50%	13.02%	13.13%	16.77%	13.39%	9.86%	11.87%	13.03%	13.18%
Average MC (%)	11.95%	±	0.71%	12.88%	±	0.19%	13.34%	±	2.00%	12.69%	±	0.41%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	10.11	10.08	10.09	10.2	10.21	10.12	10.10	10.15	10.19	10.11	10.13	10.1
Thickness after (mm)	11.25	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.20	11.10	11.20	11.00	11.10	11.00	11.00	11.00
Thickness swelling (%)	11.28%	9.13%	9.02%	7.84%	9.70%	9.68%	10.89%	8.37%	8.93%	8.80%	8.59%	8.91%
Average TS (%)	9.81%	±	0.74%	9.07%	±	0.62%	9.40%	±	0.76%	8.77%	±	0.09%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.9: Mechanical and physical properties of fully bio-based adhesive used re-manufacturing system

Particleboard number	B			B100			B100100			B100100100		
Sample number	331	332	333	811	812	813	821	822	823	831	832	833
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	49.03	49.34	50.06	49.58	49.72	49.84	49.80	50.1	49.82	49.50	50.18	49.73
Thickness (mm)	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.00	9.99	9.92	10.04	10.1	9.87	10.07	10.08	10.10
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	180.00	178.00	175.50	185.00	205.00	206.00	152.00	145.00	142.00	92.50	85.50	78.50
MOR (MPa)	8.10	8.33	7.81	8.40	9.30	9.45	6.81	6.38	6.58	4.15	3.77	3.48
Average MOR (MPa)	8.08	±	0.15	9.05	±	0.33	6.59	±	0.12	3.80	±	0.19
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)												
P1 (10% of F load)	18.00	17.80	17.55	18.50	20.50	20.60	15.20	14.50	14.20	9.25	8.55	7.85
P2 (40% of F load)	72.00	71.20	70.20	74.00	82.00	82.40	60.80	58.00	56.80	37.00	34.20	31.40
P1 value	18.02	17.81	17.54	15.40	15.20	15.49	16.20	16.57	15.45	13.54	13.72	13.73
P2 value	72.01	71.22	70.21	66.02	66.35	66.00	64.82	66.33	61.80	54.10	54.83	54.95
d1 value	1.44	1.45	1.42	1.52	1.56	1.50	1.48	1.42	1.45	1.45	1.42	1.53
d2 value	1.88	1.90	1.84	1.87	1.91	1.90	1.92	1.87	1.88	2.10	2.05	2.19
MOE (MPa)	2049.50	2110.93	2082.28	2461.28	2487.50	2189.87	1849.89	1807.58	1898.55	1041.61	1071.29	1028.48
Average MOE (MPa)	2080.90	±	17.75	2379.55	±	95.14	1852.00	±	26.28	1047.13	±	12.66
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)												
Length (mm)	49.93	49.97	50.05	49.89	50.03	50.04	49.99	49.97	49.98	50.12	50.02	49.29
Width (mm)	49.03	49.34	50.06	49.58	49.72	49.84	49.80	50.1	49.82	49.56	50.17	49.71
Thickness (mm)	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.00	9.99	9.92	10.04	10.1	9.87	10.08	10.07	10.10
weight (g)	18.01	17.93	18.43	19.68	19.62	19.62	21.80	21.80	21.96	22.50	23.00	23.00
Density (kg/m³)	728.40	736.81	731.92	795.62	789.54	793.03	872.19	862.16	893.54	898.63	910.14	929.40
Average density (kg/m³)	732.38	±	2.44	792.73	±	1.76	875.96	±	9.25	912.72	±	8.98
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Failure load (N)	1275.54	1284.90	1292.76	1588.00	1565.00	1497.00	1812.00	1866.00	1845.00	2265.00	2283.00	2222.00
IB (MPa)	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.64	0.63	0.60	0.73	0.75	0.74	0.91	0.91	0.91
Average IB (MPa)	0.52	±	0.00	0.62	±	0.01	0.74	±	0.01	0.91	±	0.00
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)												
Mass before dry (g)	19.78	19.93	19.35	19.88	19.90	19.95	19.80	21.01	20.41	20.03	20.61	22.51
Mass after dry (g)	18.23	18.44	17.73	18.34	18.80	18.45	17.86	18.50	18.42	17.40	17.97	19.63
Moisture content (%)	8.50%	8.08%	9.14%	8.40%	5.85%	8.13%	10.86%	13.57%	10.80%	15.11%	14.69%	14.67%
Average MC (%)	8.57%	±	0.31%	7.46%	±	0.81%	11.74%	±	0.91%	14.83%	±	0.14%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.												
Thickness before (mm)	10.10	9.87	10.05	10.00	9.99	9.92	10.04	10.10	9.87	10.07	10.06	10.08
Thickness after (mm)	11.27	11.16	11.22	11.21	11.22	11.16	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.00	11.00
Thickness swelling (%)	11.58%	13.07%	11.64%	12.10%	12.31%	12.50%	9.56%	8.91%	11.45%	9.24%	9.34%	9.13%
Average TS (%)	12.10%	±	0.49%	12.30%	±	0.12%	9.97%	±	0.76%	9.24%	±	0.06%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.												

Table C.10: Mechanical and physical properties of bio-based and synthetic adhesive used re-manufacturing system

Particleboard number	B50S50			B50S50100			B50S50100100		
Sample number	841	842	843	851	852	853	861	862	863
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	49.75	50.14	50.18	49.90	49.93	49.92	50.32	50.24	50.21
Thickness (mm)	9.89	9.93	10.06	9.89	9.90	9.89	10.04	10.03	10.02
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	265.00	235.00	254.00	155.50	156.00	155.00	104.00	108.50	99.00
MOR (MPa)	12.25	10.69	11.25	7.17	7.17	7.14	4.61	4.83	4.42
Average MOR (MPa)	11.40	±	0.46	7.16	±	0.01	4.62	±	0.12
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)									
P1 (10% of F load)	26.50	23.50	25.40	15.55	15.60	15.50	10.40	10.85	9.90
P2 (40% of F load)	106.00	94.00	101.60	62.20	62.40	62.00	41.60	43.40	39.60
P1 value	16.02	16.12	16.37	16.50	14.38	14.43	13.94	13.98	13.97
P2 value	68.00	68.46	69.50	58.20	57.42	57.72	55.81	55.96	55.90
d1 value	1.54	1.53	1.62	1.54	1.37	1.74	1.65	1.58	1.54
d2 value	2.00	2.00	1.97	1.98	1.90	2.28	2.28	2.21	2.17
MOE (MPa)	1981.12	1913.89	2507.04	1656.56	1414.30	1400.63	1101.12	1109.08	1111.74
Average MOE (MPa)	2134.02	±	187.52	1490.50	±	83.12	1107.31	±	3.19
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)									
Length (mm)	50.02	50.01	50.00	50.18	50.06	49.82	49.94	50.11	50.54
Width (mm)	49.75	50.14	50.18	49.90	49.92	49.91	50.21	50.24	50.23
Thickness (mm)	9.89	9.93	10.06	9.90	9.89	9.89	10.03	10.04	10.02
weight (g)	21.10	21.00	21.10	22.00	21.50	22.00	23.45	23.30	23.50
Density (kg/m³)	857.33	843.39	835.96	887.48	869.91	894.61	932.40	921.82	923.85
Average density (kg/m³)	845.56	±	6.27	884.00	±	7.34	926.03	±	3.24
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.									
Failure load (N)	2410.00	2487.00	2455.00	2801.00	2807.00	2831.00	2887.00	2950.00	2965.00
IB (MPa)	0.97	0.99	0.98	1.12	1.12	1.14	1.15	1.17	1.17
Average IB (MPa)	0.98	±	0.01	1.13	±	0.01	1.16	±	0.01
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)									
Mass before dry (g)	19.77	20.10	19.78	23.50	22.50	22.45	21.00	21.21	22.50
Mass after dry (g)	17.95	18.30	17.30	20.61	19.73	19.60	18.59	18.72	19.76
Moisture content (%)	10.14%	9.84%	14.34%	14.02%	14.04%	14.54%	12.96%	13.30%	13.87%
Average MC (%)	11.44%	±	1.45%	14.20%	±	0.17%	13.38%	±	0.26%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.									
Thickness before (mm)	9.89	9.93	10.06	9.91	9.90	9.89	10.04	10.03	10.02
Thickness after (mm)	11.00	11.00	11.00	10.80	10.90	10.80	10.80	10.70	10.90
Thickness swelling (%)	11.22%	10.78%	9.34%	8.98%	10.10%	9.20%	7.57%	6.68%	8.78%
Average TS (%)	10.45%	±	0.57%	9.43%	±	0.34%	7.68%	±	0.61%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.									

Table C.11: Olive seed tannin system with virgin and recycled wood particles

Olive seed tannin system (System 7)						
Particleboard number	71			72		
Dry contents (w/w)	65% (wt.) of virgin wood particles			65% (wt.) of recycled wood particles		
	35% (wt.) of live seed tannin			35% (wt.) of olive seed tannin		
Sample number	711	712	713	721	722	723
Length (mm)	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00	200.00
Width (mm)	50.10	49.79	50.10	49.85	49.88	49.79
Thickness (mm)	10.03	10.02	10.03	9.76	9.79	9.78
Span (mm)	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00	150.00
Failure load (N)	175.00	177.00	171.00	232.00	231.65	228.53
MOR (MPa)	7.81	7.97	7.63	10.99	10.90	10.80
Average MOR (MPa)	7.80	±	0.10	10.90	±	0.06
MOR should be 8 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (13 or over for Type 13 and 18 or over for Type 18.)						
P1 (10% of F load)	17.50	17.70	17.10	23.20	23.17	22.85
P2 (40% of F load)	70.00	70.80	68.40	92.80	92.66	91.41
P1 value	15.52	16.73	16.11	23.24	23.15	22.84
P2 value	62.30	66.40	64.42	92.75	92.65	91.43
d1 value	1.24	1.27	1.30	1.40	1.59	1.60
d2 value	1.67	1.74	1.71	2.01	2.14	2.19
MOE (MPa)	1815.79	1780.18	1966.65	2074.52	2278.04	2106.03
Average MOE (MPa)	1854.21	±	57.15	2152.86	±	63.25
MOE should be 2000 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (2500 or over for Type 13 and 3000 or over for Type 18.)						
Length (mm)	49.97	50.12	50.01	50.12	50.13	50.21
Width (mm)	50.10	49.79	50.1	49.85	49.88	49.79
Thickness (mm)	10.03	10.02	10.03	9.76	9.79	9.78
weight (g)	17.89	17.57	17.04	19.32	19.65	19.83
Density (kg/m³)	712.46	702.67	678.07	792.28	802.70	811.06
Average density (kg/m³)	697.73	±	10.23	802.02	±	5.43
Density should be 400 or over up to 900 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.						
Failure load (N)	423.00	431.00	421.50	549.00	542.50	547.14
IB (MPa)	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.22	0.22	0.22
Average IB (MPa)	0.17	±	0.00	0.22	±	0.00
IB should be 0.15 or over for Type 8 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. (0.2 or over for Type 13 and 0.3 or over for Type 18.)						
Mass before dry (g)	21.46	21.65	21.43	19.00	19.60	19.70
Mass after dry (g)	18.65	18.43	18.82	17.00	17.54	17.56
Moisture content (%)	15.07%	17.47%	13.87%	11.76%	11.74%	12.19%
Average MC (%)	15.47%	±	1.06%	11.90%	±	0.14%
Moisture content should be 5 or over up to 13 for all the Types classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications.						
Thickness before (mm)	10.03	10.02	10.03	9.76	9.79	9.78
Thickness after (mm)	11.27	11.21	11.15	11.27	11.21	11.15
Thickness swelling (%)	12.36%	11.88%	11.17%	15.47%	14.50%	14.01%
Average TS (%)	11.80%	±	0.35%	14.66%	±	0.43%
Thickness swelling should be 12 or under for Type 13 and 18 classification of JIS A 5908:2015 specifications. Any value for Type 8 classification.						

Table C.12: Working and strength properties of adhesives, with typical uses Type [368, 369]

Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Natural origin				
Animal, protein	Solid and liquid; brown to white bondline	Solid form added to water, soaked, and melted; adhesive kept warm during application; liquid form applied directly; both pressed at room temperature; bonding process must be adjusted for small changes in temperature	High dry strength; low resistance to water and damp atmosphere	Assembly of furniture and stringed instruments; repairs of antique furniture
Blood, protein	Solid and partially dried whole blood; dark red to black bondline	Mixed with cold water, lime, caustic soda, and other chemicals; applied at room temperature; pressed either at room temperature or 120° C (250° F) and higher	High dry strength; moderate resistance to water and damp atmosphere and to microorganisms	Interior-type softwood plywood, sometimes in combination with soybean adhesive; mostly replaced by phenolic adhesive

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Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Casein, protein	Powder with added chemicals; white to tan bondline	Mixed with water; applied and pressed at room temperature	High dry strength; moderate resistance to water, damp atmospheres, and intermediate temperatures; not suitable for exterior uses	Interior doors; discontinued use in laminated timbers
Soybean, protein	Powder with added chemicals; white to tan, similar colour in bondline	Mixed with cold water, lime, caustic soda, and other chemicals; applied and pressed at room temperatures, but more frequently hot pressed when blended with blood adhesive	Moderate to low dry strength; moderate to low resistance to water and damp atmospheres; moderate resistance to intermediate temperatures	Softwood plywood for interior use, now replaced by phenolic adhesive. New fast-setting resorcinol-soybean adhesives for finger jointing of lumber being developed
Lignocellulosic residues and extracts	Powder or liquid; may be blended with phenolic adhesive; dark brown bondline	Blended with extender and filler by user; adhesive cured in hot-press 130 °C to 150 °C (266 °F to 300 °F) similar to phenolic adhesive	Good dry strength; moderate to good wet strength; durability improved by blending with phenolic adhesive	Partial replacement for phenolic adhesive in composite and plywood panel products
Synthetic origin				

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Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Cross-linkable polyvinyl acetate emulsion	Liquid, similar to polyvinyl acetate emulsions but includes copolymers capable of cross-linking with a separate catalyst; white to tan with colourless bondline	Liquid emulsion mixed with a catalyst; cure at room temperature or at elevated temperature in hot press and radio-frequency press	High dry strength; improved resistance to moisture and elevated temperatures, particularly long-term performance in a moist environment	interior and exterior doors; moulding and architectural woodwork; cellulosic overlays
Elastomeric contact	Viscous liquid, typically neoprene or styrene butadiene elastomers in an organic solvent or water emulsion; tan to yellow	Liquid applied directly to both surfaces, partially dried after spreading and before pressing; roller-pressing at room temperature produces instant bonding	Strength develops immediately upon pressing, in-creases slowly over a period of weeks; dry strengths much lower than those of conventional wood adhesives; low resistance to water and damp atmospheres; adhesive film readily yields under static load	On-the-job bonding of decorative tops to kitchen counters; factory lamination of wood, paper, metal, and plastic sheet materials

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Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Elastomeric mastic (construction adhesive)	Putty like consistency, synthetic or natural elastomers in an organic solvent or latex emulsions; tan, yellow, grey	Mastic extruded in bead to framing members by caulking gun or like pressure equipment; nailing required to hold materials in place during setting and service	Strength develops slowly over several weeks; dry strength lower than conventional wood adhesives; resistant to water and moist atmospheres; tolerant of outdoor assembly conditions; gap-filling; nailing required to ensure structural integrity	Lumber to plywood in floor and wall systems; laminating gypsum board and rigid foam insulating; assembly of panel system in manufactured homes
Emulsion polymer /isocyanate	Liquid emulsion and separate isocyanate hardener; white with hardener; colourless bondline	Emulsion and hardener mixed by the user; reactive on mixing with controllable pot-life and curing time; cured at room and elevated temperatures; radio-frequency curable; high pressure required	High dry and wet strength; very resistant to water and damp atmosphere; very resistant to prolonged and repeated wetting and drying; adheres to metals and plastics	Laminated beams for interior and exterior use; lamination of plywood to steel metals and plastics; doors and architectural materials

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Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Epoxy	Liquid resin and hardener supplied as two parts; completely reactive leaving no free solvent; clear to amber; colourless bondline	Resin and hardener mixed by the user; reactive with limited pot-life; cured at room or elevated temperatures; only low pressure required for bond development	High dry and wet strength to wood, metal, glass, and plastic; formulations for wood resist water and damp atmospheres; delaminate with repeated wetting and drying; gap-filling	Laminating veneer and lumber in cold-moulded wood boat hulls; assembly of wood components in aircraft; lamination of architectural railings and posts; repair of laminated wood beams and architectural building components; laminating sports equipment; general purpose home and shop
Hot melt	Solid blocks, pellets, ribbons, rods, or films; solvent-free; white to tan; near colourless bondline	Solid form melted for spreading; bond formed on solidification; requires special application equipment for controlling melt and flow	Develops strength quickly on cooling; lower strength than conventional wood adhesives; moderate resistance to moisture; gap-filling with minimal penetration	Edge-banding of panels; plastic lamination; patching; film and paper overlays; furniture assembly; general purpose home and shop

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Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Isocyanate	Liquid containing isomers and oligomers of methylene diphenyl diisocyanate; light brown liquid and clear bondline	Adhesive applied directly by spray; reactive with water; requires high temperature and high pressure for best bond development in flake boards	High dry and wet strength; very resistant to water and damp atmosphere; adheres to metals and plastics	Flakeboards; strand-wood products
Melamine and melamine-urea	Powder with a blended catalyst; may be blended up to 40% with urea; white to tan; colourless bondline	Mixed with water; cured in hot press at 120 °C to 150 °C (250 °F to 300 °F); particularly suited for fast curing in high-frequency presses	High dry and wet strength; very resistant to water and damp atmospheres	Melamine-urea primary adhesive for durable bonds in hardwood plywood; end-jointing and edge-glueing of lumber; and scarf joining softwood plywood
Phenolic	Liquid, powder, and dry film; dark red bondline	Liquid blended with extenders and fillers by the user; film inserted directly between laminates; powder applied directly to flakes in composites; all formulations cured in hot press at 120 °C to 150 °C (250 °F to 300 °F) up to 200 °C (392 °F) in flakeboards	High dry and wet strength; very resistant to water and damp atmospheres; more resistant than wood to high temperatures and chemical ageing	Primary adhesive for exterior softwood plywood, flakeboard, and hardboard Furniture;

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Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Polyvinyl acetate emulsion	Liquid ready to use; often polymerised with other polymers; white to tan to yellow; colourless bondline	Liquid applied directly; pressed at room temperatures and in high-frequency press	High dry strength; low resistance to moisture and elevated temperatures; joints yield under continued stress	Furniture; flush doors; plastic laminates; penalised floor and wall systems in manufactured housing; general-purpose in-home and shop
Polyurethane	Low viscosity liquid to high viscosity mastic; supplied as one part; two-part systems completely reactive; colour varies from clear to brown; colourless bondline	Adhesive applied directly to one surface, preferably to water- misted surface; reactive with moisture on the surface and in the air; cures at room temperature; high pressure required, but mastic required only pressure from nailing	High dry and wet strength; resistant to water and damp atmosphere; limited resistance to prolonged and repeated wetting and drying; gap-filling	General purpose home and shop; construction adhesive for penalised floor and wall systems; laminating plywood to metal and plastic sheet materials; speciality laminates; installation of gypsum board
Resorcinol and phenol-resorcinol	Liquid resin and powdered hardener supplied as two parts; phenol may be copolymerised with resorcinol; dark red bondline	Liquid mixed with powdered or liquid hardener; resorcinol adhesives cure at room temperatures; phenol-resorcinols cure at temperatures from 21 °C to 66 °C (70 °F to 150 °F)	High dry and wet strength; very resistant to moisture and damp atmospheres; more resistant than wood to high temperature and chemical ageing	Primary adhesives for laminated timbers and assembly joints that must withstand severe service conditions.

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Type	Form and colour	Preparation and application	Strength properties	Typical uses
Urea	Powder and liquid forms; may be blended with melamine or other more durable resins; white to tan resin with colourless bondline	Powder mixed with water, hardener, filler, and extender by the user; some formulations cure at room temperatures, others require hot pressing at 120 °C (250 °F); curable with high-frequency heating	High dry and wet strength; moderately durable under damp atmospheres; moderate to low resistance to temperatures in excess of 50 °C (122 °F)	Hardwood plywood; furniture; fiberboard; particleboard; underlayment; flush doors; furniture cores

Appendix D

An appendix

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Glossary

Absorption

The process by which one thing absorbs or is absorbed by another.

Adherend

The surface to which an adhesive adheres.

Adsorption

The process by which a solid holds molecules of a gas or liquid or solute as a thin film.

Analogy

A comparison between one thing and another, typically for the purpose of explanation or clarification.

Anisotropic

An object or substance having a physical property which has a different value when measured in different directions.

Biocide

A poisonous substance, especially a pesticide.

Bondline

The layer of adhesive which attaches two adherends. The interface between an adhesive and an adherend.

Butt joint

A joint made by bonding two surfaces that are perpendicular to the main surface of the adherends.

Cellulose

An insoluble substance which is the main constituent of plant cell walls and of vegetable fibres.

Chemical cure

Mode of setting or polymerisation.

Coagulation

The action or process of a liquid, especially blood, changing to a solid or semi-solid state.

Cocondensation

Two simultaneous condensation reactions.

Condensation

Water which collects as droplets on a cold surface when humid air is in contact with it.

Cross-link

A chemical bond between different chains of atoms in a polymer or other complex molecule.

Curing

Harden (rubber, plastic, concrete, etc.) after manufacture by a chemical process such as vulcanisation.

Curing temperature

The temperature to which an adhesive or an assembly is subjected to cure the adhesive. The temperature attained by the adhesive in the process of curing, it (adhesive curing temperature) may differ from the temperature of the atmosphere surrounding the assembly (assembly curing temperature).

Curing time

The period of time during which an assembly is subjected to heat or pressure, or both, to cure the adhesive.

Further cure may take place after removal of the assembly from the conditions of heat, or pressure, or both.

Degradation

The process in which the beauty or quality of something is destroyed or spoiled.

Denaturation of protein

Disruption and possible destruction of both the secondary and tertiary structures.

Depolymerisation

The process of converting a polymer into a monomer or a mixture of monomers.

Diatomaceous earth

A naturally occurring, soft, siliceous sedimentary rock that is easily crumbled into a fine white to off-white powder.

Diffusion

The spreading of something more widely.

Discrepancis

An illogical or surprising lack of compatibility or similarity between two or more facts.

Dowel

A projecting peg used for holding together components of a structure.

Eco-innovation

Development of products and processes that contribute to sustainable development, applying the commercial application of knowledge to elicit direct or indirect ecological improvements.

Elastic modulus

See **Storage modulus**

Elastomer

Natural or Synthetic polymer having elastic properties.

Elastomeric

Polymeric with viscoelasticity.

Electrostatic

Relating to stationary electric charges or fields as opposed to electric currents.

Emulsion

A stable dispersion of two or more immiscible liquids held in suspension by small percentages of substances called emulsifiers.

Endothermic

Accompanied by or requiring the absorption of heat.

Epichlorohydrin

An organochlorine compound and an epoxide.

Exfoliate

material being shed from a surface in scales or layers.

Exothermic

Accompanied by the release of heat.

Fermentation

The chemical breakdown of a substance by bacteria, yeasts, or other microorganisms, typically involving effervescence and the giving off of heat.

Formaldehyde

A colourless pungent gas in solution made by oxidizing methanol.

Fungicide

Biocidal chemical compounds or biological organisms used to kill parasitic fungi or their spores.

Gel point

An abrupt change in the viscosity of a solution containing polymerisable components.

Glass-transition temperature T_g

The temperature region where the polymer transitions from a hard, glassy material to a soft, rubbery material.

Glucomanan

Water-soluble polysaccharide that is considered a dietary fibre. A Solution undergoes gelation at the gel point.

Glulam

A type of structural engineered wood product comprising a number of layers of dimensional lumber bonded together with durable, moisture-resistant structural adhesives.

Graft copolymerisation

Grafting one or more blocks of homopolymer as branches onto a main chain.

Hardwood

The wood from a broadleaved tree (such as oak, ash, or beech) as distinguished from that of conifers.

Heartwood

The dense inner part of a tree trunk, yielding the hardest timber.

Hemicellulose

Any of a class of substances which occur as constituents of the cell walls of plants and are polysaccharides of simpler structure than cellulose.

Holocellulose

The total polysaccharide fraction of wood or straw and the like that is made up of cellulose and all of the hemicelluloses and that is obtained by removing the extractives and the lignin from the original natural material.

Hydrolysis

The chemical breakdown of a compound due to reaction with water.

Hydrothermal

Relating to or denoting the action of heated water in the earth's crust.

Hygroscopic

A substance tending to absorb moisture from the air.

Imaginary modulus

See **Loss modulus**

In-phase modulus

See **Storage modulus**

Infiltration

The spread of a tumour, cells, tissue

Interlocking

Two or more things having parts that overlap or fit together.

Lignin

A complex organic polymer deposited in the cell walls of many plants, making them rigid and woody.

Lignosulfonate

A by-product of the sulphite method for manufacturing paper from wood pulp. Sometimes it is called sulphonated lignin.

Liquefaction

A useful method of turning whole biomass into liquids.

Loss modulus

The energy lost to friction and internal motions. So-called viscous or imaginary modulus. It is a measure of the deformation energy used in the sample during the shear process and then lost, reflecting the viscous behaviour of a sample.

Lumber

A type of wood that has been processed into beams and planks

Lumens

The inside space of a tubular structure, such as an artery or intestine.

Mannan

Any of several polysaccharides that are polymers of mannose and occur especially in plant cell walls and in some microorganisms.

Microfibril

A very fine fibril, or fibre-like strand, consisting of glycoproteins and cellulose.

Microorganism

A microscopic organism, especially a bacterium, virus, or fungus.

Miscible

Forming a homogeneous mixture when added together.

Modulus of Elasticity

The ratio of stress to strain in elastically deformed material.

Monomer

A molecule that can be bonded to other identical molecules to form a polymer.

Orthotopic

Relating to the grafting of tissue in a natural position.

Pectin

Naturally occurring substance (a polysaccharide) found in berries, apples and other fruit.

Penetration

The passage of an adhesive into an adherend.

Permeability

Capable of being permeated or passed through

Polyaddition

Polyaddition reactions are chemical reactions in which the polymer is originated by successive additions of functional groups (monomer A) inside of molecular structures with double bonds (monomer B).

Polycondensation

Polymers formed as a result of reactions involving the condensation of organic materials in which small molecules are split out.

Polymer

A compound formed by the reaction of simple molecules having functional groups which permit their combination to proceed to higher molecular

weights under suitable conditions. Polymers may be formed by polymerisation (addition polymers) or poly-condensation (condensation polymers). When two or more different monomers are involved, the product is a copolymer.

Polymerise

Combine or cause to combine to form a polymer.

Polyol

An organic compound containing multiple hydroxyl groups.

Polyurethane

A polymer composed of organic units joined by carbamate (urethane) links.

Porosity

The ability of an adherend to absorb an adhesive.

Pot life (working life)

The period of time during which an adhesive or resin prepared for application after mixing with catalyst, solvent, or other compounding ingredients, remains usable. The effective working time for an adhesive after preparation; interval before the adhesive system becomes unusable through an increase in viscosity or curing.

Pozzolanic activity

A measure for the degree of reaction over time or the reaction rate between a pozzolan and Ca_2^+ or calcium hydroxide $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the presence of water.

Pressure-sensitive adhesives

Adhesive materials which bond to adherend surfaces at room temperature immediately as low pressure is applied. Adhesives which require only pressure application to effect permanent adhesion to an adherend.

Proline

An amino acid which is a constituent of most proteins, especially collagen.

Pyrolysis

Decomposition brought about by high temperatures.

Radical

An atom, molecule, or ion that has an unpaired valence electron.

Real modulus

See **Storage modulus**.

Rheology

The science of deformation and flow of matter.

Resilience

The ability of a substance or object to spring back into shape; elasticity.

Resin

A solid, semisolid, or pseudosolid organic material that has an indefinite and often high molecular weight, exhibits a tendency to flow when subjected to stress, usually has a softening or melting range, and usually fractures conchoidally. A liquid resin is an organic polymeric liquid which, when converted to its final state for use, becomes a resin.

Rosin

A resin obtained as a residue in the distillation of crude turpentine from the sap of the pine tree (gum rosin), or from an extract of the stumps and other parts of the tree (wood rosin).

Sapwood

The soft outer layers of recently formed wood between the heartwood and the bark, containing the functioning vascular tissue.

Scavenger

A substance that reacts with and removes particular molecules, groups, etc.

Sealant

A gap-filling material to prevent excessive absorption of adhesive, or penetration of liquid or gaseous substances.

Shear thinning

The non-Newtonian behaviour of fluids whose viscosity decreases under shear strain. It is sometimes considered synonymous for pseudoplastic behaviour, and is usually defined as excluding time-dependent effects, such as thixotropy.

Slender

Small width relative to length or height

Softwood

The wood from a conifer (such as pine, fir, or spruce) as distinguished from that of broadleaved trees.

Solid content

Describes how much water you can expect in your water-based adhesive. Most typical adhesives have a solid content around 50%. Starch based adhesives mostly have a solid content of 5-20% and some synthetic products up to 80 or 90%. Dextrin based adhesives can be around 70% solid content. Animal-glue (gelatin, protein adhesive) mostly has a solid content of 60-70%. These adhesives have an application temperature of ca. 70 degrees Celsius.

Steric Hindrance

At a given atom in a molecule is the congestion caused by the physical presence of the surrounding ligands, which may slow down or prevent reactions at the atom.

Stiasney number

The ratio of the oven-dried weight of the precipitate to the total dissolved solids content of the tannin extract expressed as a percentage.

Storage life

The period of time during which a packaged adhesive can be stored under specified temperature conditions and remain suitable for use. Sometimes called shelf life. Refrigerated storage often extends storage life considerably.

Storage modulus

The motion of the polymer molecule which follows the macroscopic deformation, thus it is elastic and stores some of the deformation energy. So-called elastic modulus, in-phase modulus, real modulus. It is a measure of the deformation energy stored in the sample during the shear process.

Storage stability

Providing evidence on how the quality of a product varies with time under the influence of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and light.

Thermoplastic

Denoting substances (especially synthetic resins) that become plastic on heating and harden on cooling, and are able to repeat these processes.

Thermosetting

Denoting substances (especially synthetic resins) which set permanently when heated.

Tomography

A technique for displaying a representation of a cross section through a human body or other solid object using X-rays or ultrasound.

Tracheid

A type of water-conducting cell in the xylem which lacks perforations in the cell wall.

Vessel

The water conducting tissue of plants.

Vitrification

The transformation of a substance into

a glass, that is to say a non-crystalline amorphous solid.

Viscosity

The state of being thick, sticky, and semi-fluid in consistency, due to internal friction.

Viscouse modulus

See **Loss modulus**

Wetting

The process in which a liquid spontaneously adheres to and spreads on a solid surface. A surface is said to be completely wet by a liquid if the contact angle is zero, and incompletely wet if it is a finite angle. Surfaces are commonly regarded as unwettable if the angle exceeds 90°.

Xylan

Yellow gummy pentosan that yields xylose on hydrolysis and is abundantly present in plant cell walls and woody tissue.

Xyloglucans

Members of a group of polysaccharides typically referred to as hemicelluloses.

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